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**DigitalJobsPH as Tool for the Philippine Countryside Digitalization:
An Evaluation of a Government Initiative
for Countryside Development**

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Acceptance

This Thesis titled DigitalJobsPH as Tool for the Philippine Countryside Digitalization: An Evaluation of a Government Initiative for Countryside Development is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Development Communication (MDC).

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Biographical Sketch

Joshua Eleazar Domen has been working in the ICT industry since time immemorial and is inclined as to how technology plays an important role in shaping the country's development.

The author finished his BS Information Technology degree from St. Paul University Dumaguete in 2012. He landed to numerous ICT-related jobs, from being an IT instructor; to an unsung copyeditor for IT books, journals, and articles; to a Technical Support Engineer; and to a Project Development Officer. He currently works as an Information Technology Officer for the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) and has been in the department based in Cebu City since 2018.

He is an active learner and was awarded as one of the Ten Outstanding Students of the Philippines – Central Visayas (Region 7) and was a finalist to the national search held in Malacañang Palace in 2012. He represented the country in various international programs including Singapore, Malaysia, Japan, and India.

As someone coming from the province, he values the importance of ICT in areas that are far flung and may not be of reach for an Internet connectivity. He advocates for a “digital literacy for all” and believes that in becoming computer literate, no one must be left behind.

He acknowledges major cities like Manila, Cebu, and Davao as IT-BPM destinations and major ICT hubs but aspires for other areas, especially those in the countryside, to experience the same.

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Dedicated to:

My family and friends
and to all OFW 2.0 (Online Filipino Workers)

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
BIR	Bureau of Internal Revenue
BPO	Business Process Outsourcing
DICT	Department of Information and Communications Technology
DJT	DigitalJobsPH Training
DOST	Department of Science and Technology
DTI	Department of Trade and Industry
IBPAP	IT and Business Process Association of the Philippines
IIDB	ICT Industry Development Bureau
ILCDB	ICT Literacy Competency Development Bureau
IT-BPM	Information Technology-Business Process Management
MSMEs	Micro, small, and medium enterprises
OSYs	Out-of-School Youths
PISCON	Philippine Impact Sourcing Conference
PWDs	Persons with Disabilities
RIS	Rural Impact Sourcing
SCs	Senior Citizens
TESDA	Technical Education and Skills Development Authority
VC2	Visayas Cluster 2

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Rural Impact Sourcing (RIS), now DigitalJobsPH Training (DJT), was launched in 2017 by DICT to provide technical training and non-formal education to the rural areas of the country; however, since it is still on its infancy stage, a lot has to be done and more locations need to be considered for implementation to cover the entire archipelago and reach out to more marginalized yet deserving Filipinos.

According to the data gathered from the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) – ICT Industry Development Bureau, in 2017, 196 graduates were recorded to have been working online. In 2018, of the 1023 total number of graduates in 68 nationwide locations set for that year, 399 have been recorded to have online jobs. A total of Php 2,731,328 income has been raised among the graduates with online jobs, a total accumulation during and after their training. Six hundred forty-five MSMEs partnered with DTI have been helped with the digital marketing course. Of this, Php 26, 435, 501.95 is the total amount generated by the MSMEs that were partnered with the trainees.

There were 68 actual locations for 2018, of which only 65 were originally set as target locations for the year. That makes up to 105% of the original plan. Sixteen companies were established by the DJT graduates themselves.

For 2017 and 2018 data, 95 locations were established. So far, there have been 1832 graduates and 595 of which have landed with online jobs and a total of 40 companies were established by the DJT graduates, 1089 MSMEs have been assisted,

and Php 35,591,296.70 worth of sales has been generated by these MSMEs where the DJT scholars worked for.

For 2019, 96 locations had been set with 2112 graduates estimated to graduate (22-25 per location), 1 rural BPO group/company for each location should be established, and 25% of the total number of graduates should have online jobs.

A long-term goal for 2022 has been eyed with 10,000 graduates, 500 DJT Hubs (a facility in their locality where DJT technical training graduates can work on 24/7), and 3000 MSMEs helped.

For Region 7 and Region 8 alone, 46 graduated from 3 locations in 2017, 212 graduated from 10 locations in 2018, and 325 graduated from 17 locations in 2019.

It is safe to assume that with the increasing number of successful DJT graduates being produced year by year, the DJT program of the DICT's ICT Industry Development Bureau (IIDB) has provided an impactful approach in addressing the advancement of IT-BPM industry in the countryside, regardless of how far they are from the major cities and IT-BPM hubs of Manila, Cebu and Davao.

Background of the Study

Impact sourcing is defined as the practice of bringing digitally enabled outsourcing jobs to marginalized individuals (Sandeep, 2015). Also known as socially responsible outsourcing, it is an arm of the business process outsourcing (BPO) industry that employs socioeconomically disadvantaged individuals as a major workforce in providing information-based services to local and global clients. While the traditional BPO sector involves constructing massive infrastructure and infostructure

and employing workers with significant levels of education and language literacy, impact sourcing focuses on utilizing workers from poor and vulnerable communities to perform information services regardless of location or education, for as long as there is presence of stable Internet connection.

Only major cities in the Philippines are advantaged with high IT-BPM jobs and opportunities available for grabs. Manila ranks second in Tholons Super Cities list for 2018, an index measuring cities' competitiveness in doing IT-BPM services, while Cebu at 11th and Davao at 75th. As far-flung towns and rural communities are not reached with these opportunities, how can rural areas perform, provide, and catch up with the growing IT-BPM industry?

In 2017, the ICT Industry Development Bureau (IIDB) of the Department of Information and Communication Technology (DICT) tried to address this challenge by implementing then the Rural Impact Sourcing (RIS) Technical Training nationwide, providing a comprehensive 21-day training for selected scholars interested in undergoing such workshop. In 2019, the name of the program was rebranded and since then, RIS has been known as DigitalJobsPH (DJT). Different DJT sites or locations throughout the country are selected and the training is done there, bringing technical training to these rural areas. Part of the trainees' completion requirements is to work real time with micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) by developing the latter's website. Basically, DJT tries to help address unemployment through the online freelancing industry. IIDB is under the Countryside and ICT Developments and Innovations arm of DICT.

Ever since its inception, and although it is still on its infancy stage, DJT has trained thousands of graduates and opened opportunities for employment. DJT has

also empowered local talents and IT-BPM-underprivileged areas, especially those that are far from major cities. The DJT graduates need not leave the comfort of their homes, and their families, to perform work.

On July 17, 2019, during the 3rd Philippine Impact Sourcing Conference (PISCON) that was held in Clark, Pampanga, Director Emmylou Delfin of the ICT Industry Development Bureau of the Department of Information and Communications Technology announced the changing of the name of Rural Impact Sourcing into DigitalJobsPH Technical Training. This is to align the program under the “DigitalPH” project, where other programs have also been renamed: “Stepping Up the Value Chain” into “DigitalServicesPH” and “SeedsPH” into “DigitalStartupsPH”. Meanwhile, DigitalCitiesPH retained its branding.

This study shall provide an in-depth review of what impact sourcing is as a new term in this developing digital world. It will also provide an overview of what DigitalJobsPH Technical Training is, then Rural Impact Sourcing, and evaluate how the government used this approach from 2017 to 2019 to further develop the countryside, digitally, in Regions 7 and 8. Answers to a survey questionnaire of some respondents to know how they’ve come far to the online freelancing industry after joining the training shall also be emphasized.

This is worth studying since an analysis of the government approach to DJT, including the development communication tools and processes and identification of the challenges and accomplishments of such project will be taken into consideration. DJT will also be compared and contrasted to other government projects having the same approach and goals such as those from the Department of Trade and Industry

(DTI), Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), and Department of Science and Technology (DOST).

Measuring and determining whether DJT or RIS as a government project has met its objectives of building capacities of marginalized groups towards a digital countryside and answering whether such deserves continuation will also be answered in this study. With the millions of pesos doled out to fund the DJT or RIS project, does it deserve the budget allocation?

The Research Problem

This study seeks to find answers if there is a significant relationship between DigitalJobsPH, an online freelancing training provided by DICT, and a digital countryside, among the members of marginalized groups in Region 7 and 8.

Since the inception of the DigitalJobsPH program in 2017 spearheaded by DICT, 583 trainees around Central and Eastern Visayas have availed of the cluster implementation of the training.

These trainees come from the marginalized group, which are the priority beneficiaries of DICT: out-of-school youths (OSYs), unemployed, underemployed, students who can commit to join the training, persons with disabilities (PWDs), and senior citizens (SCs).

The status of some of the training graduates shall be the primary focus of the study. How have they been doing after the training? Have they landed into online jobs, which is the training's core? Do they have online presence?

Is DigitalJobsPh an effective tool in building the capacities of the marginalized sector and in pushing for a digital countryside?

Furthermore, the following research questions are considered:

1. Has DICT been an enabler enough in providing opportunities for other locations in the country?
2. Given the limitations of hosting the IT-BPM industry in far-flung areas and communities, can local government units still be able to support these kinds of operations through the DigitalJobsPH training initiated by DICT?
3. Has DigitalJobsPH been effective and has it met its objectives?

Objectives of the Study

At the end of this study, the following objectives should be accomplished:

1. Describe Rural Impact Sourcing Technical Training (now DigitalJobsPH) and what it intends to accomplish in terms of countryside IT-BPM development and determine who can benefit from such
2. Determine whether DJT has met its objectives of capacitating the marginalized sector in the rural communities, leading to a digital countryside, over the years as a government project in Region 7 and 8
3. Determine whether DJT deserves continuation or halt through the training graduates' responses to open-ended questions
4. Recommend means to improve DJT towards achieving its objectives of a digital countryside

Significance of the Study

For 2019, a budget of Php 50,789,327 has been allocated by the ICT Industry Development Bureau (IIDB) of DICT for the conduct of DJT alone, which includes intentions for trainings, monitoring and development, assessment and planning, regional activities, and professional fees. This is a huge amount of sum, and it is important to have this study conducted to know if DJT deserves such allocation. As this is government money, it is important to know if DJT accomplishes its targets and mandates and realizes the goals that it is tasked to achieve.

This study shall become an avenue to highlight the importance of the DJT program and realize its roles to countryside development through communication.

DJT, just like the Department of Information Technology where it belongs, is still on its infancy stage. With this study, it will be evaluated to know whether it has become effective in the recent years that it has been waving.

This study can contribute to further the development of DJT and can help DICT in terms of evaluation, assessment, and management of its brainchild. Improvement can be made by DICT, and to a certain extent, other government agencies, in terms of the ways they handle development projects and programs as this study aims to do so.

Limitations of the Study

This study is representative of the DigitalJobsPH Technical Training's campaign in Central Visayas (Region 7) and Eastern Visayas (Region 8) for the past years that the program has been promulgated.

Respondents were from these two regions that, in 2019, have the most number of technical trainings that were conducted in comparison to all other regions in the country.

Metro Cebu, located in Region 7, is one of the Centers of Excellence in the IT-BPM industry and is a model for other cities to follow that wish to embrace IT-BPM as a source of income. Cebu City is noted to have the very first IT Council in the country. The Cebu IT BPM.Org (CIB.O) traces its roots in 2001 as the Cebu Educational Development Foundation for Information Technology (CEDFIT), where the organization supports various initiatives and programs that will enhance the ICT potentials in the area. Academes, companies, industry sectors, and government agencies make up the organization.

It is no surprise that Cebu City is one of the leaders in the ICT sector. As a matter of fact, the first Internet connection in the country was first established in the city. On March 29, 1994, at 10:18 am, the country first connected to the world wide web through a 64 kbps link to Sprint, an Internet service provider in the US, at the University of San Carlos in Talamban, Cebu City.

Dumaguete City, the capital city of Negros Oriental, has been hailed as one of the Next-Wave Cities in the country, along with nine other cities. These cities make up what would be the next IT hubs and top locations for local and international IT-BPM players, apart from the centers of excellence like Metro Manila, Metro Cebu, and Metro Davao. Being a university town, the City of Gentle People has catered to 12,000 full-time BPO employees.

On June 30, 2020, through an online launch, Tagbilaran City, Bohol, and Tacloban City, Leyte, have been named as part of the 25 Digital Cities 2025, as

announced by the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) and the Information Technology and Business Process Association of the Philippines (IBPAP) (Figure 2.3). These cities constitute the priority cities that are deemed as the next destinations for the IT-BPM sector to grow, having the potentials to support this industry.

These cities and provinces in the region have been the beneficiaries of DICT Visayas Cluster 2's DJT program for the past years.

The study included Regions 7 and 8 only and respondents were from the graduates of 2017 to 2019 training programs.

Figure 1.1 – IBPAP and DICT’s 25 Digital Cities 2025, announced through an online launch on June 30, 2020 through Facebook Live. These cities have the potential to become the next IT hubs in the country and in the next few years until 2025, they shall be the focus of various events and activities by DICT that will strengthen their ICT ecosystem. (IBPAP, 2020)

Theoretical Framework

DigitalJobsPH is a rebranded name of the original program which was known as Rural Impact Sourcing. Thus, a theory that the researcher can attribute this study to is the Impact Sourcing Theory of Change.

The Theory of Change (TOC) can be traced back in 1954 by Peter Drucker that emerged as a new way of analyzing motivating programs and initiatives working for social and political change. It focuses on not just generating knowledge about whether a program is effective but also on explaining what methods it uses to be effective. Carol Weiss popularized the term “Theory of Change” as a way to describe the set of assumptions that explain both the mini-steps that lead to the long-term goal of interest and the connections between program activities and outcomes that occur at each step of the way. Weiss challenged designers of complex community-based initiatives to be specific about the theories of change guiding their work and suggested that doing so would improve their overall evaluation plans and would strengthen their ability to claim credit for outcomes that were predicted in their theory.

The Center for Theory of Change defines TOC as a specific and measurable description of a social change initiative that forms the basis for strategic planning, ongoing decision-making, and evaluation. According to the body, “Like any good planning and evaluation method for social change, it requires participants to be clear on long-term goals, identify measurable indicators of success, and formulate actions to achieve goals.” Furthermore, TOC differs from any other method of describing initiatives in a few ways: (1) it shows a causal pathway from here to there by specifying what is needed for goals to be achieved, (2) it requires you to articulate underlying assumptions which can be tested and measured, and (3) it changes the way of thinking about initiatives from what one is doing to what one wants to achieve and starts there.

The Global Impact Sourcing Coalition (GISC) on their working paper on *Social Impact Measurement Framework* (2019) developed the Impact Sourcing Theory of Change to achieve its objectives in developing the Impact Sourcing Measurement Framework and considered TOC as an important component to the framework. The coalition defined TOC as a theory that seeks to lay out the anticipated path to impact that a specific organization, program, or business practice – such as Impact Sourcing – follows

to achieve positive change. The Impact Sourcing Theory of Change, developed as the foundation of the framework that GISC prepared, is a further elaboration of the Impact Sourcing Value Chain. It establishes the impact objectives of Impact Sourcing and identifies drivers and inputs – investments made by buyer and supplier companies – that can be expected to result in direct outputs and lead to intended outcomes and impacts for impact workers (i.e., freelancers in the rurality), their households, and communities. The Impact Sourcing Theory of Change, explained further in the next paragraph, builds off the Impact Sourcing Standard and connects to relevant Sustainable Development Goals and Targets.

The Impact Sourcing Value Chain is also conceptualized by GISC that offers a high level overview of the activities and impacts generally expected across the actors of Impact Sourcing – a business practice where a company prioritizes suppliers that intentionally hire and provide career development opportunities to people who otherwise

have limited prospects for formal employment (i.e., Impact Workers). GISC defines Impact Workers as people hired into an organization who were previously long-term unemployed or living in poverty, which have been identified by the GISC as universal

signs of disadvantage that applies across cultural, political, and geographic contexts, and enables companies offer inclusive employment opportunities across every community they operate in.

The Impact Sourcing Value Chain

Figure 1.2 – The Global Impact Sourcing Coalition (GISC) values the Impact Sourcing Value Chain as an important component in framing the Impact Sourcing Measurement Framework. The premise highlights that when investments are forged by the buyer-supplier companies to impact workers, the household and the community of the latter also benefit from such impacts and outcomes (GISC, 2019)

GISC is founded on the premise that increased market demand for socially responsible suppliers that employ, train, and provide career opportunities for vulnerable workers will result in systemic improvement in the lives and livelihoods for impact workers, their families, and their communities. Further, as businesses and governments adopt Impact Sourcing as a priority procurement criterion, supplier organizations will seek to differentiate themselves based on their community impacts, and the supply of inclusive employment opportunities across supply chains.

Coining Impact Sourcing and TOC together, GISC lays foundation on the concept of Impact Sourcing Theory of Change as having objectives for Impact Sourcing to:

- 1) Increase access to decent work opportunities for Impact Workers** – where the provider/buyer commitments to Impact Sourcing directly increase the pool of jobs available and accessible for workers that are long –term unemployed or living in poverty, in which inclusive hiring and employment practices reduce barriers and enable success for impact workers to apply for roles, earn job offers, accept positions, and thrive in their roles
- 2) Improve well-being for Impact Workers, their households, and communities** – where decent and consistent compensation enables impact workers to increase their individual and household income and subsequently their savings and spending on critical goods and services, such as quality food, housing, and education, that promote long-term financial stability and wellbeing, in which work-related benefits such as health insurance and retirement contributions enable impact workers to bolster their individual and household resilience over the near and long terms
- 3) Enable transition beyond Impact Employment** – where on-the-job trainings (OJTs) and development programs which focus on building valuable and transferable skills enable impact workers to achieve employment stability and advance along a career path that offers them subsequent growth opportunities, in which performance management systems and feedback loops empower impact workers with the information

they need to continuously improve, and eventually transition beyond their initial impact employment role, whether by achieving long-term stability in their role, through internal promotion, or through securing external advancement opportunities.

The Impact Sourcing Theory of Change conceptualized and drafted by the Global Impact Sourcing Coalition (GICS) in 2019 is of utmost importance and value to this study as the same principle is theorized as the driver of success in shaping and building the marginalized sectors' capacities, in terms of impact sourcing and online freelancing, leading towards a digital countryside through the DigitalJobsPH training program of DICT.

This study also uses the Anchored Instruction Theory, with the DigitalJobsPH program being a training ground for would-be online freelancers that would provide opportunities for the digital countryside to prosper amid their location, where opportunities are scarce.

Such theory emphasizes technology-based learning where students take technology as the carrier, use the reality of living world as main contents to discover problems, generate questions, and ultimately solve the problems. Indeed, DJT as a training program makes use of technology to deliver its modules, with practical applications in its contents that have to be delivered by the students for them to be able to finish the training as requirements to graduate.

Anchored Instruction Theory is taking the real life of the world as the core contents of teaching through educational media. Students discover, solve problems in the various

means of the real living world. The reality of the living world is referred to as the “anchor,” and the process of establishing and identifying the real living world to solve the problems is figuratively called “casting the anchor.” “Anchored” instruction is one of critical instructional models under the constructive learning theory. It was proposed by a cognitive and technical team under the leadership of American professor John Bransford in Vanderbilt University in 1992.

For Fried et al. (2005), it is a technology-centered learning approach that falls under the social constructionism paradigm. This theory is a form of situated learning that emphasizes problem solving within an integrated learning context, which can be examined from multiple perspectives. "In other words, the learning is contextualized to provide students with realistic roles that serve to enhance the learning process" (Fried et al. 2005).

In their training, students or trainees have to finish real-world online freelancing tasks or activities provided by the trainer through technology-based education. For example, a task for a social media marketing and advertisement course is to produce daily social media posts for their partner MSME. This is the very same nature of the Anchored Instruction Theory.

Figure 1.3 – The Anchored Instruction Model by Evan Glazer (Glazer, 2016)

For a thriving IT-BPM industry, impact sourcing especially those designed to reach to the rurality is but a helping hand. For an archipelagic country that is divided by seas and mountains, the Philippines is an ideal location for rural impact sourcing initiatives to flourish.

DICT's DigitalJobsPH technical training (DJT), a project under the ICT Industry Development Bureau, is a key that unlocks the potentials of areas that are far from the major hubs. With a stable Internet connection and necessary tools, area-challenged individuals have no reason not to work online and provide not only a boost to their personal needs but to the nation's economy as well.

For more than two years now, DJT has provided success stories across the country and benefitted individuals to learn offshore freelancing jobs and then in turn earn clients that would hire them and let them earn income that is above the minimum wage, without having to leave the comfort of their homes.

Not much has been studied about DJT's extent and how much it has impacted the digital Filipinos.

From DJT graduates' meetup for all the regional clusters of DICT, many success stories have been shared by the graduates themselves. However, tracking all the graduates and checking on how they have been doing after the program is still a challenge for the agency. Future plans of a more systematic and coherent approach is currently being discussed to address this tracking initiative among the graduates of the program.

From the general impact sourcing standpoint, a few researchers have made studies about this term most especially that it's been recently coined as the digital age came in.

India, which has been the prime IT-BPM location being able to cater outsourcing jobs for its major hubs, has also been the prime mover for impact sourcing jobs.

Sandeep (2015) considers impact sourcing as bringing digitally enabled outsourcing jobs to individuals who are marginalized. A company outsources jobs for individuals who can offer services such as electronic publishing, virtual assistance, web development, data transcription, web testing, and digitization, among others. Because of the advances in information and communication technology, the possibility of impact sourcing has become more wide and more lenient than it has been a few years back. The increase in broadband connectivity in emerging economies has allowed limitless possibilities in terms of employability, even in terms of geography.

This time, geography is not an issue.

As for Sandeep, "Such unprecedented connectivity has indeed helped well-meaning entrepreneurs in the global south to help marginalized communities to participate in, and reap benefits from globalization – benefits which were hitherto accrued largely by the relatively more prosperous urban populations" (Sandeep 2015).

Companies follow this new trend of online work because, for the greatest reason, there is cost reduction – allowing more income but less expenditures from an enterprise's side – without compromising the quality of service (Accenture, 2012; Sandeep and Ravishankar, 2013; Everest, 2014).

The cost reduction principle is possible because (1) companies providing impact sourcing opportunities operate at a lower cost because these rural locations also have meager cost of living (Everest, 2014) and (2) attrition rate among the marginalized section is significantly lower, around 15-40%, compared to the attrition rates in traditional BPOs.

On the other hand, the most commonly forgotten benefit of impact sourcing is the fact that companies provide opportunities for geographically or physically challenged individuals – in a term known as corporate social responsibility.

An equally important line of discourse surrounding the model is indeed about the “impact” of impact sourcing, i.e., how marginalized populations can reap benefits from it. Preliminary evidence from academic and practitioner sources suggests that marginalized individuals employed at impact sourcing companies benefit socially and economically – with improved self-esteem, confidence, self efficacy and increased incomes (Heeks and Arun, 2010; Madon and Sharanappa, 2013; Lacity et al., 2014). Furthermore, it is claimed that communities also benefit from (1) increased economic activity in and around the areas where the impact sourcing company is located and (b) the “developmental” work undertaken by the impact sourcing company as a social commitment (Everest, 2014).

For Sandeep, the impact sourcing model is making all the right noises. It has attracted support from a variety of actors including international non-profit institutions such as The Rockefeller Foundation, who have been initiating programs and creating platforms for the growth of this model; national regional governments in India, South Africa, Kenya, Ghana, Malaysia to name a few; professional associations such as the IAOP; industry lobby groups like the National Association for Software Services

Companies (NASSCOM) of India; and academic institutions and bodies that have hosted conferences and seminars to explore the phenomenon.

In the Philippines alone, an annual Philippine Impact Sourcing Conference has made rounds for years now, highlighting the importance of impact sourcing in the country. Also, the Rural Impact Sourcing technical training initiatives of the government have been becoming a buzzword especially that LGUs want to support and echo the same kind of platform to their localities.

Indeed, the claimed potential of the impact sourcing is hard to ignore.

Currently, impact sourcing constitutes 12% of the total outsourcing market, amounting to nearly 235,000 workers in India alone. It is also growing at a faster rate than the traditional IT-BPO market (~11% year on year growth). If recent estimates are to be believed, impact sourcing can address a potential global market of US\$7.6 billion market by 2017 (NASSCOM, 2014). As a tool to provide livelihood opportunities to thousands of marginalized individuals in the global south, the impact sourcing model of contracting digital services holds immense potential. Since the services currently offered are low to medium end, impact sourcing is unlikely to completely displace traditional BPO models. However, at the same time, the impact sourcing story cannot be completely ignored as it potentially presents a unique value proposition for both clients and the community.

Given the relativity of technology-based real-life learning approach in determining the success of DJT and the Anchored Instruction Theory, such model is of value and importance to the results of this study.

Another theory that the researcher believes that this study is based upon is the recent Online Collaborative Learning (OCL) which is also known as Collaborativism, devised in 2012. OCL is a theory proposed by Linda Harasim that focuses on the facilities of the Internet to provide learning environments that foster collaboration and knowledge building. DJT, as a training program, is highly dependent on the use of the Internet as tasks themselves provided by the trainer (facilitator) to the students or trainees rely heavily on the use of the Internet. Posting on social media sites, creating infographics, and developing websites, depending on the course where the trainee is enrolled into, which relies heavily in using the Internet, are the very core of DJT, which is also the core of OCL.

Harasim (2012) describes OCL as “a new theory of learning that focuses on collaborative learning, knowledge building, and Internet use as a means to reshape formal, non-formal, and informal education for the Knowledge Age.” Harasim sees the benefits of moving teaching and learning to the Internet and large-scale networked education.

Such theory emphasizes the role of peer discourse as key to learning and defines learning as intellectual convergence, achieved through three progressive stages of group discourse: idea generating, idea organizing, and intellectual convergence. An observance in DJT is that trainees become more successful in finishing their tasks and graduate with flying colors if they would discuss with their fellow trainees on how to do their tasks like social media posts, web development, among other (i.e., teamwork even if the task is individual) – the very same emphasis of OCL.

The Online Collaborative Learning (OCL)

Figure 1.4 – Harassim's pedagogy of group discussions in OCL (Harassim, 2012)

OCL is also derived from social constructivism, since students are encouraged to collaboratively solve problems through discourse and where the teacher plays the role of facilitator as well as a learning community member. This is a major aspect of OCL but also of other constructivist theories where the teacher is not necessarily separate and apart but rather, an active facilitator of, knowledge building. Because of the importance of the role of the teacher, OCL is not easy to scale up. Unlike connectivism, which is suited for large-scale instruction, OCL is best situated in smaller instructional environments. This last issue becomes increasingly important when seeking commonality among online education theories. The same is true with DJT, which is small scale in nature, with only a maximum of 25 students per training batch are accepted.

The success of DJT graduates, after finishing their training, in landing into online jobs, as what the program envisions, is what the proponent of this study adopts

and how such idea is intertwined to OCL – the use of the Internet. It is assumed that successful graduates land into online jobs if there is a stable Internet connection in their rural areas and if they communicate with their peers for various online opportunities, which is an intellectual convergence on shared understanding, shared position, and mutual contribution.

Both Anchored Instruction Theory and Online Collaborative Learning Theory, which is based on social constructivism, play an important role in determining and answering the research objectives of this study.

Of another value to this study is the Human Capital Theory. Such theory regards education as an investment “like any other” and as a generator of externalities. According to the theory, the educational level of the agricultural labor force has an influence on the agricultural productivity.

The relationship of education with labor productivity may take three forms:

- That education can improve the quality of farmers’ labor by enabling them to produce more with their available stock of production factors
- That education can increase the efficiency of resource allocation
- That education can help farmers to choose more effective means of production by adopting new techniques

Similarly, this theory sheds light to the study as DigitalJobsPH, being a literacy program, and a form of non-formal education, may bring opportunities to the rural areas. It may not be to that field of agriculture but making these areas and communities digitally empowered and equipped with labor force that can accommodate to making these areas outside of the major urban hubs as a digital countryside.

The earliest human capital idea can be traced back to Adam Smith in the 18th century, while the modern theory was popularized by Gary Becker, Jacob Mincer, and Theodore Schultz. Another person we can attribute such theory is Paul Romer, who founded the modern innovation-driven approach to understand economic growth.

As discussed in the literature review, the idea of linking the human capital theory to online freelancing and as driver for rural growth and productivity has been earlier discussed by Arjan Van Den Born and Arjen Van Witteloostuijn in their book, *Drivers of Freelance Career Success* (2012). In their book, Arjen and Witteloostuijn attributed the success of freelancers from high-level education, which highlights human capital as an important variable in determining one freelancer's success in their careers.

Operational Definition of Terminologies

Term	Operational Definition
DJT trainees	Participants of DJT who were accepted to and availed the training program. Not all trainees may be a DJT graduate
DJT graduates	Graduates of the DJT program who successfully met all the necessary requirements to finish the DJT training module
Impact Sourcing	The process of outsourcing jobs not from the main sectors but rather in socioeconomically disadvantaged individuals
Online Jobs	Business process jobs that are done with the use of devices over the Internet not through traditional brick-and-mortar organization but preferably at homes
Digital Countryside	A vision for far-flung and rural communities outside of major cities or hubs in the country to be technologically advanced with digital opportunities for their citizens, like jobs that are computer-based and processed over the Internet
Gig Economy	A labor market characterized by short-term contracts or freelance work
Digital	Using means of electronic technology to perform various transactions in comparison to manual method
Information Technology- Business Process Management (IT-BPM) Industry	The sector that uses various IT technologies including cloud-based computing in providing solutions and services to businesses
Cloud-based Computing	The use of computer system resources without the physical and direct active management by the users
IT/ICT Councils	Organizations in areas that promote ICT to advance academic, business, and government well-beings
Fruitful	DJT being able to meet its objectives in capacitating marginalized sectors and a digital countryside
Marginalized group/sectors	Members of the community at risk of being subjected to multiple discrimination because of characteristics or backgrounds

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

As a new term and concept developed during this digital age, not much has been studied about impact sourcing. A few studies have emerged but are of limited content and structure. However, various concepts are of importance to and whose related literatures are included in this chapter.

Impact Sourcing

For Oprins (2016), impact sourcing and online outsourcing have emerged recently as new models that intentionally or unintentionally provide income to underprivileged groups in the global south by giving them access to information technology (IT)-enabled service jobs.

As ICT connect workers to work regardless of their background and geography, it is possible that they could help overcome social, cultural, and physical constraints that might have excluded underprivileged groups from participating in the labor market.

In his study, Oprins pronounced that online outsourcing and impact sourcing industry largely concentrate in urban hubs and employ well-educated workers stemming from a middle-class background, based on qualitative interviews with impact sourcing managers and service providers from both sectors, Facebook observations, and quantitative, geographical data, results. This makes it ambiguous to see industries as alternatives to mainstream information technology-enabled service provision. Moreover, results from his study show that online outsourcing is on the verge of

change, which could negatively effect on workers' jobs, whereas impact sourcing requires change if more jobs are to be created.

Furthermore, in assessing the geographical distribution of online outsourcing and impact sourcing across the Philippines, Oprins found how both these industries are largely spin-offs of the mainstream service outsourcing industry. Although some online freelancers can be found in more remote regions, the majority lives in highly urbanized areas, especially the mainstream service outsourcing hubs, where they have access to a sufficiently stable Internet and electricity network. Moreover, similar to the mainstream service outsourcing industry, the most advanced tasks outsourced via online labor platforms tend to be conducted in the Philippines' largest urban hubs. Likewise, the impact sourcing initiatives of some local impact hubs fall short in reaching out to underprivileged groups living in highly rural yet low employment areas.

In an international scope, Sandeep (2015) considered studying impact sourcing and online outsourcing in India, where it leads the global community in terms of IT-BPM services, that is, according to Tholons International, and is home of the largest impact sourcing companies.

Information Technology and Business Process Outsourcing (IT-BPO) models have evolved with shifting client requirements and vendor-side innovation. Some classic examples of IT-BPO models include global delivery, shared services center, offshore multi-sourcing and nearshoring. A number of factors have contributed to how these models have come into being and evolved over the years. Some of these factors include globalization (Contractor et al, 2010), global competition (Apte and Mason, 1995), deregulation in developing economies (Nilekani, 2009), and IT-enabled

transformations such as improvements in telecommunication technology and bandwidth availability (Aspray et al, 2006).

It has been found out that impact sourcing companies at the moment are precariously positioned. It remains to be seen how successfully they will fulfill the mission of providing livelihood opportunities to thousands of semi-skilled and skilled workers in the global south. Ultimately, the future of these impact sourcing companies in India will depend on their capability to match their urban counterparts on quality while operating at significantly lower costs. Sandeep argues that it is impossible to take a purely transactional view of impact sourcing. With a growing economic inequality between rural and urban areas in most emerging markets, the logic of trickle-down economics has taken a real beating in the recent times. Disillusionment with free-market regimes and the liberalization agendas of governments is rife, in the scope of India. Against this background, impact sourcing companies can provide a modest but important opportunity for marginalized communities to plug into the global outsourcing phenomenon and to derive tangible economic benefits from it.

In 2019, the Global Impact Sourcing Coalition (GISC) on their working paper on *Social Impact Measurement Framework* developed the Impact Sourcing Measurement Framework and considered the Impact Sourcing Theory of Change as an important component to develop the framework. Further discussion of this was elaborated in the previous chapter. The coalition's premise on impact sourcing highlights that not only is the impact worker (online job worker or freelancer) benefits from the job demands of the buyer or supplier drivers, but also the family or household of the worker, and his or her community.

The IT-BPM Industry and BPO Subsector

Impact sourcing plays an important role in the Information Technology-Business Process Management (IT-BPM) sector, in which the former is a subsector of the latter.

Business process outsourcing (BPO) is defined as the transfer of a company's non-core activities to a third party that uses information technology for service delivery (Errighi et al. 2016). There are two types of outsourcing: (1) "nearshoring," undertaken in geographical proximity to the lead firm, and (2) "offshoring," where the service provider is remotely located. Indeed, enabled by improvements in ICT, firms have outsourced noncore activities to locations with lower labor costs, sufficiently high human capital, and adequate ICT infrastructure (Messenger et al. 2010). Online jobs, those of which independently freelanced by Filipinos, also often called as home-based jobs, are mostly offshore with most of their clients outside of the Philippines.

India and the Philippines have become the two largest destinations for BPO. As a result, BPO has become one of the most important global supply chains in the service category.

The Philippine BPO sector had its formative years in the early 1990s when a number of foreign data encoding companies settled in the country. It gained momentum in the early 2000s with the launch of international outsourcing and offshoring of voice-based services. In recent years, the Philippine BPO sector has grown rapidly, thanks to its considerable output of college graduates with a good command in English. The reason for the large share of call centers is the Americanized English of Filipinos, which gives the country a competitive edge over India (Friginal 2009).

The speedy rise of the industry in the country is causing supply side deficiencies as companies struggle to attract and retain enough qualified BPO professionals. Another unfavorable aspect of service offshoring is the high cost of office air-conditioning. With electricity costs estimated at 10% of total operating costs of BPOs, high power rates are an additional burden on BPOs operating in the Philippines (Beerepoot et al. 2013).

Companies that outsource their business services come from a wide variety of industries, notably banking, retail, tourism and medical services. Unsurprisingly, BPO involves a wide range of activities and is divided into subsectors depending on the types of service provided.

Major cities like Manila, Cebu, and Davao have become the major key players in the Philippines in terms of information technology (IT) and business process management (BPM) or IT-BPM services.

Locally, the IT and Business Process Association of the Philippines (IBPAP) and the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT) have named cities in the Philippines as Centers of Excellence, Top 10 Next-Wave Cities, and Emerging Cities. The ranking system takes into consideration quantity, quality, and scalability of talent; availability of infrastructure; competitive cost of doing business; government support; and business environment.

The Centers of Excellence include Metro Manila, Metro Cebu, Metro Clark, Bacolod City, Davao City, and Iloilo City. The Top Ten Next-Wave Cities are Baguio, Cagayan de Oro, Dagupan, Dasmariñas, Dumaguete, Lipa, Malolos, Naga, Sta. Rosa, and Taytay. The Emerging Cities comprise Balanga, Batangas, Iriga, Laoag, Legazpi, Puerto Princesa, Roxas, Tarlac, Tuguegarao, and Zamboanga.

The IT-BPM sector accounts for a significant percentage in the country's gross domestic product at 6%, from just 0.075% in 2000. Industry revenues from IT, business process outsourcing (BPO), and engineering services that make up the IT-BPM sector soar by 18.7% year by year generating \$22.9 billion in 2016. It is estimated that by year 2020, the total revenue will amount to \$55 billion, according to sources coming from US experts. The Oxford Business Group (OBG) reported that the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas stated that soon, this industry will overtake the value of remittances from overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs), currently accounting for an estimated 10% of the country's annual GDP. Remittances from overseas workers and IT-BPM make up the country's top two earners of foreign exchange. OBG states that "the industry will soon surpass foreign remittances as the single largest contributor to GDP, driven by growth in the emerging segments of healthcare, analytics, and financial services outsourcing."

In terms of employment, along with the rise of revenues is the rise of jobs created. In recent years, the employment rate ballooned to 1.15 million Filipinos being employed in the IT-BPM sector, a very significant increase from only 101,000 employees in 2004. It is estimated that by 2022, 7.6 million direct and indirect IT-BPM jobs will open, 500,000 jobs outside the National Capital Region (NCR), and the Philippines will contribute to a 15% global IT-BPM market share. Some jobs under this sector include call center or customer service representatives, copyediting and copywriting or content writing, digital marketing or e-commerce, search engine marketing and advertising, social media marketing, graphic designing, web development, virtual assistance, and computer programming and operations development, to name a few.

The IT Industry and Business Process Association (IBPAP) has announced that in 2019, the IT-BPM industry grew by 5.8% in headcount and 7.1% in revenues, despite the challenges brought about by geo-political developments, uncertainties in government policies, and disruptive technologies such as artificial intelligence (Figure 2.2). From \$24.5 Billion in 2018, the revenues collected that were related to the IT-BPM sector grew to \$26.3 Billion last year.

IT-BPM industry in 2016-2019: A Quick Look

Figure 2.1 – IBPAP’s full-time employees (FTEs) and revenue growth 2016-2019 for the IT-BPM sector (IBPAP, 2019)

Indeed, IT-BPM will become the “economical source of the future” and will play an important role in the development of our country.

However, it seems that only metropolitan cities and major areas of the country are the only ones being benefitted from this sector. Far-flung areas seem to retain their usual agriculture or horticulture, pisciculture, or poultry livelihood as their means of income – and citizens of these areas leave their homes to go to major cities and be employed as workers in the IT-BPM field since opportunities are not found from where they come from. Or even if the local government units (LGUs) from these areas are interested to invest and venture in the IT-BPM sector in their respective localities,

investors and stakeholders do not consider their places to put up a site and open jobs for them because, in the first place, it will always be a risk for them, with all other factors combined.

The Rural Impact Sourcing (RIS) Program of DICT

To address this, the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT), the government agency responsible for the planning, development, and promotion of the country's information and communication technology agenda in support of national development, which was just formed in 2016, implemented the Rural Impact Sourcing (RIS) technical training program in 2017, which is now known as DigitalJobsPH Technical Training (DJT).

The DigitalJobsPH Technical Training is intended to create meaningful ICT-enabled jobs in socio-economically disadvantaged areas in the country. It specifically focuses on areas where there is high population but low employment due to lack of investors. It also aims to promote ICT-enabled jobs as a high-value economic activity in rural communities that are not yet ready to host Information Technology–Business Process Management (IT-BPM) operations.

DJT benefits disadvantaged individuals in the countryside. It looks beyond the common source of supply for traditional outsourcing to provide higher-income employment and access to new income opportunities to individuals that might not otherwise be employed in this sector. These individuals are typically people who are at a unique disadvantage and lack access to traditional employment.

To be able to help address unemployment in the country and support more Filipinos in the countryside gain employment through the online freelancing industry,

the DICT has implemented DJT. The training primarily aims to increase people's hireability by focusing on development and improvement of their ICT skills and utilize it for employment opportunities.

Aside from empowering the local talents with the skills and knowledge, the training has become a good venue for collaboration since it also provided an online marketing opportunity for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). Trainees undergo practical exercises which included a 21-day campaign wherein they create digital campaign strategies for these MSMEs.

Applicants are screened during training day(s) through an interview and examination on English grammar, digital literacy, logic aptitude, and special added examination depending on the module/course that may range from typing test, essay, etc. A maximum of 25 trainees are selected to attend the free training. They are also known as "scholars" since they will pay nothing during the training, with provisions like meals and kits (notebook, pen, USB flash drive, lanyard, etc.) provided to them.

The various courses offered under the training include (1) Digital Marketing/e-Commerce (14 days), (2) Web Development (7 days), (3) Social Media Marketing and Advertising (10 days), (4) Search Engine Marketing and Advertising (10 days), (5) Graphic Design (8 days), and (8) Virtual Assistance (8 days). A special course, Online English as Secondary Language (ESL) (3 days) is also offered, in partnership with 51Talk. Training days vary by module, with meetings at 2-3 consecutive days a week, to give time for the trainees do tasks or assignments. All trainings however, except for Online ESL, have a 21-day campaign period after their face-to-face training, where the trainees and trainer meet virtually to finish their tasks. At this period as well is when trainees try to seek for online jobs and be hired. Once they get employed, they will

graduate with medals during the graduation ceremony. Assessment and graduation come after the 21-day campaign period.

Every training is supported by the local government unit (LGU) where the training is held. In the Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) signed by both parties, the LGU takes care of the meal provisions, venue, and Internet connection, while DICT provides the transportation, accommodation and honorarium of the trainer – which are leading online workers in the country. The Department of Trade in Industry (DTI) is also involved in the Digital marketing and E-Commerce module, where they are the ones providing the MSMEs. At some point, ICT councils of the areas where the training is held also support the training in various means.

Only the Digital Marketing/e-Commerce course requires the presence of the MSMEs. Further, this training recognizes the role of the MSMEs to provide employment opportunities and contribute to economic growth especially within their locality. By increasing competency of the talent, this training will also serve as an avenue to promote the use of e-Commerce by MSMEs.

As an infant department, DICT has not yet been regionalized. Regions belong to clusters with a Regional and/or an Assistant Regional Director heading it. Luzon Cluster 1 (LC1) includes Ilocos Region (Region I) and Cagayan Valley (Region II); Luzon Cluster 2 (LC2) includes Central Luzon (Region III) and Cordillera Administrative Region (CAR); Luzon Cluster 3 (LC3) includes Southern Tagalog Mainland (CALABARZON/Region IV-A), Southwestern Tagalog Region (MIMAROPA/Region IV-B), and Bicol Region (Region V); Visayas Cluster 1 includes Western Visayas (Region VI); Visayas Cluster 2 includes Central Visayas (Region 7) and Eastern Visayas (Region 8); Mindanao Cluster 1 includes Zamboanga Peninsula

(Region IX) and Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM); Mindanao Cluster 2 includes Northern Mindanao (Region C) and Caraga (Region XIII); and Mindanao Cluster 3 includes Davao Region (Region XI) and SOCCSKSARGEN (Region XII).

There is no exact, uniform DigitalJobsPH training target for every cluster. At the end of the year, Directors, Provincial Officers, and IIDB staff meet to assess and plan out the locations for the coming year. It is there where the next locations for next year are plotted. Some clusters have higher target locations than others, depending on their pledge. The average locations for every cluster in a year is 10.

In the conduct of these trainings, special Technology Empowerment for Economic Development (Tech4Ed)–DJT Hubs have been established and utilized to serve as training centers in selected communities. The Tech4ED–DJT Hub is a shared facility which provides access to ICT-enabled contents and services. These centers also serve as DJT hubs where beneficiaries, after the training, can do jobs online with their free facilities.

Online Outsourcing and Online Jobs

Kuek et al (2015) use online outsourcing to refer to the contracting of third-party workers to perform tasks via Internet-based marketplaces or platforms, consistent in meaning with the crowd work parlance in Hunt et al (2017). In this typology, online outsourcing is classified into microwork and online freelancing. Microwork and online freelancing often overlap, the major difference between the two is the size and complexity of the tasks and the compensation offered (Kuek et al. 2015). Microwork and online freelancing are akin to microtask and macrotask, respectively.

Global sourcing has increased competition in services markets for a wide variety of activities, from low-skilled functions (data entry, word processing, call centers) to higher-skilled activities (software development, consultancy, medical services, research and development). A range of services which were previously conceived to be non-tradable are now being provided electronically over large distances (World Bank 2007).

With the expanding opportunities for offshore service delivery, this sector is infinitely and definitely rich in opportunities. Consequently, developing countries with educated manpower should be able to benefit from this trend and construct niches for themselves in a world economy that is increasingly connected by telecommunications networks (Dossani et al. 2007). Despite the rapid expansion of employment in some developing countries, a number of contested issues regarding the complexity of work, quality of employment, and the longer-term prospects of workers in the offshore service sector demand further research (Beerepoot 2013).

The modern meaning of the term “freelancer” started to be used since the second part of the 20th century in order to define the unaffiliated journalists who provided on-demand services for various press organizations. It was not long until the term started to be used for other services (graphic design, multimedia content creation and editing, advertising, marketing, legal or business consulting, among others) that were delivered beyond the traditional employment connection. The occurrence and fast spreading of the Internet turned the freelancing concept into a global phenomenon so that freelancers became a stand-alone class of professionals with a continuously increasing share among the labor market (Gheorghe 2015).

Online jobs and freelancing gave birth to the emergence of the concept of “gig economy.”

Gig Economy

The “gig economy” has emerged rapidly as a form of service delivery that challenges existing business models, labor-management practices, and regulations. The ways in which platform companies transact with workers, in particular, have created a burgeoning public interest but have yet to give rise to a corresponding academic literature (Healy 2017).

Woodcock defines such term to refer to labor markets that are characterized by independent contracting that happens through, via, and on digital platforms. The kind of work that is offered is contingent: casual and non-permanent work. It may have variable hours and little job security, involve payment on a piece-work basis, and lack any options for career development. This relationship is sometimes termed “independent contracting,” “freelancing,” or “temporary work.” Traditionally, a gig refers to short-term arrangements typical of a musical event. An aspiring musician might celebrate getting a gig, or tell a friend that they have a gig in the back room of a pub or other venue. This is of course no guarantee that they will get to perform regularly. There might be the chance of a repeat performance if they play particularly well or are particularly popular – or it may just be a one-off. They might get paid – either a fixed fee, a share of the ticket price, or payment in kind (some free drinks perhaps). Their expenses might get covered. But also, they might not (Woodcock 2020). This is the same principle with the gig economy in the digital landscape, where workers, known as freelancers, experience the same.

A significant number of Filipino professionals, and even those who were once deemed as undesirables under local labor standards, are increasingly found to be migrating to online platform labor. Considered by the Philippine government as a solution to its employment gap, the country now boasts of having some of the highest-earning online freelancers in the world (Graham et al. 2017). Valorized under the guise of creativity and flexibility, platform labor is seen as empowerment for Filipino workers. It provides them with new work opportunities to earn dollars, it gives them entry into the “global workplace,” and facilitates a flexible work arrangement that takes away the challenges of daily commute while giving them valuable time with their families at home (Soriano et al. 2020).

In the Philippines, part of the national government’s labor strategy to bring in much-needed foreign currency inflows and as a source of job creation is to tout the mantra of Filipinos being “world class service workers” and “modern heroes.” The contradiction at the heart of this valorization is that it helps drive labor export despite the precariousness associated with such work (Rodriguez 2010). From foreign domestic labor to call center labor and now to digital platform labor – Filipinos aim for work that matches their distinct traits as the top service workers of the world, exploitative conditions notwithstanding. Platform laborers in particular are now being labeled as the “OFW 2.0” – no longer the “Overseas Filipino Worker” but the “Online Freelance Worker.” Through digital labor, one still earns dollars and performs as a “global worker,” only this time without having to be away from home.

Van Den Born and Van Witteloostuijn (2012) studied extensively the career of the professional freelancers, a growing phenomenon in many developed countries but not yet the focus of many career studies. In sum, external environment in which an

individual freelancer operates is the most important factor in determining career success. They suggested that more work need to be performed on the relationship between the environment and individual career success in order to achieve a successful career for these professionals. Education is highlighted as a determinant for a successful online freelancer, much to the idea of the human capital as an investment for career growth.

Tholon's Digital Nations and Super Cities List

Tholons International, a leading full-service strategic advisory firm for global outsourcing and investments, annually identifies 100 key cities in the world that are conducive and strategic for IT-BPM services. Being part of their list is highly important for cities as companies and organizations tend to invest and put up their businesses in locations listed in the Tholons 100. The Tholons' Services Globalization Index provides cities and nations to emerge as a preferred destination for global digital demand attracting global investors and stakeholders.

In their 2018 Super Cities report, Manila ranks second from its fourth rank in 2017, just behind Bangalore, India. Cebu City jumped one notch higher from 12th to 11th spot, Davao City from 85th to 75th, Santa Rosa, Laguna, from 100th to 87th, and Bacolod City from 97th to 89th. Iloilo City enters the list anew at 92nd, while Dumaguete City, which was part of the Top 100 Outsourcing Destinations in 2016 as 92nd in 2016, has never made a comeback ever since. The factors considered in this list are (a) talent skills and quality, (b) business catalyst, (c) cost, (d) infrastructure, (e) risk and quality of life, and (d) digital innovation. Majority of the Top 5 cities come from India (Bangalore, 1; Mumbai, 3; Delhi, 4; Hyderabad, 5). Some ASEAN cities also make up the list with Singapore at 12th behind Cebu City (11th), Kuala Lumpur at 13th, Ho Chi

Minh City at 28th, Hanoi at 32nd, Penang at 54th, Jakarta at 59th, Bangkok at 63rd, and Da Nang at 83rd.

The Philippines is way ahead of not only its ASEAN neighbors but also of the entire global competition in Tholons' 2018 Top 50 Digital Nations list. From its third rank in 2017, the country jumped one step higher at second spot. India, for recent years, still claims the perpetual trophy at first. Brazil is 3rd, USA at 4th, and Mexico at 5th. Canada, Russia, Vietnam, Colombia, and South Africa, respectively, follow. ASEAN countries that make up the Top 50 include Singapore (13), Thailand (16), Malaysia (17), and Indonesia (19). The same factors with that of the Super Cities list have been considered for the Digital Nations report: (a) talent skills and quality account for the location's total population and technical and non-technical graduates and scalability (19%); (b) business catalyst involves not only the employment in BPO and ITO sectors and the presence of BPO and ITO providers but also the ease of doing business (15%); (c) cost speaks for the costs and operations for BPO and ITO salary, real estate, and bandwidth (15%); (d) infrastructure considers the business environment: airport connectivity, leased line providers, mass transport systems, hospitals and educational institutes, and availability of class-A IT parks and buildings (11%); (e) risk and quality of life comprises the political, social, natural, and commercial risk (15%); and (f) digital and innovation covers what sums up digital transformation: open innovation ecosystem, startups, diversity, and maturity, innovative policies and incentives, unicorns, cybersecurity, global digital competitiveness, and digital skills, scale, and attractiveness (25%). All these data are computed per country through a methodology comprising primary research, secondary research, and qualitative and quantitative analysis.

However, in 2019, the Philippines dropped a few notches down as it ranked fifth after India, Brazil, USA, and Canada. According to one of the country's experts in the ICT industry, this sliding down can be attributed to the country's lagging approach towards startups and artificial intelligence, which Tholons gave higher points recently.

Digital nations: 2019 vs. 2018 rank

Figure 2.2 – Tholons Top 25 2019 Digital Nations (Tholons 2019)

Digital Economy

Dahlman et al. point out the importance of the digital economy for developing countries. Digital economy is the amalgamation of several general-purpose technologies and the range of economic and social activities carried out by people over the Internet and related technologies. It encompasses the physical infrastructure that digital technologies are based on (broadband lines, routers), the devices that are used for access (computers, smartphones), the applications they power, and the functionality they provide (IoT, data analytics, cloud computing).

This brand new term, i.e., digital economy, is believed to foster growth and productivity and support inclusive development. This growth is demonstrated by the adoption of digital technologies by a large number of consumers, firms, and governments albeit at varying rates across sectors and countries. Adoption and usage of digital technologies raises the productivity of capital and labour and enables the participation in global value chains (Milleret et al. 2014).

Digital economy has permeated multiple aspects of modern life, including retail, transportation, education and agriculture, and benefits consumers, businesses, and governments. This economy is bringing about greater convenience for consumers and citizens in a whole range of areas (Dahlman et al. 2016).

Governments in developing countries should work with sharing platforms and other stakeholders to design appropriate regulations to formalize the sharing economy and ensure public concerns are addressed and taxes collected. The sharing economy can thus contribute to the much needed economic development, environmental sustainability, and social cohesion (Soans et al. 2016).

Digital Countryside

Sawada believes that new technologies will drive higher productivity, better-paying jobs, and economic growth. There is optimism about developing Asia's job prospects despite growing concern that new technologies could cause widespread job loss. These reasons for this optimism include the rising demand that offsets job displacement driven by automation, the creation of new occupations and industries due to technological change and economic growth, and the increase of many new jobs in information and communications technology (ICT), and new types of jobs that are expected to arise in health care and education and in finance, insurance, real estate,

and other business services. New technologies often automate only some parts or tasks of a job, not the whole job. Finally, automation of jobs goes ahead only where it is both technically and economically feasible. Nonetheless, new technologies alter the skills required of the workforce and may cause losing of jobs or unemployment as some firms downsize or close. These make the less skilled more likely to experience lower wage growth, exacerbating income inequality (Sawada 2018).

Sawada further explains the roles of governments in these challenges, “Governments should respond to these challenges by ensuring that workers are protected from the downside of new technologies and able to harness the new opportunities they provide. This will require coordinated action on skills development, labor regulation, social protection, and income redistribution. Governments should use new technologies in education and skills development, as well as in the delivery of public services like social protection programs. Government support for new technologies must benefit people and protect their rights and privacy” (Sawada 2018).

In leveraging technological advances for inclusive growth, the government has an important role to play in. It will center on the following aspects: (1) response to technology (i.e., education and training, favorable labor regulation, social protection, tax policies); (2) use of technology (i.e., skills development and job matching, provision of public goods and services); and (3) support for technology (i.e., investments in ICT infrastructure, consumer protection, and innovation and technology adoption).

Schools also play a crucial role in making technology prosper. Schools need incentives to strengthen foundational skills that enable individuals to learn, and to relearn. For imparting the specialized skills needed to work with new technologies, universities and institutions specializing in technical and vocational education and

training are key, and they will have to cater not only to the rising number of graduates from secondary education but also to adults seeking to upgrade their skills or retrain.

Given the central role the Internet plays in new technologies, developing a nationwide broadband backbone and other ICT infrastructure is but essential, as is basic infrastructure for electricity supply and transport. Currently, DICT's iGov and GovNet projects are implemented to cater to such goal. Public investments are needed to extend Internet access to remote and challenged regions. Appropriate regulation of mobile and Internet providers will help ensure affordable services. Governments need to consider the protection of personal data and privacy and competition policy has to evolve to ensure that large technology firms abide by the norms of fair competition. Appropriate public policy interventions are also critical in ensuring that new technologies serve economic and social development.

For Eliseo Rio, Jr., previously the Acting Secretary of DICT, the country's ICT infrastructure needs a lot of improvements in order to cope up with the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Rio explains further that all of the country's ICT infrastructure is invested or owned by the private sector. The government has almost no investment in ICT infrastructure. But DICT is doing its mandate in fulfilling the National ICT Agenda. The department is now putting up critical infrastructure in ICT environments.

Government intervention to the IT-BPM industry signifies that its policies and actions are aligned to its vision of inclusive growth. Moreover, government support to the IT-BPM industry suggests that it capitalizes on the growth led path in this particular context. The Philippine government, responding to the needs of the growing IT-BPM industry, should continue providing a reinforcing force towards employment generation. In this instance, the enabling force is a training program for human

resource development, realized in the form of the government and industry partnership (Keitel 2013).

These key terms and programs correlate to one another. With online freelancing, recently referred to as gig economy, being part and parcel of the business process outsourcing subsector of the IT-BPM sector, education and training play an important role in providing opportunities for Filipinos to be part of such economy. DigitalJobsPH, a program intended to train would-be freelancers, is provided by DICT since 2017. Freelancing also shapes the digital countryside, where Filipinos are provided opportunities to earn more than the traditional employment, without having to leave the comforts of their homes. Online freelancing leads to make countries become competitive in the digital economy, where Tholons, an independent body based in the UK, annually determines which countries lead the global scale.

Chapter III

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Diagram 3.1 The Conceptual Framework for the relationship of DJT towards a digital countryside
DigitalJobsPH as Tool for the Philippine Countryside Digitalization...

The figure shows the conceptual paradigm to present the figure of the study.

The independent variable is the DigitalJobsPH training which factors out its relationship towards a digital countryside. For a digital countryside to be considered as its namesake, the common variable Location is of importance as it would determine whether the location is considered a rural area, far from the metro and urban centers.

Between the two components, four variables comprise what make a digital countryside a digital countryside: 1) Talent Skills and Quality, 2) Business Catalysts, 3) Innovation, and 4) Cost and Infrastructure.

The Talent Skills and Quality refer to the available pool of human resources that are present in the locality that can cater and accommodate to the needed workforce for a digital countryside to prosper. This includes Online Freelancer Presence and Digital Workforce who are employees that specifically cater to digitally related jobs. The Trainee or Marginalized Sector, the beneficiaries of DJT, are part and parcel of this variable as they make up the freelancing community once they finish the training. Labor Pool and Skills availability refer to other jobs that may or may not be digitally related but are still of importance for the ecosystem to thrive, regardless of the nature of their work. In an ecosystem where there plays a symbiosis for everyone to meet their needs and demands, they are counted as part of a digital countryside ideology. Graduates Output, another variable that make up the first one, refers to the number of graduates produced in the area. What makes a digital countryside successful includes the available workforce who have finished a level of education that can cater to the needs in the ecosystem.

DICT conducts and spearheads DJT and thus is as important variable that plays a significant role in the framework. The cluster may partner with an LGU who can

provide other necessities for the program, which may include Connectivity (Internet) and Equipment, which are also intertwined to Cost and Infrastructure, discussed later. Depending on arrangements, either variable can deliver its counterpart support for the training to happen. Both are connected to the Trainee/Marginalized Sector as the latter are citizens or constituents of the LGU where the training is hosted. The Instructor is who DICT taps to moderate and facilitate the learning. These Instructors should be online freelancers themselves and are hired as third-party resource persons of DICT. The Instructor and Trainee interact directly with DICT and/or LGU as the medium, through DJT.

The Trainee/Marginalized Sector represents the priority beneficiaries of DJT: Out-of-School Youths (OSYs), Unemployed, Underemployed, Students, Persons with Disabilities (PWDs), and Senior Citizens (SCs).

Another major variable is the Business Catalysts. This pertains to opportunities and the setup that such rural community has in its business and commerce ecosystem. It includes industry-related activities as well as the degree of organizational support present in a location, which is geared to develop the services industry and support the development of digital technology, innovation, and entrepreneurship. This component includes the sub-variables Employers and Investors and Business Landscape. The former is what constitutes people or juridical entities that employ the workers for work, regardless of digital jobs or not, that create opportunities. The latter pertains to the business ecosystem model that the rural location has in its being.

Innovation is the lifeline of today's business landscapes. For a digital countryside to prosper, it must embrace and adopt digital technologies and platforms like social media, mobile technology, artificial intelligence, among others, to catch up

with the growing demands. The parameters include Innovative Policies, which include special ordinances or legislatures that adopt technology principles. The presence of ICT councils, that are born out of legislatures and council meetings, also forms part of these policies. Another sub-component, Competitiveness, is the assertion of one's locality to embrace technology and innovation as a standard of normal transactions, including those that are present in government agencies and units.

A digital countryside also constitutes Cost and Infrastructure. The amount an employer or client invests on operations in case they put up their business there, the cost of living for an individual person in case they decide to work there, the cost of a household unit or rental spaces, the cost for basic commodities, and the price for a stable Internet connection form part of the sub-variable Cost. Connectivity on the other hand represents the stability of Internet connection in the area. Being a digital countryside which relies heavily on the use of the Internet, how does the area play in terms of this advantage? Transportation as a sub-variable is as important as the others. As workers commute and go to their offices, in case that their work is physical, how much is spent by one? IT Parks and Economic Zones are also determinant for a digital countryside. With ease and accessibility these facilities offer, a digital countryside location may be able to live up to its name.

Although the four variables Talent Skills and Quality, Business Catalysts, Innovation, and Cost and Infrastructure make up a digital countryside, only the first one, with emphasis on Trainees/Marginalized Sectors representing the Digital Workers of Talent Skills and Quality, will be the primary concern of this study.

How has DJT, being a training program provided by DICT, that provides online freelancing courses, been able to provide opportunities and capacitate the

marginalized sectors of the community (OSYs, Unemployed, Underemployed, Students, PWDs, SCs) that leads to a digital countryside?

Chapter IV

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research Methodology

Since the study wanted to know the impact of the training as evidenced by the answers from respondents, this study then is qualitative in nature.

To better understand the thoughts and experiences of the DJT graduates, or respondents, and enable to gather in-depth insights on the study using open-ended questions, the study is a qualitative research. The study aims to understand how the DigitalJobsPH training program of DICT is related to building the capacities of marginalized sectors in Regions 7 and 8 towards a digital countryside, in which the lived experiences during and after the training of the respondents were taken into consideration.

The respondents received an online questionnaire through Google Forms to fill out and answer. The Google Forms link was also posted in the official Facebook page of DICT Visayas Cluster 2 (www.facebook.com/DICTFOOVC2) to make it more accessible and reach the required number of sample size easily, given the current COVID-19 situation. With the study being qualitative, this study will help understand the social reality of the marginalized groups, in their natural setting. Careful understanding of the realities to predict the future of the training will be taken into consideration and summary, conclusions, and recommendation will be provided.

The study is also phenomenological in nature. Being phenomenological, the study helps us understand the meaning of people's lived experience, in this case, the marginalized sectors of the community who graduated from the DigitalJobsPH training

of DICT implemented in Visayas Cluster 2. The study explores what the DJT trainees experienced during their training and focuses on their experience during and after DJT.

The qualitative research method used in this study is through surveys with open-ended questions. This is elaborated in the Data Collection.

A brief numerical analysis will also be discussed to summarize questions in the survey that are not open ended but whose data are of value to understand the success rates of DJT.

Respondents of the Study

The participants of the study are the RIS/DJT graduates from all the locations in Region 7 (Central Visayas) and Region 8 (Eastern Visayas) since the inception of the program in 2017 up to 2019. Although the program is implemented nationwide, the scope is limited to the implementation in DICT Visayas Cluster 2 (Regions 7 and 8) only and is not representative of the nationwide implementation of the program but an evaluation and assessment of the implementation in Central and Eastern Visayas areas only.

The following are the locations per year and the number of graduates:

Year	Location	Number of Graduates
2017	1. Bogu City	21
	2. Maasin City	21
	3. Allen, Northern Samar	25

2018	4. Sogod, Southern Leyte	20	
	5. Maria, Siquijor	24	
	6. Bayawan City	20	
	7. Tagbilaran City	25	
	8. Borongan City	24	
	9. Palo, Leyte	24	
	10. Ormoc City	25	
	11. Naval, Biliran	23	
	12. Catbalogan City	25	
	13. Barili, Cebu	22	
	2019	14. Can-avid, Samar	25
		15. Bindoy, Negros Oriental	19
		16. Loon, Bohol	23
17. Sogod, Cebu		10	
18. Calbayog City		22	
19. Larena, Siquijor		22	
20. Baybay City		22	
21. Tacloban City		25	
22. Catbalogan City		25	
23. Catarman, Northern Samar		22	
24. Maasin City		18	
25. Dumaguete City		22	
26. Tagbilaran City		16	
27. Biliran, Biliran		23	
28. Naga City, Cebu		22	
29. Zamboanguita, Negros Oriental		26	
30. Cebu City		8	
TOTAL LOCATIONS: 30		TOTAL GRADUATES: 583	

Using Slovin's Formula, the proponent has arrived at a sample size of 238.

$$\eta = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

where η = Sample size

N = Population size (total graduates): 583

e = Margin of error: 0.05

where Confidence Level = 95%, Alpha Level = 5% or 0.05

$$\eta = \frac{583}{1 + (583)(0.05)^2}$$

$$\eta = \frac{583}{2.4575}$$

$$\eta = 238$$

This means that out of the 30 locations where the DigitalJobsPH training was conducted and implemented in Regions 7 and 8 from 2017 to 2019, with a total of 583 graduates, and with a confidence level of 95%, 238 DJT graduates were surveyed for a safe sample size following Slovin's Formula. That is equal to 40.82% of the total graduates being asked to respond to the study.

Given the travel restrictions and limit to physically interview the respondents, a combination of non-probability sampling methods of voluntary response and snowballing techniques was used to gather data from the subjects. Although biased in nature, such method makes it convenient for the researcher and is available at the time and height of the pandemic. It is also less resource intensive, more accessible, and convenient to work with as compared to probability sampling.

The first of approach of voluntary response sampling was initiated by generating a Google Forms link and was posted through the official Facebook page of DICT Visayas Cluster 2. The DJT graduates volunteered themselves in answering the online survey.

Another sampling method used was snowball sampling. When there was not enough respondents to complete the target sample size, the respondents who answered voluntarily were asked to recruit their fellow DJT graduates to answer such

survey. Also, the provincial officers and coordinators of DICT offices under DICT VC2 were tapped to help disseminate such survey for the graduates to answer. This allowed more reach to the target respondents.

The first 238 participants who answered the survey were chosen for the analysis of data.

For the data analysis, the approach on thematic analysis is considered to analyze the qualitative data gathered.

Data Collection

Due to COVID-19 restrictions of travelling to personally approach the respondents in their areas, an innovative way of using the Google Forms was carried out to send to the participants.

The public, shortened link <http://tiny.cc/DICTPostTrainingSurvey> (complete link: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScxHXONNDmzpIIsA-R08Iz5LgXaY098Z0R-eHXrjQOF0uvECg/viewform?usp=sf_link) was given to the respondents through (1) the e-mail address they provided after their training and/or (2) Facebook Messenger private messages, whichever was available.

The data gathering procedure was first carried out from April 16, 2020 to June 16, 2020, and resumed October to December 2020 – with four months of allowance to send out and gather answers data, with the hopes of identifying whether the RIS/DJT technical training has become impactful and effective in DICT Visayas Cluster 2 areas throughout the course of its existence which started in 2017. There was a resumption of the data gathering procedure after the deliberation of the

proponent in September, with the correct sample size considered. This was during the height of the pandemic.

As mentioned, the electronic Google form method was utilized to lessen the risk of going out from homes as the global pandemic has limited travel and leaving the homes of citizens.

It is emphasized that Regions 7 and 8 were the chosen locations for the study as the researcher has the first-hand data and information of the graduates. However, this does not imply that the study is representative of the entire nationwide implementation of DJT and is only a fraction of the project's entirety. Of the 16 regions in the Philippines (NCR is excluded as the region is not or does not have a rural area; thus, no DJT was ever done in the capital), Central and Eastern Visayas regions make up the 12.5% of the archipelago. However, in future studies and higher learning, the researcher would want to consider a whole-of-nation approach in studying the program as it provides development in the country.

The study would indicate how fare DICT Visayas Cluster 2, the regional operations center in charge of both regions, has implemented the program from 2017 to 2019.

Analysis of Data

More than a statistical evaluation, the study discusses results of open-ended survey questions, with the very nature of this research as being qualitative. Four open-ended questions from the survey will be qualitatively analyzed, with a separate table each.

The thematic analysis of qualitative data is used to closely examine the data to identify common themes and patterns of the DJT graduate-respondents in DICT VC2 areas.

There are 6 steps considered in deductively analyzing the data, namely, familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing up. The last one will be presented in the next chapter.

Only those valid open-ended answers to questions were considered in the analysis. This means that answers with “N/A,” “not applicable,” and the like will not be merited in the data analysis.

Coding

The coding step entails highlighting sections of texts from the survey extracts and coming up with short-hand labels or codes to describe the content.

Note that there are four important open-ended questions raised in the survey.

Table 4.1

Open-Ended Question 1 (OEQ1): “What should RIS/DJT improve on?”

<u>Survey extracts</u>	<u>Codes</u>
“Longer training days and more advanced lessons”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training • Advanced lessons
“Comprehensive training on the subject”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive training
“make training easier for starter“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easier training for starters
“Training days should be longer enough especially if it is a comprehensive one, and even its not so that there would be enough time for the to comprehend what is being taught since not everyone is as "techy".“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training

“Skills that is in demand for the beginners so that they can easily land jobs. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-demand skills for beginners
“Training days should be longer in order to master the topic. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training
“More trainings please“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings
“Training should be longer in order for us to really apply it in the online world and DICT graduate should have a group like linkend in order for recruiters to have an access to us for hiring purposes. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training • Creation of groups
“More trainers and more time so that scholars can finish the requirements on time“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainers • Longer days of training
“Stable internet connectivity and ICT ready and equipped classroom and training facility. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity • Conducive facility
“Longer Training dates, don't cramp up schedule“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training
“The students should focus on gaining knowledge and experience rather than focusing on delivering outputs.. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainees' focus on knowledge gathering
“I am satisfied and appreciated with this training that they offered to us. nothing to improve on. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing to improve
“Should be longer time to finish the requiremnts“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training
“Training should have more time face to face“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training
“None. I'm satisfied of what happen on our training. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing to improve
“I think the DICT should have it's own training facility or permanent location to conduct a training. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permanent venue of training facility
“Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the requirements Mentoring with the new graduates. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training • Graduate mentorship
“The internet should have a secure and stable connection“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Tasks that are given should have more longer time to do. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training
“training days should be longer to accomodate more time to finish the requirements“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training
“Should be required to teach voluntary to some out of school youth in the municipality. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Required voluntary teaching of graduates
“Training days should be longer“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training
“Provide more trainings“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings by DICT

“Internet connection should faster. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast Internet connectivity
“During our training we had struggle of our internet connection. So hopefully next time they should also provide the stable connection. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Focus the training on one subject at a time“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject concentration
“Bringing out clients“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Client provision
“Training should be in specific niche so that every trainees can focus what work was to be done. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Niche concentration
“The DICT should recruit more competent trainers. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competent trainers
“Longer training days and internet accessibility“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training • Stable Internet connectivity
“Training days should be longer. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training
“Training days should be longer and devices to be borrowed even after the training. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer days of training • Provision of equipment
“Training needs more actual and good internet, must extended days training“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actual training methods • Stable Internet connectivity
“Internet connection should be improve so that other requirements can finished before the training end. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“A reliable internet connection could be of big help especially in the SMM niche“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“To provide strong wifi connection“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“It should be longer in order for trainees deliver great results and understand more the topic“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Must improved their WiFi connection and more time to finish the said task. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity • Longer training days
“not to compressed the training days so much that as a result trainees are forced to do all the tasks without really understanding or learning anything from the lesson“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Training days should be longer“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Securing venue and stable internet connection during training first before conducting a training“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Venue of training facility • Stable Internet connectivity
“Training days should be longer“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Yes, the training days should be longer. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days

<p>“Trainings should have any follow up group activities such as meetings, gatherings, and other related trainings. This will help the graduates have sustainability in their career and groups before finally letting them off the hook. “</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group follow-ups
<p>“Availability of facilities and equipments and stable fast internet. “</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Venue of training facility • Availability of equipment • Stable Internet connectivity
<p>“Training days should be longer to ensure in depth discussion of topics without needing to rush the trainer because of the schedule. If in depth training is done, graduates will feel more prepared for embarking on their online journey. Coaching after the training would also be good to guide graduates on how to build their online presence, impressive portfolio, applying for jobs, writing impressive resumes and cover letters. These are important to get them noticed by employers online.“</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Group follow-ups • Mentoring/coaching
<p>“Longer training s“</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
<p>“Publicity in rural areas & urban poor settings“</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publicity
<p>“Availability of fast internet connection“</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
<p>“Actual process in getting online clients in order the trainees to have an idea in the real world of freelancing. Participation of MSME affects the process and cooperation is always very low. Why not create a trainee's website/Social media that will serve has his/her own portfolio. MSME should serve as actual client. “</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of online clients • MSMEs' participation • Creation of website/social media account
<p>“Trainings should spend more time/days. And hoping that RIS/DJT will continue again and again in order to help more. “</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Continuation of training
<p>“Focus On Specific Training ON a Specific qualified Scholar“</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific training per scholar
<p>“Trainings days should be longer and the internet connectivity must be stable“</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Stable Internet connectivity
<p>“Longer training Days“</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
<p>“Traning days should be longer so it will not end up.like a crash course, but still i am thankful for the traininf i had attended. “</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
<p>“Specific Skills or Module with enough time to fully teach the steps dealing different situation if different outcome in your work or in your employer in order for fully understand the training and be confident. “</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific training • Longer training days
<p>“Maybe making sure that there is a stable and reliable internet connection during the live training. And training days should be longer to accomodate more time to finish the requirements. “</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet Connectivity • Longer training days
<p>“Training should be extensive“</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days

“Provision of ICT Equipment at home“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of ICT equipment
“Provide a laptop to DJT scholars after graduation. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of ICT equipment
“Conduct another training“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings by DICT
“To provide more trainings to enhance our skills more; provide online freelancing job to the graduates. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings by DICT • Provision of online jobs to graduates
“Handouts or the lesson notes that are from the trainer will be very helpful so even after training, you still have reference you can look back.“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of trainer’s references
“Should have a follow-up training for certain topics. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group follow-ups
“Training should be longer“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Small programs and orientations- like different online skills that meets the demand online“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings by DICT
“If we are to assume trainees are newbies to ICT, the Digital Marketing comprehensive module should be adjusted to take into account the psychology of learners. Based on my experience (considering I am a certified trainer myself), the current module is overwhelming. The process of learning should not be overwhelming, but should be fun, to be effective and for the knowledge transfer to be more permanent. The learning experience the trainee undergoes should be a positive one not a stressful one. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjustment of module for beginning trainees • Fun and effective learning • Positive learning, not stressful
“comprehensive is too comprehensive / longer time is needed/ the lack of self confidence when skills is required to land the needed job hiring online“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjustment of module • Longer training days • Improvement of trainees’ self-confidence
“Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the requirements“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Before training ends trainees should have prepared resume and check thoroughly by trainer to at least a trainee will be hired for at least one online job“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group follow-ups
“Training should have a longer time period“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Updates on the module. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjustment of module
“Training should not be crammed. Half-day classes should be enough. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Half-day classes
“A quick check for graduates regarding the status of their application and provision of guidance in improving their profile and application letters. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Utilization of nearest Group follow-ups
“Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the req’s.“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Training days should be longer and they should provide fast and reliable internet connection with good facilities.“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Stable Internet connectivity

“Training on communication(English).“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication skills training
“Improve training venues.“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Venue of training facility
“Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the requirements“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“More time on training“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Training should be longer to accomplish the tasks correctly and hands-on application is very important to be considered in the training so that the participants can apply the actual correct method on the computers.“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Hands-on application in training module
“Training days should be longer“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“They should expand their locations to help other people especially on the provinces. “	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion of training locations
“Create more Tech4Ed centers and Digital hubs.“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of Tech4Ed centers and digital hubs
“Longer training days and to get together more often to immediately adhere to quintessential information“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Group get-togethers
“Must provide job after the training“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of online jobs
“hardware“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of ICT equipment
“Should be in longer time“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“There should be a specific training course. ”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific training course
“More training should be launch“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings by DICT
“I hope DJT will improve on opening more room for more participants as there’s only limit to 25 per session“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More participants per batch
“More guide in entering the online freelancing community“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More guide in entering online freelancing
“LONGER DAYS FOR TRAINING“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“There should be shorter but concise number of campaign period to trim down from 21 but more days of training“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shorter campaign period • Longer training days
“Nothing, I am satisfied“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing to improve
“Get-together more often after the training“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group get-togethers
“Establishment of hubs in barangays or key areas just like DTI’s GoNegosyo Center“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Jobs should be provided to participants or guide in landing into jobs after the training“	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of online jobs
“Improve venues for trainings ”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve venue

“Longer training days and more time to accomplish the tasks”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“More time for training”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Longer period of time for training”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Provide stable Internet connection so that there is no breaks or halts in the classes”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“More training days to finish the tasks,5 days in a week will do”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Establishment of freelancing hubs or co-working spaces in DICT offices”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs/co-working spaces
“DJT should improve on its trainers and encourage the graduates to also become trainers”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve trainers’ quality • Encourage graduates to be trainers
“During screening of applicants, DICT must see to it that everyone is one the same level. There are others who are advanced while others have no idea of what is being taught.”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper screening and levelling-off of participants
“DJT should improve its screening and selection of trainees”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper screening and levelling-off of participants
“DICT should always follow up on their trainees especially that others leave the training even if there is a training bond for those who have not finished”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group follow-ups
“Days for learning should be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Longer training days but lesser time or if possible, no more campaign period”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • No campaign period
“DJT trainers must be well versed and have good command in communicating to their learners”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of quality trainers • Trainers’ communication skills
“Provide better Internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“DICT must have its own venue for these trainings to be conducted – less expenses for the government or partners”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permanent venue for trainings
“Longer training days as everything is crammed in a matter of 8 days or so”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Training days should be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Establishment of DJT hubs in DICT Centers where trainees can do assignments”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Training days should be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“DICT should market DJT to its fullest extent so that many will participate”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing and publicity

“Better internet connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer time to do assignments or tasks”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“As the lessons rely heavily on the Internet, make the Internet connection faster”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“DICT must improve on its facilities for the trainees to do their tasks or assignments. Not all have Internet at their homes so it would help for DICT to provide areas with free connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of DICT facilities • Provision of free Internet connection
“Training days should be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access/connection”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“Nothing more, I am satisfied. ”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing to improve
“Establishment of DJT hubs ”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Better internet connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“Training days should be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Improve the training’s Internet speed”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“Improvement on the module as I believe some matters are already obsolete and not the industry standards anymore”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjustment of module
“Online freelancing entails stable and fast Internet connection”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity • Faster Internet connectivity
“Length of training must be longer to accommodate some breathing for the trainees”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Centers with Internet provision so trainees can do their tasks after the training”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Training days should be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Establishment of centers or hubs with Internet connection”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Training days should be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Establishment of training venues or hubs that can accommodate multiple people”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs

“Securing fast and reliable Internet connection is a must”	Fast Internet connectivity Stable Internet connectivity
“Nothing”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing to improve
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“More time to prepare the assignments or tasks given and improve the quality of Internet connection. Although I have Internet connection in where I live, some of my classmates or batchmates do not have”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Please I hope DJT can improve its length of the training. I’m shocked that the deadline for a task is nearing but it requires a lot of effort”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“DJT must improve its venues and facilities where they conduct the training”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of training venue
“Support of the LGU must really be evident, not only from DICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evident LGU support
“Improve internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training days”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“More time to finish the lessons and less tasks as some are burdensome”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connection”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“DJT must be longer in terms of its number of training days”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Establishment of DJT hubs”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Please improve the connectivity. Sometimes we have nothing to do because there is no Internet connection in the first place”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“More training days, less assignments”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Lesser assignments/tasks
“Adding in or transforming DICT offices into coworking spaces where it can be used as training venues or venues to finish trainees’ tasks”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs • Permanent training venues

“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“DJT must improve on its marketing collaterals. Some of my friends do not know that there is an existing training”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing and publicity
“Longer training days”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Please make the Internet connection faster or not dwindling”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“DICT must consider spreading the word about the training more and more to provide more opportunities to the public. ”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing and publicity
“More hours for training”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Establishment of DJT hubs”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connectivity so that we can finish on time”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Establishment of more Tech4Ed hubs or training locations with free Internet connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of Tech4Ed centers/digital hubs
“More marketing promotions. I never know of this training not until my former workmate told me so”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing and publicity
“Better internet provider”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“Establishment of DigitalJobs hubs aside from the training venues that are accessible to the public to finish tasks or perform assignments”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of Tech4Ed centers/digital hubs
“Make Internet access not just an option but a necessity for the training, if possible even after the training”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training sessions/number of days for training”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Establishment of DJT hubs”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Improve the module as some thigs are not updated anymore. I know there are new bills or laws regarding online freelancing but were not discussed”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjustment of module
“Longer hours for training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity

“Establishment of DJT hubs”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“More days to learn online freelancing”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connection”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Please make the training longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Establishment of DJT hubs”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“Internet at some point lags because there are many users accessing all at the same time. I hope this is improved”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Provide better venue, good and stable connection, a trainer who is not only a freelancer but also with good communication skills”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Venue for training • Stable Internet connectivity • Quality trainer with good communication skills
“There should be longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Establishment of DJT centers or hubs”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital hubs
“The number of days seem lacking, it must be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connection”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training hours or sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Improve quality of trainers that can really deliver”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of trainers
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“Training days must be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Trainers must really know what they are talking about”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of trainers
“Training must be longer as it’s as if everything is crammed”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“An Internet connection that can accommodate multiple users all at the same time. Imagine 25 or so trainees connected to one access point. ”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Improve quality of trainers”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of trainers
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity

“Not only should the trainees be screened, also the trainers who must be approachable”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper screening of trainees • Proper screening of approachable trainers
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Trainers should be accommodating. They are key to the success of the graduates”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accommodating trainers
“Improve its campaign in promoting the existence of this opportunity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing and publicity
“Access to Internet must be given priority so that everyone can comprehend, especially trainees who are beginners”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“DJT should improve the quality of the trainers. Our trainer has to invite another speaker to talk about Wordpress”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality trainers
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Better and more aggressive marketing promotions by DICT or the organizers”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing and publicity
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“DICT must see to it that their trainers are really equipped and has a passion for teaching”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipped trainers with passion for teaching
“Longer training days and trainers must be of good quality, trainers who are not only book smart but also street smart”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days • Quality trainers
“Better internet connection”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“DJT trainers must also learn from the students”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality trainers also learners
“Training sessions must be longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access please”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Trainers of DJT must be well versed and good in speaking, not only in online freelancing”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality trainers effective in communication • Quality trainers well versed in online freelancing
“Longer training sessions for everyone to grasp the lessons”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Stable Internet connection for everyone to enjoy”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity

“I myself am a trainer and teacher and I see that our trainer is not that efficient in delivering the modules, although points to her for being motherly”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient quality trainers
“Longer training sessions”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet access”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable Internet connectivity
“Longer days for trainings”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days
“Better internet connectivity”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster Internet connectivity
“Short period of training, here’s hoping DICT consider making the number of days for the course/module longer”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer training days

Table 4.2

Open-Ended Question 2 (OEQ2): “What can you suggest to help improve the program and provide continuity of graduates' online freelancing involvement?”

<u>Survey extract</u>	<u>Codes</u>
Election of batch officers Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings, • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>I think All of the above must be checked here but the most important that the graduates will land a job and not left them behind. Although they have the skills but the confidence them to apply is another hindrance factor of why they don't pursue on applying on the freelancing jobs. It should have a coaching system so that every graduates will land into jobs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graduates landing into jobs • Follow-up system
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Webinar by fellow batchmate

<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT
<p>Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

<p>Election of batch officers Cluster-wide online meeting Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Cluster-wide online meeting • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT

<p>Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • More trainings conducted by DICT • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc) • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Election of batch officers Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Cluster-wide online meeting</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cluster-wide online meeting
<p>Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).
<p>Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, You should focus on teaching students how to find clients since that is where most freelancers struggle.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Teach students to find clients
<p>Clients provided by DICT or projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clients provided by DICT
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT

Cluster-wide online meeting
More trainings conducted by DICT
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).
Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate

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<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Quarterly meetings • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate

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Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate, Job Matching

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- Quarterly meetings
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- Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
- Webinar by fellow batchmate,
- Job Matching

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Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).
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<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc) • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc) • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Not at all</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not at all
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc) • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc) • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

<p>Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc) • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
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<p>Quarterly meetings Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc) • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers Cluster-wide online meeting Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Cluster-wide online meeting • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, If graduates will organize themselves into a freelancer group or digital agency, they should be given trainings on management, business, leadership, entrepreneurship and financial literacy as well because technical training is just a starting point. Moving forward as an entrepreneur, they need guidance and assistance with the right agencies that can help them to succeed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc) • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Other trainings for organized groups
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate

Election of batch officers, Webinar by fellow batchmate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • More trainings conducted by DICT
<p>I suggest DICT will create a online portal mainly for 'DICT Graduates'. There DICT can provide the graduates an entryway to a variety of helpful information, tools, links to legit online homebased jobs, and a forum between the graduates where they can share thoughts about freelancing and online jobs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online portal for graduates • Forums among graduates
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

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<p>More trainings conducted by DICT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More trainings conducted by DICT
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<p>Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Webinar by fellow batchmate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Webinar by fellow batchmate
<p>Quarterly meetings Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
<p>Election of batch officers Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

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<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
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Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
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<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
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Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
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<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
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<p>Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
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<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers

Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers

Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
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<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers

<p>Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Quarterly meetings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings
<p>Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers
<p>Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
<p>Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
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Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quarterly meetings • Election of batch officers
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Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings • Cluster-wide online meeting • More trainings conducted by DICT • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub
Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub • Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). • Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

Table 4.3

Open-Ended Question 3 (OEQ3): “What other projects/programs by DICT that you want to participate in?”

<u>Survey extract</u>	<u>Code</u>
Webinars and talks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars and talks
Virtual assistant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training
ePayment and Cyber Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online payment and cybersecurity trainings
comprehensive training on graphic designing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphic design training
Many. the more skills that you have the higher chance to land job.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
Video Editing and Graphics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, I learned a lot like making portfolio for my job hunting.
Follow up with the graduates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DJT graduates' follow-ups
Anything that involves online jobs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job webinars and talks
Personality training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personality training
Seminars relating to financial aspects and rates of output and online tasks depending on client and output complexity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial seminars • Online job webinars and talks
They should conduct an intensive training for jobs like: setting up Fb Ads and Google Ads How to become an SEO specialist How to become a virtual assistant How to become an appointment setter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job trainings
I think graphic designs, because I am interested in designs and I want to learn and improve my skill	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphics design training
To have an online based tutorial. E-learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-learning training
Training customer service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer service training
It my pleasure to participate any training from DICT. Because iknow it will help me to my success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
Animations.. another skill to develop.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animation training • Other trainings
Dropshipping, Graphic Design, Animation, Lead Generation, Video Editing. Because they are also in demand jobs online.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
Virtual Assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training
Photoshop tutorial video editing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphics design training
e commerce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-commerce training
More elaboration about FB ad marketing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FB ad and marketing training
Web dev training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training

Virtual assistant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training
Trainings/ Webinars/Seminar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other webinars and trainings
As long as it could help me I will participate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
SEO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEO training
Webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars
Maybe seminars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminars
I want to be train more about graphic designs, and graphic arts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphics design training
Virtual Assistant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training
Digital Jobs Ph - SMM training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media marketing training
Anything and I'm so willing to participate anytime.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Web dev and graphics design.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web development training • Graphics design training
Website designing, and graphic designing to enhance our skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web design training • Graphics design training
I love to be part of the training program so that I can share also my knowledge to other who eager to learn more.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Become a trainer for DJT
Virtual Assistant and Video editing because I like data entry jobs and editing videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training • Video editing training
Training on virtual assistance in order to have more knowledge about the job	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training
Digital marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital marketing training
virtual assistant training, social media campaign and booster training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training • Social media campaigns • Skills enhancement training
I want to enroll E-commerce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-commerce training
Voice Account VA trainings or webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training • Other webinars
Focus on developing web	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training
Adobe Photoshop Virtual Assistant.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphics design training • Virtual assistance training
Trainings on coding/programming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coding/programming training
Online workshop, seminars, webinars and trainings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars

I'm interested in learning Shopify, Amazon FBA, eBay listing, Magento, and other eCommerce platforms. Off-Page SEO is also another one. Video creation/editing is also important because social media is big on videos these days. More people engage with video content posts compared to photos.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online freelancing trainings • Video editing training
Web developing, this is my favorite	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training
Workshops & trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings and workshops
Messenger automation, Animation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online freelancing trainings • Animation training
I want to teach others. But I need to experience the actual world of online freelancing that I can share with my trainees too.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Become a trainer for DJT
Video editing Training/seminars, comprehensive SEO training, follow up webinars etc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video editing training • Other trainings and webinars
Digitaljobs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DJT
Tech4ed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4Ed
Seminars about improvement or best way to do each freelancing skills in order to be competitive. I suggest webinar or training in Shopify and should have enough time to teach all necessary topics.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Social media training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media management training
Seminar/ actual training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminars • Other trainings
Graphic Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphics design training
Web development, if possible, programming and graphic design is a big help.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training • Programming training • Graphic design training
Training related on digital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital marketing training
Topics about social media management and customer service management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media management training • Other trainings
Helpful skills as video editing, photo editing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video editing training • Graphics design training
I would love to participate for another face-to-face training.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
Drop shipping, lead generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online freelancing trainings

The new normal now is really going online. DICT should offer more webinars, but, perhaps not just on technical or Digital Jobs PH trainings. Considering DICT is the technology agency of the government, perhaps, DICT can also work with other government agencies like DTI, for example, to create more relevant and holistic webinars to Filipinos. The economy is down due to the pandemic, so webinars that can easily empower Filipinos to earn would be relevant.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
I suggest that modules for basic training like Virtual Assistant , bookeeping online, transcribed and how we can be competitive to other applicants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online freelancing trainings
I would love to have a training on Web Design using HTML, CSS and Bootstrap 4 since I have gone training on Web Development using WordPress so that I can enhance my skills more in programming.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training • Programming and coding trainings
Enhancement of resume preparation that will encourage employers to at least try to hire graduate from the course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portfolio building training
Webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars
Application Development because in this time of crisis everybody needs legit information with just one tap of a finger. Hopefully an intensive program for e-payments too.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application development training
Digital marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital marketing training
Webdev	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training
Technical Support Trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical support trainings
Training on CSS and Java	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming/coding trainings
Trainings on essential online tools used by freelancers for their online jobs. (e.g. Photoshop, MS tools such as Advance Excel, Access, Outlook, Publisher, PowerPoint etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online freelancing trainings
I want to participate in their specific trainings to specialize in a specific niche.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
POS courses for businesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
Training on Graphic/Visual design, Programming, ESL to broaden my options in freelancing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graphics design training • Programming/coding training • ESL training
Seminars or webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminars and webinars
Basic IT courses since computer is really useful these days.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy training
Web design, programming, apps developer.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training • Programming and coding trainings

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application development training
All of it if possible, not only does this pace way to provide more opportunities but this too can mold characteristics of self sufficient individual that can support the nation as a whole	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Another Trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainigs
should have ESL training, because it's the only job that is flourishing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESL training
Comprehensive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital marketing and e-commerce training
Virtual Assistant and Lead Generation which is highly demand in an online jobs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training • Online freelancing trainings
I would like to participate any form of training in DICT to improve my knowledge and skills specially in Virtual Assistant, because i need to improve my knowledge and skills in that specific area.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings • Virtual assistance training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Tech4Ed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4Ed
I WOULD LIKE TO ATTEND TO ANOTHER COURSE OR MODULE OF DJT IF GIVEN THE CHANCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DJT
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Tech4Ed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4Ed
I think if there are cybersecurity trainings by DICT I would glad to be involved in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybersecurity trainings
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Tech4Ed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4Ed
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Tech4Ed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4Ed
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Join other trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars

Tech4Ed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4ed
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
If DICT will establish a coworking space or training center or facility, I wish to make use of such	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make use of DICT facilities
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Tech4Ed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4Ed
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
I hope to participate in more trainings conducted by DICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
I am interested in learning how to create a website for government agencies or LGUs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government website training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Tech4Ed trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4Ed trainings
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other RIS courses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other DJT trainings
Trainings on programming/web development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming training • Website development training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
More trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings

Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
I am interested in Government Web Hosting Services training of DICT to develop websites of LGUS, NGAS, ETC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government website training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Tech4Ed, PNPKI, Cyber security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech4Ed • Philippine National Public Key Infrastructure • Cybersecurity training
Other trainings or other DJT courses and modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars • Other DJT trainings
Free Wifi For All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of Free Wifi For All sites
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
If given the chance, I will attend other trainings by DICT if they are for free just like DJT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
I want to become a trainer for RIS/DJT too	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Become a DJT trainer
Free webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
More trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
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Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
DigitalJobsPH Web Development course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other DJT training

Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
DJT SMM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media marketing training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Training on web development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Trainings and webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other DJT module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other DJT training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Webinar topics like IoT, 4Ri, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet of Things webinar • Fourth Industrial Revolution webinar • Other webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Web development training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website development training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Training on online ESL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESL training
Application development like Android or ios.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application development training
I want to take the ICT Proficiency exam of DICT so that I have a chance to work in the government.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take the ICT Proficiency exam as civil service eligibility

Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
VA/virtual assistance course	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual assistance training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Webinars related to social media marketing and e-commerce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media marketing training • E-commerce training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Catch-up sessions among DJT graduates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graduates' catching up sessions
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Free trainings and webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Digital literacy trainings - I want to also share what I learned from the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy trainings • Become a trainer for other trainings
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Trainings that will improve my chances of being hired	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online freelancing trainings
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars

Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Training for social media marketing and ecommerce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media marketing training • E-commerce training
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Digital literacy training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DJT made me more skillful
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars
I want to have more Free Wifi sites from DICT in our locality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of Free Wifi sites in localities
Other trainings/webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other trainings and webinars

Table 4.4

Open-Ended Question 4 (OEQ4): “How has DJT/RIS changed your life?”

<u>Survey Extract</u>	<u>Code</u>
It opened doors to me and I can easily partner with the government for projects. I also widened my network and connections.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opened opportunities • Easy partnership with government projects • Widened network and connections
A bit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
Yes. a lot of improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement

through the training i was able to learn new knowledge and skills that is very helpful to this generation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new knowledge and skills
Its Okay.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
Yes, I learned a lot like making portfolio for my job hunting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portfolio creation • Job applications
Yes, in my computer knowledge.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new knowledge in terms of computers
I learned that there are many ways to earn money in online platforms you dont need to apply or become an employee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning of ways to earn income
DJT/RIS changed my life to inspired my self to work online with less stress.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspiration • Work with less stress • Job satisfaction
I've become involved and equipped with technical ideas and knowledge for professional skill applications.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of technical ideas
Many aspects actually	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple facets
DJT helped me build a career as an online freelancer/Virtual Assistant. I Work and earn money from the comfort of our home. And on top of that, I get to spend more time with my family. I am a working mom but a full time mom as well. I can say that I am financially stable. I invested some of my earnings to open a food business with my sister. we will start serving as soon as the covid19 crisis ends.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build online career • Working at home • More time with family • Working mother at the same time full-time mother • Financially stable • Investment of earnings to open a business
This time nothing at all yet but maybe in the future. But this training fill up my knowledge about SMM so kudos to all. Thank you for sharing your ideas about social media marketing to us.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty • Generation of knowledge
I got an ideas on how to work online.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of ideas
It help me to become a better person.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-improvement
Made me more confident when looking for a job	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More confidence in applying for a job
I am very much grateful for DJT program of DICT because I gained basic knowledge about online freelancing for free. I had the confidence to apply in different freelancing platforms. I am also grateful for my trainer.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of knowledge • Self-confidence in applying for a job
Its changed when it comes to understanding about digital marketing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of digital marketing
Gain confidence and courage to face challenges through task.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence
a lot from zero knoledge to 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of knowledge
Proper way of doing SMM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certainty in doing social media marketing

I was able to enhance my skills because of the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling
They enhancing my skills using digital.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling
It does not change ..It give me more knowlegde about selling your skills .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of knowledge
It really change my life because of dict I became a knowledgable person how to find job through online.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of knowledge • Confidence in applying for a job
I had more local connections.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More connections
A little bit improved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-improvement
<p>DJT/RIS changed my life in so many reasons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * I am now a computer literate. * I learn how to manage my time. * Self confidence, self motivated. * Discover new skills. * And now, I can be part of this online automated world. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of knowledge • Time management • Self-confidence and motivation • Discovery of new skills • Chance to join the online freelancing community
<p>Rural Impact Sourcing changed my view on freelancing. That you can work from home and everyone can be a freelancer. No matter what is your status in life, whether you normal person or PWD as long as you have the proper knowledge.</p> <p>RIS added experience and knowledge to my web development skills. It served as a stepping stone for a much higher chance of getting hired at upwork.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability and chance to work at home amid being members of the marginalized sectors • Upskilling of experiences • Generation of knowledge • DJT as stepping stone for better chances of working
Because of DJT/RIS I was able to find a job online.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of jobs
I learned a lot of things through this training, applied it to my bussiness and it really works. Now life is easy as it is.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learnings • Application of learnings to business • Improved life
DJT makes me digital literate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy
I learned a lot about social media marketing. And have more skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of knowledge on social media marketing • Upskilling
I am more competitive enough to work in any company.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence
Yes, I feel like I have elevated my static knowledge in the world of freelancing, I learned that it has a wide variety of opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening of knowledge • Wide variety of opportunities
I learn more digital skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling of digital literacy skills
It gave me confidence and opportunities in online freelancing even though I don't have any job yet rather than sticking to online tutor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence • Wide variety of opportunities • Uncertainty but confidence to land into an online freelancing job

It gives me confident to work online jobs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence
it made me more confident, and this confidence hugely changed my life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence
Internet has a lot of opportunities to offer. We just only need to discover it more and should leard how to earn income from it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide variety of opportunities
It helped me gain skills that I now used as a VA to my client	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling • Generation of job • Support to current job
Not Much	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
DJT/RIS change my life in a way that it helps me finding online home based job..	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More opportunities to work online
DJT/RIS had opened more windows of opportunities for me, both on the online and physical work area.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide variety of opportunities both for online and traditional jobs
It opens to more oppotunities for me about online jobs and e-commerce and e-marketing workspace and work at home. Thank you.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide variety of opportunities • Able to work at home
It has opened the world of online freelancing to me and has given me a way to be with my son more. I'm lucky to have been chosen as one of the scholars.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities to work online • More time with family
I dont know	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
DICT-RISTT E-Commerce has opened up fresh perspectives on digital opportunities which will impact societies in general. If the backbone of Philippine economy rests on MSMEs, the digital landscape is its horizon.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide variety of opportunities • Generation of new ideas and skills • Better philosophical view
It has realized my untapped potentials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling
I learned to push myself through the limit. It boosted my confidence in getting online job specially that my portfolio was improved.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence • Self-improvement
I was mold to become a productive citizen inspite of how covid affect us nowadays. I was able to improve my learned techniques in digial marketing particulary in social media. Helped some of my friends by sharing the skilss i learned from the training. Hoping and looking forward to explore more opportunities in digital world. Thanks and Godbless DICT!	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-improvement • Helping acquaintances by sharing skills • Exploring more opportunities
It made me more engaged in the new and basic advantage in digital technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy
It did not changed my life yet.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
It help me as a therapy as a stroke patient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-improvement as a member of the marginalized sector (stroke patient)
Yes, somehow I am now confident to apply in online jobs platform .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence

It has changed my life to take a step to the online jobs but not confident enough due to not enough full teach the web development and I was planning to propose to make the website of my previous employer in Saudi but I am afraid I may not give their expectations due to the knowledge I have right now although I have been viewing youtube tutorials but its different with the actual training.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training as stepping stone in online jobs • Uncertainty
Ive learned a lot of things with the DJT training but not everybody is fitted to be an online freelancer. If there is one thing i realized after the training, what we learned in the training room is very much different when you will be applying for a job. In my case, i have to stop due to health reasons. But it doesnt mean that i am giving up.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple facets of learning • Uncertainty of learning in training to actual jobs
Not at all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
Life Changing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple facets
It was a big advantage to me in applying everytime the employer saw it in my resume that I am a graduate of DJT/RIS and a lot of job positions to apply for.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence • Availability of multiple job positions
It opened my mind on how the digital works nowadays.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy
I already taken few steps into the freelancing world. It makes me more confident to face realities in life.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stepping stone in online freelancing • Self-confidence
It gave me more credentials that I can be more confident and qualified in applyingin online work.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More credibility • Self-confidence • More qualified in online jobs
It has opened the door for me to freelancing and I have never been so satisfied with my career until I experienced online job. RIS is a blessing to me and my family. Thank you DICT. More power!	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stepping stone in freelancing • Job satisfaction • Training as blessing
It improves my knowledge and skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of knowledge • Upskilling
It helped me open my mind to all possibilities online.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunities online
It has opened a lot of possibilities for me.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunities online
Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affirmation of DJT's life-changing goals
DJT taught a lot of new things and made me enhanced my skills and make me want to share my skills to others.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new learning
Had more learning on online jobs and technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new learning • Digital literacy
I acquired skills I can use in the future.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling
I did found another skill.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discovery of new skills
It has opened doors to new opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunities

It changed enough to be more hard-working and finishing task on time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be more hardworking • Time management
Gives me knowledge in digital field.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy
I learned a lot from the training and it helps me find a better job.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning new things • Better chances of finding a job
I am empowered to build site using wordpress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowerment • Upskilling • Digital literacy
Being recognized as DICT graduate is a life changing already. DICT is like giving eligibility to the graduates to work online. Contributing to the online workforce. Forever thankful and grateful to DICT who provided training opportunity to individuals like me, so thank you very much.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Credibility for graduates to work online
DJT/RIS helped me to be more responsible in handling tasks and tracking what I do. I am also able to wake up early without using an alarm clock since the training days.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-improvement, i.e., being more responsible in tasks • Time management
Knowledgeable to online world	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of knowledge
It gave me a better perspective that life indeed should go on and that it gave me a chance to be productive even after retirement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better philosophical view and standpoint • Wider opportunities even on retirement
Not so much right now	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
Wow, haha. They conducted a really useful seminar that can be used in daily life.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple facets
It gives me more knowledge about the digital world and making me digitally literate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new knowledge • Digital literacy
I've been much more open to the many possibilities and opportunities around me if I look for it	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunities
Not really	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
a bit...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
DICT change my life in online industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple facets
As a student, DJT changed my life by providing an extra income thru part-time job	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Earning extra income through additional jobs even if still a student
RIS give me so much confident in applying for a Job both offline and online, it gives me a lot of opportunity I got hired by the municipal after the Training and currently i am working at TESDA also i have a parttime job online.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence • Wider opportunities • Employment in an NGA • Part-time online jobs
I now work online, thanks to DJT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment
I BECOME MORE TECHY AS A PERSON	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy

I landed into an online job, more time for my family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment
I am now working online!	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment
I am now working online and provide for my family as I have 2 kids and sickly parents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • Financial support to family
It allowed me to be more particular in clerical stuff and always check and recheck my works in the office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-improvement
I now have multiple gigs or freelancing companies and I would like to train others who would like to become online freelancers like me too	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • To share to others the knowledge learned
From working in fast food chains, I am now working at home able to support my family's needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • Financial support to family
As an out-of-school youth who only finish high school, being rejected by companies because of lack of education, I am now working for an international advertising company as a content creator and graphics designer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized sector (OSY)
I am now working online and the certificate I gained from RIS became my passport to landing into online jobs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • Wider opportunities
I can now travel and work at the same time because I am into an online job that has flexible time scheme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travel and work at the same time without issues or hindrances • Flexibility of time
It changed me in terms of being able to provide food on the table	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support to family
It changed my life for just a bit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
I am a single mom but with the online jobs that I have, I am able to provide for my children, thanks to DICT's trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • Financial support to family
Not at all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
I stopped schooling and college drop-out because of financial but I think I can go back to school now since I can support my schooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To continue school with earnings from online job employment
I am introvert but thanks to DJT where I met my fellow trainees, I became more confident especially in landing into online jobs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-improvement • Self-confidence
I am now working online and I love this kind of job where I have more time for my family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment
COVID19 pandemic didn't affect me at all because I still have my online job with me. While others lost their jobs, I have something that support me	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • Not losing job even if there is pandemic
I have additional online gigs after the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional online job employment

I was able to send my 2 children to private schools. Before when I do not have online job, they are studying public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support to family • Provide better education to children
I was able to buy a secondhand car	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition of wealthy possession
Thanks DICT, I have a chance to go to China and continue my online job there	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunity to travel abroad • Online job employment
Me and my batchmates were able to launch a digital startup agency for those who want to create their websites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of agency
Not changed at all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
It gave me connections to other online freelancers not only in our province but the whole of Philippines and other countries too	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider connections to other freelancers including overseas
It helped me in my freelancing career and I was able to renovate our house which is now my working place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved online freelancing career • Renovation of house • Working at home
My batchmates from Bayawan created our own group where we are a digital marketing agency catering to the needs of those who wants our services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of digital agency
As a PWD with polio, I am earning at home where I don't need to leave our house to earn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized group (PWD)
Not at all changed, just slight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
I'm tapped to develop websites of international brands and gain money from this. Aside from financial, I am emotionally satisfied because the training boost my confidence in applying in online jobs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • Financial gain • Emotional gain • Self-confidence
Slightly changed in terms of additional item in resume	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty • Improvement of portfolio
I was able to buy a laptop to continue my online career	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investment in ICT equipment • Online job employment
I can now afford what my children wants. Although I am not sure until when this will be but I'm enjoying it as of the moment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support to family
I learned new things for free	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new learnings
Before Im afraid or has phobia in using computers, now I can say I am improved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Self-improvement
It changed me careerwise. I left my office daytime job and concentrated in fully working online.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in career • Online job employment

I am no longer a son who waits for my parents' allowance, I can now provide on my own and there are times I'm the one giving them even if I am just only a student	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-supporting financially amid being a student • Financial support to family
Still the same jobless	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
At daytime I work in the LGU, at night time or when I have free time I work online which supports my financial obligations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More work opportunities • Online job employment
Not really	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
Still the same before but I have included DJT in my portfolio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty • Improvement of portfolio
None at all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
DJT changed my perspective in life. I thought that being old and senior citizen, I am now turning 61, I cannot work anymore. But now, I am partner with my son we are both working online and we enjoy life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in philosophical views • Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized sector (senior citizen)
I am more aware of the online careers and opportunities we have in this world. Although I am not yet working online, I see myself working one day when I am ready and when I already have the equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of online opportunities • Wider opportunities for employment • Positive mindset towards working online
I found out I have other skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realization of skills
The training paved the way for me to find my niche. I am a vlogger, just a small YouTuber with no other means of income. Because of the training I have something to put or add in my contents that I'm pretty sure will help my viewers, and also me for monetization.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-discovery of niche • Wider opportunities to share • Generation of income
New learnings and skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new learnings • Upskilling
Aside from gaining friends and fellow online freelancers, my classmates in the training, it also opened more opportunities for me to work sideline. I have midnight jobs and this really helps me because I am a single parent.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaining of peers • Wider opportunities for part-time work • Financial support to family amid being a member of the marginalized group (solo parent)
Not at all changed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
My life has changed in such a way that I am already working online and I left my job in the BPO to concentrate working online. I have more time for my family as I can work anytime.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • More time for family • Time management
New skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling

As an IT professional, I acquired new learnings that I didn't study during college. I already have an online presence with my own website and I have clients who hire me for their websites.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new learnings • Digital literacy • Online job employment
Just the same	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
I gained a lot of friends, learnings, and opportunities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New peers • Additional learning • Wider opportunities
DJT made me aware of the opportunities online, compared to day-job work. The salary is higher and more competitive than my regular work.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunities • Better income
I once had phobia in using computers but now I am more confident thanks to the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Self-confidence
I have become more digital literate,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy
Being a member of the marginalized sector as an out-of-school youth, availing the free training helped me a lot in terms of jobs generation. I am now working online and it proves that even if I don't have a diploma I can still make it in online world.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized group (OSY)
Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affirmation
Nothing much	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
I have a business and with DJT I was able to still sell and earn even if there is pandemic and lockdown because I transitioned to online selling which I learned from the DJT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to continue business amid pandemic • Generation of income
DJT served its purpose in providing opportunities to the countryside. There are limited jobs in the province and with online freelancing and good Internet connection I can earn even if there is few opportunities from day jobs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More opportunities provided • Online job employment amid fewer or less work opportunities in the countryside
The training provided opportunity to grow. I might have not been successful in terms of schooling or education, I can provide proper education to my children as I earn through online.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunities • Financial support to family • Online job employment
It made me more confident.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence
It made me more independent without having to ask money from my parents or family and relatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-support financially
I am a teacher by profession but I opted not to practice my profession because I find it stressful. In online freelancing which I learned from DJT, I enjoy working at my own pace at my own time. It's very convenient for solo parents like me.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility of time • Career shift • Convenience of work • Job satisfaction • Financial support to family amid being a single parent

The training helped me a lot in terms of finances. As the pay is bigger and higher online compared to traditional work, I am able to provide more for my family. I learned online freelancing with the help of DICT's DigitalJobs training and I really appreciated the efforts of my trainer and DICT to mould as as freelancers. I am very thankful to the team.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better income • Financial support to family
It helped me grow my network being an already existing online freelancer prior to joining the training.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing of network • Self-improvement
A lot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple facets
I learned more digital skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Upskilling
More confidence in applying online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-confidence
It changed me in terms of my perspective in life. Before I felt lost in which job is suited for me. I always lose my determination in working everytime I find it routine. But with the help of DJT, I am now working online and I can say that I like how dynamic it is working online. Different job roles, different tasks. The salary is also higher.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in philosophical standpoint or view • Self-confidence • More determined • Online job employment • Dynamic job roles • Job satisfaction • Higher pay or income
Not really	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
I learned the skills necessary for online freelancing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling.
It changed my outlook in working. Before, the chances of being hired is earning a degree or having a backer. In online freelancing, you can prove yourself worthy to be hired by showing your portfolio or your works. The certificate provided by DICT really helped me in landing into an online job.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change of work outlook • Improved portfolio • Online job employment
It changed me in terms of being able to provide more for my family.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support to family
DJT changed me in terms of growth in mindset. I became more skillful and compassionate in helping others to also succeed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth in mindset • Upskilling • More compassionate to help others
It made me even better in terms of the technical aspects of my knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Upskilling • Generation of knowledge
DJT brought me a lot of blessings. For one, I am now working online. The money I earned from freelancing also allowed me to put up my own buy and sell business.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online job employment • Setting up of own business
None so far	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
RIS or DJT proved me that there are opportunities just waiting and you can be successful if you really given efforts to finish the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunities

I am more equipped in terms of technical knowledge and skills and I can now contribute to the bills in our house	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Upskilling
I discovered that I have talent. Imagine, an out of school youth who once worked as a cashier and waitress now earns more than those who are blessed in life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-discovery of talents • Online job employment • Better income
Continuous improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-improvement/growth
Before the training, I am a plain housewife, in my 50s, with teenage children. I have basic computer knowledge as I used to work once in a bank as a teller before resigning. The training changed my life as I know more about computer stuff and I am currently working on the side while being a full-time mom. Thanks DICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Upskilling • Online job employment
Now more than ever, I can provide for my family due to the learnings I gotten from the training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support to family
Many to mention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple facets
Just a few changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty
I'm not yet working online but I will try to become once I have my own computer. I am confident to enter the freelancing community since I learned a lot from the program.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive mindset and outlook • Self-confidence
I became more aware of the online opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness of online opportunities
I was able to raise money for the operation of my mother through online freelancing. I also have time to stay beside her during hospital admission because I can carry with me my work – laptop and with my own time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support to family • Flexibility of time • Accessibility of work.
I was able to pay my debts because of working online which I learned through DJT. I am now debt-free and as a matter of fact, I'm the one lending now.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to pay debts • Financial support
I am the breadwinner of the family and through the training, I became able to support my family more.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support to family
DJT made me more skillful	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upskilling
The training allowed me to widen my horizons as I became more professional in the online freelancing community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider opportunities • Online job employment
The training changed me in so many ways as to how I value time and effort. Before that I wasn't into online freelancing yet, I would not make importance of the time. But in online freelancing, it taught me to make use of time wisely because we can be cramming in finishing our tasks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value of time and effort • Change in philosophical views
I am more knowledgeable and skillful about computers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital literacy • Upskilling
More knowledge learned about online freelancing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of new learnings

Generating of Themes

The codes from the previous step allowed a condensed overview of the main points and common meanings that recur throughout the data.

After the coding step, the proponent has combined codes into single themes that best represent and encapsulate the patterns that link all other codes.

The following tables are the themes generated for every open-ended question.

The themes, after careful review, will be analyzed in depth and discussed in the succeeding chapter on Results and Discussion.

Table 4.5

Open-Ended Question 1 (OEQ1): “What should RIS/DJT improve on?”

Codes	Theme
Longer training days, Days of training should be longer	Training days
Actual training methods, Adjustment of module, Adjustment of module for beginning trainees, Advanced lessons, Communication skills training, Comprehensive training, Continuation of training, Easier training for starters, Fun and Effective Learning, Half-day classes, Hands-on application in training module, Improvement of trainees' self-confidence, In-demand skills for beginners, Lesser assignments/tasks, Niche concentration, No campaign period, Positive learning, not stressful, Shorter campaign period, Specific training, Specific training course, Specific training per scholar, Subject concentration, Trainees' focus on knowledge gathering, Encourage graduates to be trainers, Improvement of ICT equipment, More participants per batch, More trainings, More trainings by DICT, MSME's participation, Proper screening and levelling-off of participants	Training Module and Methods
Utilization of nearest Group follow-ups, Creation of groups, Creation of website/social media account, Graduate mentorship, Group follow-ups, Group get-togethers, Quarterly meetings, Required voluntary teaching of graduates, Expansion of training locations	Post-Training Gatherings of Graduates

Client provision, Provision of equipment, Provision of free Internet connection, Provision of ICT equipment, Provision of online clients, Provision of online jobs to graduates, Provision of online jobs, Provision of trainer's references, Availability of equipment , Availability of equipment , Mentoring/coaching, More guide in entering online freelancing	Post-Training Support by DICT
Marketing and publicity, Publicity, Evident LGU support	Marketing and Promotions
Nothing to Improve	None (satisfaction)

Table 4.6

Open-Ended Question 2 (OEQ2): “What can you suggest to help improve the program and provide continuity of graduates' online freelancing involvement?”

Codes	Theme
Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc), Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Post-Training Provision and Support of DICT
Cluster-wide online meeting, Follow-up system, Quarterly meetings, Election of batch officers	Follow-ups of Graduates
Forums among graduates, Webinar by fellow batchmate, More trainings conducted by DICT	Post-Training Activities and Gatherings of Graduates
Clients provided by DICT, Graduates landing into jobs, Job Matching, Online portal for graduates, Teach students to find clients	Post-Training Online Job Support by DICT
Not at all	Nothing to Improve

Table 4.7

Open-Ended Question 3 (OEQ3): “What other projects/programs by DICT that you want to participate in and why?”

Codes	Theme
Animation training, Application development training, Coding/programming training, Customer service training, Cybersecurity trainings, Cybersecurity trainings, Digital literacy training, Digital literacy trainings, Digital marketing training, Digital marketing and e-commerce training, E-commerce training, E-learning training, ESL Training, FB ad and marketing training, Financial seminars, Graphic design training, Graphics design training, Government website training, Fourth Industrial Revolution webinar, Online freelancing trainings, Online job trainings, Internet of Things webinar, Online job webinars and talks, Online payment and cybersecurity trainings, Other trainings, Other webinars and trainings, Other trainings and webinars, Other webinars, Personality training, Programming training, Programming and coding trainings, Portfolio building training, Programming/coding trainings, Programming/coding training, Seminars, Seminars and webinars, SEO training, Social media marketing training, Skills enhancement training, Social media management training, Trainings and workshops, Technical support trainings, Video editing training, Virtual assistance training, Web design training, Web development training, Webinars , Webinars and talks, Website development training	Other trainings and webinars
DJT graduates' follow-ups, DJT, DJT made me more skillful, Graduates' catching up sessions, Other DJT trainings, Other DJT training, Social media campaigns, Yes, I learned a lot like making portfolio for my job hunting.	DigitalJobsPH
Tech4Ed, Tech4Ed trainings	Tech4Ed
Become a trainer for DJT, Become a DJT Trainer, Become a trainer for other trainings	DigitalJobsPH Trainer
Make use of DICT facilities	DICT facilities
Philippine National Public Key Infrastructure	PNPKI
Take the ICT Proficiency exam as civil service eligibility	ICT Proficiency Exam

Table 4.8

Open-Ended Question 4 (OEQ4): “How has DJT/RIS changed your life?”

Codes	Theme
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Additional online job employment, Availability of multiple job positions, Better chances of finding a job, Build online career, Certainty in doing social media marketing, Chance to join the online freelancing community, DJT as stepping stone for better chances of working, Dynamic job roles, Earning extra income through additional jobs even if still a student, Employment in an NGA, Exploring more opportunities, Generation of income, Generation of job, Generation of jobs, Higher pay or income, Improved online freelancing career, Improved portfolio, Improvement of portfolio, Improvement in career, Job applications, More opportunities to work online, More qualified in online jobs, More opportunities provided, More work opportunities, Not losing job even if there is pandemic, Online job employment, Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized sector (OSY), Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized group (PWD), Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized sector (senior citizen), Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized group (OSY), Online job employment amid fewer or less work opportunities in the countryside, Opened opportunities, Opportunities to work online, Part-time online jobs, Support to current job, Stepping stone in online freelancing, Stepping stone in freelancing, Training as stepping stone in online jobs, Training as blessing, Wide variety of opportunities, Wide variety of opportunities both for online and traditional jobs, Wider opportunities, Wider opportunities online, Wider opportunities even on retirement, Wider opportunities for employment, Wider opportunities for part-time work, Affirmation, Affirmation of DJT's life-changing goals, Multiple facets

**Employment
Opportunities and
Income Generation**

Additional learning, Awareness of online opportunities, Credibility for graduates to work online, Digital literacy, Generation of ideas, Generation of knowledge, Generation of knowledge on social media marketing, Generation of new ideas and skills, Generation of new knowledge and skills, Generation of new knowledge in terms of computers, Generation of technical ideas, Generation of new learning, Generation of new knowledge, Generation of new learnings, Improvement of knowledge, Learning new things, Learning of ways to earn income, Learnings, More credibility, Multiple facets of learning, Realization of skills, Strengthening of knowledge, Understanding of digital marketing, Upskilling, Upskilling of experiences, Upskilling of digital literacy skills

**Digital Literacy and
Upskilling**

Be more hardworking, Better philosophical view, Better philosophical view and standpoint, Career shift, Change in philosophical standpoint or view, Change in philosophical views, Change of work outlook, Confidence in applying for a job, Discovery of new skills, Emotional gain, Empowerment, Growth in mindset, Improved life, Improvement, More confidence in applying for a job, More determined, Portfolio creation, Positive mindset towards working online, Positive mindset and outlook, Self-improvement, Self-confidence in applying for a job, Self-confidence, Self-confidence and motivation, Self-improvement as a member of the marginalized sector (stroke patient), Self-improvement, i.e., being more responsible in tasks, Self-discovery of niche, Self-discovery of talents, Self-improvement/growth, Value of time and effort

**Self-Confidence, Self-
Growth, and
Development**

<p>Able to pay debts, Acquisition of wealthy possession, Better income, Financial gain, Financial support, Financial support to family, Financial support to family amid being a member of the marginalized group (solo parent), Financial support to family amid being a single parent , Financially stable, Investment in ICT equipment, Provide better education to children, Renovation of house, Self-supporting financially amid being a student, Self-support financially, To continue school with earnings from online job employment</p>	<p>Financial Stability and Support</p>
<p>Ability and chance to work at home amid being members of the marginalized sectors, Able to work at home, Accessibility of work., Convenience of work, Flexibility of time, Job satisfaction, More time with family, More time for family, Time management, Travel and work at the same time without issues or hindrances, Wider opportunity to travel abroad, Work with less stress, Working at home, Working mother at the same time full-time mother</p>	<p>Flexibility of Time and Ability to Work at Home</p>
<p>Ability and chance to work at home amid being members of the marginalized sectors, Financial support to family amid being a member of the marginalized group (solo parent), Financial support to family amid being a single parent , Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized sector (OSY), Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized group (PWD), Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized sector (senior citizen), Online job employment amid being a member of the marginalized group (OSY), Online job employment amid fewer or less work opportunities in the countryside, Self-improvement as a member of the marginalized sector (stroke patient), Self-supporting financially amid being a student, To continue school with earnings from online job employment</p>	<p>Capacitated Marginalized Sectors</p>
<p>Easy partnership with government projects, Gaining of peers, Growing of network, More connections, New peers, Widened network and connections, Wider connections to other freelancers including overseas</p>	<p>Growth of Peers, Networking, and Partnership</p>
<p>Application of learnings to business, Establishment of agency, Establishment of digital agency, Investment of earnings to open a business, Setting up of own business</p>	<p>Setting Up of New Business</p>
<p>Helping acquaintances by sharing skills, Inspiration, More compassionate to help others, To share to others the knowledge learned, Wider opportunities to share</p>	<p>Skills Sharing</p>
<p>Uncertainty, Uncertainty but confidence to land into an online freelancing job, Uncertainty of learning in training to actual jobs</p>	<p>Uncertainty</p>

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thematic Analysis

After careful review of the codes and corresponding themes that were generated, the tables that follow list and define all the themes per open-ended question.

Table 5.1

Open-Ended Question 1 (OEQ1): “What should RIS/DJT improve on?”

Training days	<p>This refers to the number of days that the training proper is conducted, excluding the launching (referred as “Day 0”), 21-day campaign period (trainees will have to seek for actual online jobs – no more face-to-face training), assessment day, and graduation. Depending on the course or module, the number of training days vary, ranging from 8 days to 12 days. These days are staggered, meaning the days are not done consecutively. There may be 2 or 3 days per week, leading to a month or so of training proper. This gives more time for the trainees to do their weekly tasks, where they can submit on the next weekly meeting.</p> <p>Majority of the respondents, 95 of them, clamored for longer days of training. They find the training short and would like to increase the number of training days.</p>
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Training Module and Methods

All the training course modules nationwide were designed by a former consultant tapped by DICT, except for the Online ESL course. Most of the modules were based on a real-life approach, where trainees have to learn and make use of the various applications and tools used in online freelancing. They also have a 21-day campaign period, where during this time they will be looking for potential online clients after a rigorous training. The ESL course is in partnership with an online ESL company, where they train potential online ESL teachers on how they teach online. Meanwhile, the training methods depend on each DICT cluster on how they make the training more effective. Annually, pre-pandemic, the DJT implementers nationwide sit down and talk together with the DICT Central Office and the consultant for the review, suggestions, and improvements of the training courses and methods. A year-end assessment was done to not only recognize the effective DJT implementers but most of all discuss improvements and revisions of the trainings.

87 respondents for OEQ1 answered that there should be adjustments, improvements, and modifications in the training module and methodologies. Some of them suggested other trainings apart from the online freelancing course, like trainings for communication skills. Others suggested for a fun and effective learning, positive learning and not stressful, and easier training especially for beginners who have little or no knowledge in online freelancing. A number of respondents said that selection and proper screening and levelling-off of participants must be taken into consideration, and a specific training or course must be provided and aligned to the participant depending on his level of skills. Respondents also seek for improvement of ICT equipment used and provided during the training.

Post-Training Graduates Gatherings of It is highly encouraged for the DICT cluster to make follow-ups and catch-up sessions among the batches of trainings. Although the training literally ends after the graduation day, what happens after is optional for the DJT implementers. It is ideal that various activities be conducted that will gather and follow up the graduates especially on how and what they are doing after the training.

A handful of graduates, 14 of them, answered that quarterly meetings, group get-togethers, and creation of groups and web sites should be done to improve DJT. These gatherings and activities allow for more visible presence of the graduates in the community, especially in rural areas. Their presence and movement would allow their countryside to be aware of online job opportunities, with them being classic examples of online job workers, and as products of DJT.

Post-Training Support by DICT

As mentioned in the previous theme, the graduation day literally marks the end of support of DICT for the trainees. But the post-training support is deemed necessary for the graduates to grow and make it to the online freelancing community. The training equipped the necessary skills and knowledge for the trainees to work online, and the certificate they received from the training served as passports for them to be hired by online clients. Post-training support is another matter. What does DICT do after the training?

According to 11 respondents, DICT should still help them after the training. They clamored for various provisions, including equipment, clients, online jobs, and free Internet connection. Some also clamored for mentoring or coaching and guide in entering the online freelancing, which were should have already been provided by the trainers as they are expected to share their journey in online freelancing. It is important to note that DICT has facilities equipped with limited computers and free Internet connection in provincial offices where the public, including DJT graduates, can make use of. As DICT's DJT program is a job enabler, and not a job provider unlike agencies like PESO or DOLE, it is of importance that provision of online jobs or clients by DICT to the graduates is beyond the agency's control.

Marketing and Promotions

Various marketing collaterals are strategized to gather applicants for the trainings. Usually these collaterals are released at least a month prior to the screening and selection of participants. Marketing collaterals include: Tarpaulins posted in key areas in the rural community, especially in the city, municipal, or barangay halls. Posters posted in bulletin boards that inform the public about the DJT training and how to join the training. Digital posters are also posted and shared in the official Facebook page of DICT Visayas Cluster 2, whose evident reach allowed a better and easier approach in gathering participants. To some extent, local and community radio stations are also effective in promoting and publicizing the training offering. Not that only 25 final participants are selected to join the training, and it is ideal for the DJT implementers to gather at least more than double applicants for them to carefully select the and fill in the required number of trainees. There were cases in DICT VC2 areas where not even 25 applicants took part in the screening, and it is assumed that the marketing and promotions prior to the screening day are to be hold responsible for the low turnout of applicants.

8 respondents agree that publicity should be improved by DICT VC2. One respondent shared that it is only through word of mouth from her peer was she able to know about the training opportunity, not from tarpaulins, Facebook posts, nor radio announcements. Among the 8 respondents of these theme, one expressed how an evident LGU support is also helpful in making DJT more known to its community. As the LGU is the “head” of the municipality or city, its announcements are but valuable to the constituents. Promoting DJT by the LGU provides more reach and more confidence for the participants to think of DJT as a safe and credible training program for them to join in.

None (satisfaction)

This theme refers to answers of respondents that are “Nothing to improve,” which implies that they are satisfied about the whole training and there’s nothing more that the agency implementer should consider revising or improving. There were 5 of the respondents who are satisfied.

The question on what DJT should improve on is important to be raised in this study as we want to determine whether DJT deserves continuation or halt. The answers of 281 respondents for OPQ1 affirm the graduates’ desire of improving and enhancing the program that will benefit them and future participants of the program. Should there be answers like dissatisfaction, such point would raise concern in halting the program.

Table 5.2

Open-Ended Question 2 (OEQ2): “What can you suggest to help improve the program and provide continuity of graduates' online freelancing involvement?”

Post-Training Provision and Support of DICT

This theme refers to various provisions and support that DICT is suggested to provide after the training to the graduates for the latter to make it online. This suggest the graduates' needs in able for them to make it in the online freelancing community. Although DJT only provides the trainees to be equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills for online freelancing, the trainees clamor for post-training support so that they can be successful online and continue their involvement in online freelancing.

There were 380 responses all relating to such theme, which takes up the majority of answers for OEQ2. These answers include provision of ICT equipment (laptop, desktop, etc.), provision of stable Internet connection in the nearest DICT Office or Tech4Ed Center, and utilization of the nearest DCT Office or Tech4Ed center. It is implied that when one work online, one must have a device or equipment with him or her. All tasks done remotely are through the computer. During the training days, the selected trainees are provided with laptops or desktops they can use. They should however return their equipment during the graduation day, which signifies the end of the training. When a trainee who happens to get employed online during the 21-day campaign returns his or her borrowed laptop to DICT on graduation day, an issue on his or her continuity in doing the job surfaces. The graduate's equipment however is beyond the agency's capacity. Inasmuch as they wanted to lend their equipment to the graduates, there is shortage and scarcity as the equipment will also be used in another training. Thus, it is always reminded by the DJT coordinators that purchasing an equipment is an investment for the graduates as they embark in their online freelancing journey. Their equipment would serve as their weapons if online freelancing employment was a war. In terms of provision of Internet connection and utilization of the nearest DICT Office, it is no secret that DICT offices have a free wifi connection installed for the public to use, known as the Free Wifi For All program of DICT. Users can access the Internet for free in public areas, including DICT Offices. The graduates can make

use of these facilities and provisions as they go on in their freelancing career.

Follow-ups of Graduates

It is important to know that when graduates feel that they are of value to the department, even after the training, casually following up on them and their whereabouts, they feel more appreciated and cherished. The more they pass on a positive word of mouth about the training once they feel valued.

Of the 289 codes that were relating to this theme, suggestions for OEQ2 like cluster-wide online meetings, follow-up systems, quarterly meetings, and elections of batch officers reveal the desires of the graduates to be followed up. Cluster-wide meetings allow the graduates to also meet up with other batches and locations, where they can find relatability being graduates of the same training program. This would also entail networking and growing of peers to other online and potential freelancers. Quarterly meetings were also suggested as follow-up sessions by DICT to the graduates. Lastly, elections of batch officers which were initiated since 2019 by DICT VC2 during graduation day has been deemed importance and of value for the cluster. This entails easier monitoring of the graduates with point persons to represent the batch. Another classic example of the importance of forming a group and electing a set of officers is the one that happened in the Bayawan City batch, where they formed a group and elected officers, and then instituted a startup company where they provide digital services and solutions to clients, applying all those learning they received from the training.

**Post-Training Activities
Gatherings of Graduates**

and Gatherings of graduates after the training allow for the batch's being active in the community. This activeness is also tantamount to awareness where the public can know of their presence and eventually encourage the interested members of the community to take part in the online freelancing opportunities, the very same advocacy that the ICT Industry Development Bureau (IIDB), the premier implementing bureau of DJT, advocates for. This activeness also allows for potential applicants and future trainees of the training, as it becomes more known through the graduates' gatherings.

133 responses relating to this theme were gathered as suggestions for the graduates to continue their freelancing careers. Respondents said that when there are forums among themselves, webinars by their fellow batchmates, and more and other trainings provided by DICT where they can participate in, they feel that they are more active in the society. There were sharings that some of their batchmates know more or have deep knowledge of a certain topic, and it is beneficial for them to attend a webinar discussed by their batchmate who is an expert of such topic.

Post-Training Online Job Support by DICT

Aside from ICT equipment like laptops or desktops and Internet connectivity to be provided by DICT VC2 after the training, graduates also clamor for online employment support from the implementing agency. Although support should have finished right after the training, graduates seek for further support to help them advance in their online freelancing career. These support refers to strategies and means for them to land into online jobs and seek for clients.

These post-training online job support suggested by the graduates include clients provided by DICT. Although DICT is not mandated to do so, as the department is more of an enabler by providing trainings related to online freelancing, some 5 respondents demand for clients being provided by DICT, so that they can really work online. There were also suggestions related to this theme like job matching programs, where, for example, DICT VC2 would prepare a “job fair” where companies and clients would appear in one event, and the graduates will have to join and try to apply in each company. Another one is for DICT VC2 to create and establish an online portal for all graduates. This website will enlist all graduates and their portfolio, and clients can visit such site and select which ones qualify for the available jobs that they have. One suggestion is also to teach students to find clients, which would sound absurd, because such is the very core of the training – where students are taught how to land into online jobs.

Nothing to Improve

This theme refers to a response where the respondent is satisfied of DJT and there is nothing more to improve. 1 answered “not at all” pertaining to this theme.

Gathering answers from the graduates in answering the question, “What can you suggest to help improve the program and provide continuity of graduates' online freelancing involvement?” is very important to determine what are the means and ways

to improve DJT. With the goal of DJT achieving a digital countryside, gaining answers from graduates who experienced the training first hand is equal to establishing a strong foundation in providing recommendations that can help improve the program.

As online workforce in rural communities becomes an evident factor for a locality to be considered as being a digital countryside, these suggestions by the graduates to improve DJT and for them to continue their online freelancing involvement allows for highlights and important considerations for those involved in DJT – DICT itself as the implementing agency, the LGU being the benefactor, partners and stakeholders – to carefully consider the suggestions by the graduates themselves who underwent the very training.

A total of 808 codes summed up into 5 themes were gathered for OEQ2.

Table 5.3

Open-Ended Question 3 (OEQ3): “What other projects/programs by DICT that you want to participate in and why?”

Other trainings and webinars

The ICT Literacy Competency and Development Bureau (ILCDB) is the arm of DICT in terms of digital literacy. It provides trainings and webinars intended for the promotion of various digital topics from cybersecurity, digital governance, programming, etc. The Digital Literacy Training Project seeks to promote digital literacy for the special needs sector such as out-of-school of youth, senior citizen, and persons with disability through the conduct of trainings. The project aspires to increase ICT Literacy in the Special needs sector so that they would be able to cope up with the current trends and livelihood (NICTEF 2019).

In online freelancing, and at some point in traditional employment, certificates are very important in landing into jobs. The more certificates you can provide and show in your portfolio, the more likely you are to be hired. Clients even are not after the educational background of the applicant. This might be the case why some 197 codes pertaining to other trainings and webinars lead OEQ3’s tally. Various other trainings and webinars ranging from various topics make up the theme. Graduates clamor for participation and attendance in DICT’s various free webinars, as they may need these digital certificates to land into an online job. Apart from the evident certificates, the graduates wanted to learn topics that would be of help to their careers.

DigitalJobsPH

Formerly Rural Impact Sourcing, the program aims to promote and develop the online freelancing industry/home-based outsourcing through advocacy workshops and technical trainings in the rural areas. This is intended to create meaningful ICT-enabled jobs in socio-economically disadvantaged areas in the country (NICTEF 2019). This theme suggests of the graduates' desire to join other DigitalJobsPH trainings aside from the training that they joined in. It is important to note that DJT has various training courses, with specific modules, e.g., Website Development, Graphics Design, Online ESL, etc. This also means that one participant may join and learn the Website Development course, but would not learn the Graphics Design course. Eventually, when you work as an online freelancer, the more skills that you have, the more likely are you to be employed.

This might be the reason why some 11 respondents want to join other DJT trainings. It is not disallowed for training graduates to join another training, but chances are given more to those who have not joined any yet. This is another testament that graduates are satisfied of the training and they want to join another one to further their skills and learning, which leads to more chances of working online.

Tech4Ed

The Technology for Education, Employment, Entrepreneurs, and Economic Development (Tech4ED) project promotes digital inclusion by establishing e-Centers as access points for ICT-enabled services to various communities. The project addresses the issue on bridging the digital divide in the country by bringing ICT facilities to the unserved and underserved areas (NICTEF 2019). Aside from various e-platforms, Tech4ed also provides basic digital literacy trainings in the Tech4Ed centers and, recently, webinar offerings.

As in the first theme, the graduates would want to learn more that will help upskill them and receive certificates that are considered as passports for online employment. Through the Tech4Ed trainings, 9 codes relating to such theme pertain to desires of the graduates to be involved in these trainings.

DigitalJobsPH Trainer

This theme is different from the second theme in that the former pertains to graduates joining another DigitalJobsPH training as a participant again, while this theme is the interest of graduates to become a trainer who will teach and train potential freelancers. DICT Central Office highly encourages the DJT implementers to hire and tap trainers who are products and graduates of DJT itself.

4 respondents expressed their commitments in also becoming a DJT trainer to share and re-echo what they have learned from the training and as working online freelancers. By doing this and expressing such interest, this would imply how grateful they are of the training and how passionate they are in teaching others.

Free Wifi For All and DICT facilities

The Free Wi-Fi Internet Access in Public Places Project, rebranded as Free Wifi For All, aims to provide free broadband Internet access to cities and municipalities nationwide. Through the project, free public Wi-Fi will be made available in public plazas and parks; public libraries, schools, colleges and universities; rural health units and government hospitals; train stations, airports, and seaports; and national and local government offices (NICTEF 2019). Each province of DICT VC2 also has at least one DICT Office where there is free wifi connection that the public can use. Most of the facilities too have a hub or center where the public can make use of, where equipment and connectivity are available.

As online freelancers, it is a must that they have an equipment and stable Internet connection for them to work on their online jobs. 3 respondents may have limited access to Internet that they are interested in making use of the free wifi connection provided by DICT. Given that working online is tantamount to being connected to the Internet, availing of DICT's free Internet connection allows the graduates to spend less in terms of connectivity. The public can also plug in their devices to the digital hubs, facilities of DICT, so it means less expenses for them in terms of electricity or other utilities.

PNPKI

The Philippine National Public Key Infrastructure (PNPKI) allows for citizens to digitally sign electronic documents using safe and secure blockchain cryptographic tools. Especially during the pandemic, where offices began shifting to a work-from-home setting, citizens have realized the value of PNPKI in signing documents electronically, eliminating or reducing the paper-based system of physically signing important documents.

1 graduate responded to this theme and it must be because he needs to sign a digital document safely and securely. It is highly encouraged that online freelancers enroll their accounts to PNPKI so that if there are electronic documents where they have to affix their signatures, it is safe and secure provided the blockchain technology behind such.

ICT Proficiency Exam

The ICT Proficiency Certification Examination is designed to evaluate the competence of an individual to perform programming or systems analysis and design functions and is equivalent to a Civil Service Eligibility for highly technical government ICT position. This is an alternative for one to earn a civil service eligibility aside from the CSE Professional and Sub-Professional Examinations, intended for programmers and systems developers.

1 graduate expressed his interest in taking this exam provided by DICT not only to get a certificate but also for the possibility for him to land into a job in the government. There are also other opportunities that graduates seek for, not only online, but also government positions, considering the benefits a government employee has.

A total of 226 codes were collected and sorted into 7 different themes for OEQ3, "What other projects/programs by DICT that you want to participate in and why?"

This open-ended question is important as this would shed light in defining DJT from the perspective of the graduates and determine who can benefit from such. As the graduates now have knowledge of what DJT is, asking the question on which other programs or projects provided by DICT they want to join in just solidifies the foundation of DICT in promoting its advocacy of bridging the digital divide. Aside from DJT, there are other programs that DICT provides in terms of countryside development and each one is linked to DJT. For example, as graduates end their journey after the graduation ceremony of DJT, what happens to them if they want to work online but have no equipment or Internet connectivity, yet? They can make use of the facilities by DICT with free wifi connection. They may also upskill and learn additional knowledge by joining the other trainings and webinars provided by the department. PNPKI can also help them in terms of online or electronic documents. Most of the graduates also expressed their interest in joining other DigitalJobsPH trainings either as participants or as trainers. This just simply encapsulates the definition of DJT in the perspectives of the graduates. This also proves DJT's intention in accomplishing its goals of providing opportunities for IT-BPM development in the countryside, where our graduates, who come from different walks of life (unemployed, PWDs, single parents, senior citizens, students, out of school youths, underemployed, among others) are benefitted.

Table 5.4

Open-Ended Question 4 (OEQ4): “How has DJT/RIS changed your life?”

Employment Opportunities and Income Generation

DJT’s primary goal is to provide online opportunities in the countryside. Where rural communities have the traditional ways of earning income like farming or fishing, what else are available when your locality is situated in an area where opportunities are low? Major cities, like Metro Manila, Cebu, and Davao, all reap the rewards of being IT-BPM centers where people can work and earn through digital services. In rural areas, with scarcity of available jobs, citizens tend to leave their hometowns and move to these centers to earn. The introduction of online freelancing tends to eliminate or reduce such notion. With online freelancing, citizens of rural communities and the countryside can work for the IT-BPM industry without having to leave their municipalities or cities. Though the DigitalJobsPH training, citizens of these rural communities can learn how to work online and be equipped with the necessary skills. Online freelancers earn at par or even more than those who are working in bricks and mortar.

An overwhelming 103 codes denoting this theme realizes and solidifies the fruitful bearing of DJT, not only for DICT in realizing its advocacy but most especially for the training graduates who are now working online and generating income. It is also clear for the respondents how DJT has provided them not only jobs but opportunities in making it successful in the online freelancing industry, by being equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills. There are sharings from the respondents how much they earn and are more than the basic salary and minimum wages in the country. As the survey was conducted during the early period of pandemic, some respondents also shared how they are grateful of not losing their online jobs compared to those who were unfortunately retrenched or displaced.

Digital Literacy and Upskilling

What DJT provides are not jobs but rather what are needed when a rural community person wants to work online. As the proverb goes, “Give a man a fish and you feed him for a day. Teach a man to fish and you feed him for a lifetime.” The training equips the trainees the necessary skills and knowledge on how to make it in the online freelancing industry. Most trainees know how to use computers, but the training becomes an avenue for them to maximize the use of computers, applications, and platforms for their own benefit in entering the freelancing industry. Upskilling happens when the trainees learn new skills apart from those they already know of.

Upskilling is very evident from the answers of respondents for OEQ4. 61 of them expressed how generation of new knowledge and learning transpired throughout the course of the training. Upskilling is very important especially that clients are after the skills of the freelancers, and not on their educational background and other factors. This is evident to some graduates who may have not finished a degree but are able to land into an online job. Respondents have expressed how they have become skillful enough to land into online jobs. They now know how to create and develop websites, or use various applications to do graphics design, or what are techniques applied in social media management. What the trainees learned are more than the basic digital literacy, on how to use a computer, but the necessary knowledge for online freelancing, which are not taught in various curricula.

**Self-Confidence,
and Development****Self-Growth,**

Graduates not only learned the technical skills (hard skills) needed for online freelancing but also important values needed in working online (soft skills). Given that working online is different from traditional work, there are added values that graduates shared they have developed upon joining the training and by learning from their trainers who are also freelancers.

The values of time management, emotional gain, self-confidence, self-improvement, change in philosophical views, and other optimistic and positive changes were some of those revealed by the respondents under this theme. 55 codes were sorted to belong to this theme. One respondent shared, “It changed enough to be more hard-working and finishing task on time.” This pertains to the respondent being more proactive in finishing the tasks assigned to him especially that tasks are not only evaluated by the quality of work but also time bound. The more effort an online freelancer exerts for a certain task with a given time frame, the more will the client be of praises to him. At some point where a client likes the quality of work of his freelancer, the more will the former raise the payment or provide bonus to the latter. This theme is not the main objective of DJT, which develops the personality of the trainee, but it has become an indirect effect that the training has brought about to the participant.

Financial Stability and Support

Perhaps financial stability is what entices freelancers to make a living out of freelancing. Financial stability is the ability of declaring financial freedom, where one controls his or her finances instead of being controlled by them. It is also synonymous to making life decisions without being overly stressed about the financial impact because funds are readily available, and as a common term defines it, “can afford.” Financial support is the ability of someone to provide and remit parts of their finances to beneficiaries, most especially to families.

29 respondents have expressed financial stability and support that they gained from the training. With DJT equipping them the necessary knowledge and skills, and eventually landing to an online job and earning an income, the pay is higher in online freelancing especially clients are overseas with higher service payments. Related to this theme, there were respondents who answered that one was able to pay debts, acquire wealthy possessions, house renovations, buying ICT equipment, and financial support to family, among others. Indeed, DJT has become fruitful in terms of providing not just learning and employment opportunities for the trainees but opportunities that would secure their financial stabilities to provide and support their beneficiaries, especially their families.

Flexibility of Time and Ability to Work at Home

Most online jobs do not have a required time for freelancers to report to work. Unlike the “8 to 5” setting in traditional brick and mortar jobs, most clients give freedom of time to their freelancers. For example, a freelancer is asked to report 40 hours per week, but attendance may be staggered. Or perhaps, a freelancer is given a time frame or deadline to finish a certain task. His or her attendance may not be checked, and only the submission of his or task during the given deadline will be considered for payment. That is the idea of flexibility of time in online freelancing. Being able to work at home or at any location the freelancer desires to work at, as long as there is Internet connection, is another life-changing idea coming from the respondents. Where in traditional jobs, parents usually miss important occasions in school of their children because of work, or OFWs missing the growth of their children being far away from each other, online freelancing provides a more relaxed condition as jobs are done at home or at locations desired by the freelancer. With this, they have more time for their family and loved ones, not missing any occasions and even watching and guiding their children grow.

Travelling, shared by some respondents, is more rampant in online freelancing. With jobs that can be done through the use of laptops and laptops are portable, and the flexibility of time that freelancing provides, travelling and working has been made possible more than ever. In traditional jobs, one needs to apply for “leaves” to be able to travel, among other things. But a certain term, known as digital nomads, are rising. These are usually online freelancers who travel at the same time work especially in beach paradises. Another respondent shared that she is a full-time mother and a full-time online freelancer in one. While working as a housewife in the day, she can support and provide for her family by being an online freelancer at night, while everyone is asleep. Other codes that relate to this theme include convenience of work and job satisfaction, as time really is part and parcel to a worker’s satisfaction throughout his or her career. 13 codes related to this theme have been recorded.

Capacitated Marginalized Sectors DJT's priority beneficiaries are members of the marginalized groups. This includes out-of-school youths, unemployed, underemployed, students, PWDs, and senior citizens. Of note is that DJT is implemented primarily in rural locations in the countryside where opportunities are scarce and rare. DJT capacitates this group and provides opportunities for them to grow and learn skills that they might have not discovered.

In OEQ4, some 10 respondents have identified themselves as members of the marginalized sector but have benefitted from the training. Among them are solo or single parents, OSY, PWD, senior citizens, a recovering stroke patient, and self-supporting students. They shared how the training helped them advance in the community amid being subjected to multiple discrimination. This provides an interplay between DJT and the marginalized sector in providing opportunities for them to be capacitated through the training program that will upskill and reskill them. As rural communities are deprived of opportunities and chance to grow and prosper financially, DJT has been fruitful in enabling and making the community render capable of opportunities that await in the freelancing industry. Not only are those residing and living in major hubs, like Metro Manila, Cebu, or Davao, can contribute to the IT-BPM industry. Online freelancing, which is a subsector of such industry, allows and provides opportunities for rural communities to take part and play an active role in venturing into the IT-BPM industry. As freelancing can be done at any place at any time, wider opportunities can be provided to the countryside. With community members in the rurality being able to adapt in technology use, an idea of a digital countryside can surface. Simply put, being digital means using computers and the Internet as a way of life, and with online freelancers thriving and growing in the rural areas, the concept of a digital countryside takes place. The marginalized group, as they have identified themselves, benefitted and continue to benefit as online freelancers with the training they received from joining DJT. Their answers are of utmost

importance in answering the objectives of this study.

Growth of Peers, Networking, and Partnership

This theme refers to the growth of the trainees in terms of the increase in their peers, network of fellow online freelancers, and partnerships with various institutions or stakeholders.

7 respondents expressed that they gained new friends with their fellow batchmates, more connections with other people, an easy partnership with government projects being products of DICT's DJT training which would mean websites of LGUs, and a widened network of fellow freelancers here and abroad.

Setting Up of New Business

Some trainees chanced upon the idea of setting up a business venture or applying what they learned from the training in supporting small-scale businesses of their own.

There were sharings that the income that they received from working online allowed them to use as capital for business ventures. As discussed in OEQ2 under the 'Follow-ups of Graduates' theme, there was a batch in Bayawan where they formed their own group and set up a startup digital agency to cater to digital services. There was also 1 respondent who already is a business owner who transitioned her business online after learning digital skills from DJT. In this day and age where the pandemic has affected mobility in areas with lockdowns limiting the movement, transitioning online will most likely help businesses survive. This is one of the topics that is included in the DJT module.

Skills Sharing

Skills sharing is when the trainees have the idea and capacity of sharing what they learned to others who also deserve to learn the same training. This is not an objective of DJT but has become an indirect effect of the trainees' compassion in helping others.

5 codes pertaining to this theme have been collected. According to these respondents, DJT provided an avenue for them to share what they learned to their acquaintances and peers.

Uncertainty

Uncertainty refers to answers of significant respondents who have not felt or experienced changes in their lives after joining the training. They might have not been working online or have not applied what they learned from DJT to the real-world scenarios.

Those who are uncertain number to 3.

OEQ4 is perhaps the most important question raised in the study. The graduates being asked how DJT/RIS has changed their lives provides the absolute answers in determining whether DJT has become fruitful over the years for Region 7 and 8. A total of 296 codes were recorded for the themes in OEQ4.

Most of the beneficiaries of DJT belong to the marginalized group, and knowing how DJT provided an impact to them allows us to gather significant generalizations on what the relationship of DigitalJobsPH is towards capacitating the marginalized group and eventually leading to a digital countryside.

The notion of the respondents expressing that they have experienced and are experiencing positive changes validate the Impact Sourcing of Theory of Change. Its proponent, the Global Impact Sourcing Coalition, asserts that impact sourcing seeks to lay out the anticipated path to impact that a specific organization, program or business practices. DJT, being an impact sourcing training program, created and revealed positive changes after its participants in Region 7 and 8 expressed the many facets of changes they have encountered after the training – from employment opportunities and income generation to skills sharing that will benefit the other members of the society. DICT, being the government agency in charge of implementing such program, also fulfills its mandates of the national ICT agenda.

The Anchored Instruction Theory has also become evident in the very nature of DJT. As respondents revealed their need for ICT equipment and their interest in joining other trainings and webinars of DICT, the theory of emphasizing technology-based learning where students take technology as the carriers and use the reality of the living world, as the main contents, especially during the training proper where they use tools and applications utilized in online freelancing and the 21-day campaign where they are asked to look for online jobs, to ultimately solve problems, has been highlighted. Aside from this theory, the Online Collaborative Learning or Collaborativism as coined by Harasim points out the values of the Internet in providing learning environments to foster collaboration and knowledge building among the trainees. Their clamor and demand for an improvement of faster or stable Internet connection for the training duration signifies the importance and value of the Internet in the training.

The Human Capital Theory in DJT is also evident with the respondents being grateful of DJT as a non-formal education becoming an investment and as a generator of externalities, where the respondents revealed fruitful bearings upon entering the online freelancing industry from which their learnings were taken during the training.

Numerical Analysis

Although the study is qualitative in nature, there are questions that are not open ended and the data may be of use in answering the research objectives. The following summarize this analysis.

Of the 238 respondents, 40.4% are males while 59.6% are females, of which, the age of the majority is 28-29 years old. This is also true to the total number of trainees who underwent the training for the 2017-2019 duration: most of the population

are females. During the 2019 run of DJT in Region 7, the International Labour Organization (ILO) partnered with DJT Visayas Cluster 2 to conduct special trainings in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, and Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, for an exclusive women-only training to support their women empowerment advocacy. ILO also provided a soft skills training apart from the technical training provided by DICT. Thus, it is expected that majority of the respondents would be females. The respondents' average age of 28-29 years is also tantamount to the average age of participants who joined and underwent the training.

Most of the respondents also come from the Dumaguete City training location. They are followed by the respondents from Zamboanguita, Negros Oriental, and Canavid, Eastern Samar locations. Tagbilaran City (both 2018 and 2019) and Naga City, Cebu follow. 43.6% of the total respondents come from Region 8 (Eastern Visayas), while the rest come from Region 7 (Central Visayas) with 56.4%. Since cascading of the letters, answering the survey, and following up to the graduates were handed down to the locations' coordinators, this may suggest that one coordinator may not have done a strong and willful distribution and coordination of the survey forms to that of the rest with higher outcome of respondents.

Majority of the respondents as well come from the 2019 locations (79.8%) while the 2018 locations complete the chart with 19 (20.2%). Unfortunately, none of the 3 locations in 2017 have a representation. This implies that there is not enough coordination with the graduates in 2017 or there is no more active interaction between DICT's coordinators and the graduates themselves. This would also mean that DICT should have a more proactive approach in contact tracing the graduates in 2017. Considering that 2017 was the pioneering batch of DigitalJobsPH, this would mean

that tracing them after the training was overlooked, and perhaps due to this reason that tracing graduates a year after has been taken into consideration. Having 2019 as the batch with the most number of respondents justifies the trainings being recent and so coordination with them was intact and controllable.

62.8% of the total respondents comprise of graduates who underwent the Digital Marketing and E-Commerce module, followed by both the Website Development and Social Media Marketing and Advertising courses at 36.2%. Content Writing follows at 18.1% of the total. In 2018, during the year-end accomplishment national awarding of the program that happened in Zamboanga City, Visayas Cluster 2 was awarded with the most number of, and actually the hardest, comprehensive trainings conducted. This would automatically imply that majority of the respondents would really come from such module. On the other hand, per record, Web Development is the next course with the most number of trainings around Region 7 and 8 in the time period, so it was also expected that such module comes right after the comprehensive.

As for the affiliation, 42.9% answered that they are unemployed, 26.4% said that they are currently online freelancers, and 15.4% expressed that they are affected by COVID-19. Note that this survey was carried out during the early situation of COVID-19 in the country, beginning April 2020. Unemployment may be representative of the current global pandemic condition where thousands of Filipinos have been displaced and lost their jobs due to the ill economic effects of the pandemic situation. 26.4% of the respondents being online freelancers also reinforce and support the a part of them have landed a job in the online freelancing industry. In the next few discussions, thorough and in-depth analysis shall explain the factors why these

graduates have not landed into online jobs. What could have been the reasons for such? With them being part of the marginalized group, do their conditions affect their being hireable online?

Amid the pandemic, working online has been seen as one of the best alternatives to earn an income for workers who lost their jobs. 51Talk, the partner of DICT in implementing Online English as Secondary Language (ESL) module nationwide, expressed that they have never experienced a peak season as this. Since Chinese, those who were first affected by the pandemic, were not allowed to leave their homes, they instead would make use of their times at home or online to learn and study even if quarantined. Due to this, demand was high for 51Talk teachers most especially that Chinese are their customers who want to learn English. Filipinos, being known for one of the best English speakers as recognized by Chinese themselves, were tapped to man the operations of 51Talk as online teachers. Various marketing strategies were executed by 51Talk to fill the supporting capacity of their needed teachers to answer the growing demands of their partner clients in China. Meanwhile, 51Talk executives asked assistance from DICT Visayas Cluster 2 to help promote awareness so that they can gather more online teachers.

This assumption would clearly support the fact that while traditional brick-and-mortar workers lose their jobs this pandemic, the same is not true for those who are working online. Indeed, some BPOs, with the regulations of citizens not going out or being limited to leave their homes, let their workers work from their home in which they allow their computer sets to be brought home to their employees' residences for as long as they have Internet connection. This clearly supports that online work is alive while traditional businesses have been shut down or operations ceased.

59.6% of the total respondents answered 'Yes' when asked if they have found a job or are working after the training, while 40.4% or 38 of them answered 'No.' This suggests that more than half have benefitted from the training in terms of landing a job, may it be online or physical work. With certificates duly signed by DICT given to those who finished the training, they can use these as attachments when they apply for a job.

In this day and age where technical skills are but considered more by employers, as evident in the automations of their operations, owning a certificate from the training gives proof of how skillful the trainees are technically, with employers considerably prioritizing them than the rest. A DJT graduate in Negros Oriental shared that when she applied for an online job, she presented two training certificates to his now-client: one, a National Certificate (NC) II in Computer Hardware Servicing as provided by Technical Skills Development Authority (TESDA), and the other, a DJT graduate certificate. With no offense meant to the former, the DJT certificate was considered more by the client who was looking for a digital marketer.

Another graduate from Dumaguete 2019 expressed how she is thankful to DICT for offering such kind of training. She shared that had it not been because of the pandemic, she could have flown to China as she was hired by an international client to work for them as an onsite digital marketer, with another sufficing training to undergo to. Currently, she still works for them and anytime soon, they will push through with their plans when restrictions in travel and logistics be lifted.

There are also graduates who already have jobs while they joined the training. They belong to the Underemployed sector who are seeking for another venture – perhaps, they were not fulfilled in the jobs they were into. After the training, though,

they still continued with their work amid being online freelancers at night or during free time.

Being graduates of DJT also entails the chance to become the next trainers. A graduate from Eastern Visayas in 2018 was hired as a trainer in 2019, seeing his potentials as a medalist, synonymous for being outstanding, during the training. Another Digital Marketing and E-Commerce graduate from Bayawan City was tapped by DICT VC2 to handle the Web Development training in Zamboanguita, Negros Oriental, a year after. These and other similar stories are true for a number of graduates where they were tapped, instead of external DICT pool of trainers who work in the online freelancing fields, as the trainers.

There are also graduates who are professionals of fields outside of the ICT roof. Since the training is designed to suite a general audience and not really expect participants to be tech-savvy or those who come from an IT background, trainings house a mix of various participants who may have graduated in college. There were those who finished elementary and secondary education, some certified public accountants (CPAs) in the making, engineering graduates, and other sorts.

Although an advantage to have earned a degree with computer-related subjects to help them ace the trainings, most of the trainees selected have not finished schooling yet. There were a number of trainees from Bayawan City who were fast food crew members, Dumaguete City with hog raisers, Tagbilaran City with tour guides and housewives, and a lot else.

The training is not biased for persons with disabilities (PWDs). These marginalized members of the community are very much welcome to join the training. For the fact that working online does not mean having to commute or travel farther,

online freelancing is ideal for PWDs since they can work at home. A concrete example in DICT VC2 is the participant in Sogod, Cebu, where one participant cannot walk with her two legs since she is a polio victim. In Laguna, one graduate finished outstandingly even if she has cerebral palsy.

Senior citizens are no strangers in DJT. Almost every location has a senior citizen who completes the group. In Dumaguete City, a retired banker pursued the training; while another 62-year-old finished with medal in Bayawan City. They both have online careers now. Age is just a number.

Of those who answered affirmative, 27.7% answered that they found online work, 14.9% answered they are into physical work, while 13.8% answered a combination of both. This implies that a number of graduates were successful in landing a career online, which would be one of the goals of the training – to help the marginalized in establishing a digital career in the countryside. Although the percentage may be few in statistics, the sampling was too few to be representative of how the program as a whole be considered successful or not. Still, this number, in the program's infancy stage, is reasonable enough to prove that there are graduates who made it in the online industry. A thorough study, perhaps in a few more years, must be done in order to perform a quantifiable measurement of success of the program. DJT graduates earning employment online is a significant achievement for the department and the cluster implementing such. There are factors that may have hindered for the majority not working online, and this will be discussed thoroughly in the next few paragraphs.

Of those who answered online work or a combination of both, they revealed that among the kinds of online job that they do are being a digital marketer, content

writer, website manager or developer, social media manager, ads content writer, English as Secondary/Foreign Language (ESL/EFL) teacher, online marketer, graphics editor, and content creator. All these jobs are the jobs that you see in the online freelancing community. You don't regularly see these jobs in traditional companies or BPOs but are available online especially in online job sites like UpWork, 51Talk, Onlinejobs.ph, 199jobs.com, and a lot more. And these are the very same topics that are included in the modules of DJT.

Note that as of writing, there is no degree in the country that has the same in-depth topics as part of their curriculum (except for web development and graphics design) – not even in other countries too. There are online certification trainings that offer such, but there is nothing like what DICT offers – trainees have nothing to pay for.

A digital marketer makes use of the web, including social media, to help clients reach their goals in penetrating the online market. To reach more customers, various branding schemes and marketing approaches are done by the digital marketer to help promote a client's business or service.

A content writer develops and creates articles and product reviews of a certain product or service of the client to help their social media campaign successful and gather a massive crowd. The wider its reach, the more potential customers are. It should be taken into consideration that contents should be original or attractive for a campaign be successful – something that is taught in DJT.

A website developer, under the DJT module, creates and develops a fully functional e-commerce website for clients. More than being a webpage, an e-

commerce site has business transaction functionalities like purchasing orders and payment methods.

A graphics editor creates various visuals and static multimedia to produce a visual appeal that will help bridge a business and their potential customers. Having beautiful and eye-catching visuals is tantamount to potential customers and helps buyers of a certain product or service be enticed of what is being seen by the eyes.

These are some of the online jobs that the graduates who are working online have revealed they are currently doing. The training DJT program provides allows them to face this arena as they are equipped with the necessary ICT skills needed to work for clients' needs and demands.

It is quite revealing that graduates who are working online earn a significant amount of sum – a range that may not even be available in traditional physical work. 22.3% of those who work online earn between an average of Php 5,001 to Php 15,000 a month – beating the average income of common Filipinos under a minimum wage scheme, 13.8% earn less than Php 5,000, and 10.6% earn Php 15,001 to Php 30,000. Significant answers were also found out with 2 respondents answering Php 30,001 to Php 45,000 and another 2 respondents with Php 60,001 and higher. The implication of this, regardless the amount earned monthly, is that online freelancing becomes an avenue for online workers to earn, more than enough of the average.

There is not much investment to prepare when someone works online. Compared to traditional work where workers might be spending for their uniforms, food, cost of living allowance, and transportation for daily commute, online workers instead have to invest for the equipment and Internet connectivity.

With this notion, earning such amounts as stated above are advantageous especially that other expenses are not being considered by the worker. Although online workers still need to pay taxes, the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) still has a lot to do in terms of finding out who are working online or not. As workers might not declare what is true in their income online and BIR, per status quo, still has no mechanisms to verify such, an effective system must be considered if the latter is after such.

Most online workers also have their freedom of time. While traditional workers are constrained with a dayshift of 8 to 5 PM in a Philippine setting, online freelancers, mostly, have a flexible work arrangement where they can work at any time for as long as they can complete the project in a specific deadline or duration. DJT graduates who work online have shared how beneficial working online is in terms of work–life balance, since they have time for their families and time for work.

With the question on how long they have been working online since the end of their training, the longest one answered 2 years and 5 months. Other respondents have 1 year and 8 months and 1 year and 5 months. The average answers of the respondents is 2-3 months. This simply implies the longevity of the DJT graduate in working online after the training. With this statistics, it is very evident that graduates have seen how advantageous working online is compared to the traditional one. With ever-changing clients and projects that online freelancers may end up working with, it is amusing to find out how many have survived and have been reaping rewards from working in this kind of scheme. While it is an open secret that attrition rate is high in traditional BPOs, the same is not true in online freelancing. Many online-working graduates choose to stay working online.

One clear disadvantage of online freelancing is that for government contributions (Pag-Ibig, PhilHealth, SSS) not mandatory and freelancers are self-contributing, they may not be as regular paying as the traditional workers where their companies automatically deduct these from their salary.

Of those who answered that they have not landed into online jobs yet, majority of them (30.9%) said that it is because of the poor or absence of Internet connectivity in the area. This implies that since rural communities are the primary targets of the program, Internet connectivity is also an issue in the area. There were instances like in Bindoy, Negros Oriental, training that a dilemma in connecting to the Internet during the training is rampant. Training in DJT is synonymous with connecting to the Internet since the activities and projects must use the Internet. There were also locations targeted for next year that were scraped off because Internet connectivity is an issue. In Northern Samar and Northern Cebu, there were two instances where the supposed trainings were cancelled because of poor connectivity. Although DICT may help in assisting for the Internet connectivity (the partner LGU is supposedly in-charge to provide Internet connection), there are areas that are very remote that service providers cannot reach or have limited infrastructure in the areas. Even pocket WiFis or home broadband WiFis, the last resort to Internet connection, cannot suffice the needs.

With this in mind, it is obvious that some of the trainees also come from far-flung areas where Internet connectivity is rare or scarce. This would be the primary reason why majority of those who have not landed into online jobs make it difficult to work online. Being online means being connected to the Internet. And inasmuch as they want to apply what they have learned from the training, perhaps subscribe to a

stable Internet connection, they could not do so since providers cannot reach their areas. In Eastern Visayas, especially in the Northern Samar area, there is an issue of adequate Internet connection. This must be a clear proof why some other graduates have not landed into a career online.

28.7% answered that they do not have devices like laptop or desktop to pursue an online career. Of course, being connected to the Internet is not enough. In a similar view to make it more contrasting, while it is good that there is water supply in a barrio, it would be useless without pipes, faucets, and buckets for the water to flow and reach. Similarly, online freelancers, even if they have a good Internet connection, will have hands tied if they do not have equipment like computers and other devices for them to work their freelancing jobs. During the training, it is DICT or LGU that provides the equipment for the trainees to work on. However, once graduation is done, the equipment that was lent are pulled out so as to cater to and make used by other locations. Trainees are encouraged by the trainers themselves, who have evident working careers, to invest for a good laptop or desktop as these are their guns that they need once they enter the online freelancing arena.

14.9% agree that their portfolio or resumé is not enough to begin an online job. Although building profiles is part of the discussions during the training, graduates may have not earned enough certificates or working experience to help them buff up their qualifications. As mentioned, there is a different routine in the online freelancing community. While employers in traditional jobs are after academic or educational backgrounds of their applicants, such does not matter for clients online. Whatever their career might be in, it has no bearing to be employed for as long as applicants underwent training or have relevant work experiences. As a matter of fact, the trainer

of Naga, Cebu run in 2019, who has a strong online presence, is a nurse by profession. Thus is also the reason why the DJT program is not biased in terms of the educational background of the trainees.

13.8% answered that they lack guidance on how to work online. Although it is part of the training, perhaps the trainees have been stuffed with a lot of technical information overload and this part where it was discussed must have been skipped. Trainees might have also been introvert in applying online. While other successful DJT graduates have been aggressive in applying for an online job, submitting applications from here and there, there are those who are timid and reserved when applying for an online job.

A significant 2.1% of the graduates answered that they do not see themselves working online. It is quite ironic that they joined and applied for the training in which they know in the first place, with a pre-orientation being handed to them, that the training will be about online freelancing. These may be underemployed individuals who are testing waters and finding out during the training that they prefer the traditional physical jobs.

Other responses (1.1% each) include issues with availability of schedule, regular electrical interruptions evident in their areas, pregnancy conditions, and no responses to their applications. It is true that some graduates take online freelancing as an extra income from their day jobs. Perhaps, those saying that they have issues with their schedules mean that there is a conflict of time and schedule to make ends meet. Electricity is also vital when working online. As in the same case in rural areas where Internet Service Providers cannot service their rural areas, some communities too have no electricity to begin with. This is equal to them not applying what they have

learned from the training since their hands are tied from doing so. There were those who were pregnant during the training, especially in Tagbilaran and Naga, that, after the training and after giving birth, they would focus on motherhood and step aside online freelancing in the meantime. There were unsuccessful stories too. There were DJT graduates sharing that they have submitted applications from here and there, but they weren't just lucky enough to be accepted. This are all a sad reality that may be beyond the controls of DICT, partner agencies, and other stakeholders.

However, amid these issues, DJT graduates find a way to become active in the society. When asked if their batch has already formed an organization among themselves, 40.4% answered 'No,' 38.3% 'Yes,' and 21.3% 'We are planning.' Although not required after their graduation, DJT batches are encouraged to form an organization that can help catapult building rural BPOs in their areas. As in the case of Bayawan City, after graduation, they formed their "Bayawan Integrated Online Services" or BIOS, where they are a mix of DJT graduates and online freelancers in the city, and accept client jobs. While there are those members who are good in graphics, others in content writing, and others in web development, they divide among themselves who are in charge of something to finish the task or project of the client. Their common ground is that they seek for online jobs around their community or online, and they do the tasks required of them, with sharing of income equally dividing among themselves. Having noticed this technique, the DJT coordinators throughout DICT VC2 encouraged their batches to do the same thing and pattern such model from Bayawan City. True enough, Bindoy created their Bindow WebWorks team and an unnamed group in Zamboanguita. This implies that even if most members might come from the marginalized sectors of society, it has no bearing in teaming up to

create an organization that can help them post-training, even with a little help coming from DICT.

Of those who answered 'Yes' in this question, 71.2% said 'No' while 28.8% answered 'Yes' when asked if they had already activities organized or supported by the organizations that they formed. These activities include workshops, election of officers, meetings about having their own ad agency, parties, local business seminars, capability development trainings, and planning sessions. This also shows how the trainees are hungry in making themselves known in the community. All these can be considered an aggressive approach for others, especially stakeholders, to notice. This also implies that they do not want to stop learning after the graduation. With workshops organized and seminars attended, it means that they want to learn more and be abreast with the current trends in technologies. It makes the agency happy when, without instruction, the graduates among themselves have initiated putting up their own ad agencies. This clearly shows how passionate they are in building up their careers and eventually earn an income.

It is true that there are members of the society that belong to the marginalized group, but along with the country's progress especially in the ICT landscape, these people must not be left behind for the fact that they are part and parcel to what makes up the nation. With the department being a communications department, it shall see to it that it will harness the ICT landscape without anyone left behind, regardless of social, political, religious, or any other backgrounds.

Chapter VI

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The study reveals that DICT has indeed become an enabler in providing opportunities in the countryside, especially the marginalized groups in the far-flung areas and rural communities. While citizens outside of the major hubs have limited opportunities, either earning an income through the traditional jobs present in their localities like farming and fishing or leaving their hometowns behind and going to major cities to work, DICT provides awareness that there are indeed digital jobs available without having to leave their places. DICT also capacitates them and enables them to work on these digital jobs by providing a training that will upskill them on online freelancing.

While not all places can become IT-BPM centers, especially those in rural communities, with a lot of factors for companies and investors to consider and take in mind, local government units can still provide digital opportunities for their citizens by instituting online freelancing in their localities, which eventually leads them to becoming a digital countryside. DICT's DigitalJobsPH program allows the citizens of these areas to experience IT-BPM industry in their own homes. As partners of DICT's DJT implementation, LGUs have an important role to play if they want to provide opportunities for their constituents.

DJT has been effective and has met its objectives as far as Central and Eastern Visayas regions are concerned, with success stories and significant changes that the participants of these locations have experienced during and after joining the training.

DigitalJobsPH is a program of DICT that capacitates those living in the countryside, especially the marginalized groups, by providing a training on online freelancing. Online freelancing is a sub-sector of the IT-BPM industry where online freelancers rely on gigs or short- and/or long-term contracts or projects without having to work in a usual brick and mortar setting. By having an ICT equipment and by being connected to the Internet, online freelancers can work anywhere and in most cases, anytime. Online freelancing becomes an alternative for far-flung areas to earn a competitive income without having to leave their communities. The very nature of DJT is to provide a training that equips and upskills the participants so that they can make it to the online freelancing industry. Priority is given to the marginalized sector of the rural communities, especially OSYs, unemployed, underemployed, students, PWDs, and senior citizens. These persons may be discriminated because of their background, but these persons can also make it in online freelancing.

Indeed, DJT has met its objectives in building capacities for the marginalized sectors. They are given opportunities to contribute to the society by equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge to make it to the online freelancing industry. The real-world approach of DJT allows the trainees to learn skills and make use of tools that are used in online freelancing.

Given the responses gathered from the participants in the open-ended questions, DJT deserves continuation as DICT has become an enabler of providing opportunities in the countryside through these trainings provided by DJT. As far-flung and rural areas have limited employment opportunities with salaries that are competitive, online freelancing trainings are a big help for these areas to flourish.

Conclusion

With millions of pesos poured in as funded by DICT for the program to flourish, the program deserves continuation for the fact that it provides benefits in the countryside. However, a more proactive approach shall be taken into consideration especially post-training where majority of the graduates are left to questioning whether they pursue online freelancing or not. If statistical evidence be considered in future studies, perhaps a 5-year or 10-year analysis, and the results still yield the same that only a few make it online, then that's a point for scrutiny, not in terms of implementation but post-training mechanisms.

There are factors that keep the trainees from pursuing an online career. Factors, that may be beyond the controls of the department or stakeholders or location per se, but the mere fact that there are those who made it online are a proof that there is success after training. These successful graduates may have advantage over the others, like having equipment and connectivity or what not. While others, aside from having none of these, may be hampered by their location, with the training primarily focusing on rural areas where not only Internet connection is an issue, but even electricity. To begin with, trainees may not have enough money to invest into buying equipment and devices that can help them in their career online.

The program is clear in developing the countryside where citizens are limited with the traditional ways of earning an income. DJT/RIS is a good and solid foundation to begin the IT-BPM sector in such rural communities amid their location. The result of this study yields clamor from the graduates for DICT to assist them post-training. Some suggestions by the trainees may seem impossible, like providing them equipment to pursue their online career. But there are other alternatives that DICT

offers, like the Tech4Ed Centers where the public, and even them the DJT graduates, can make use of to work online.

A lot of other clamors have also been requested by the graduates which can never be denied, but a lot of success stories have also been identified. Some of these can be reviewed by DICT, especially in providing opportunities that they can easily assist with. But there are other suggestions that might be impossible to be achieved, but discretion lies upon the department.

For the program to prosper, DICT must bear in mind that the graduates lay a strong foundation for it to be fruitful in the years to come. There are graduates who are now the trainers. There are graduates who help cascade information from DICT to their localities. And even if these trainees belong to the marginalized group, their voices are but the voices of all other Filipinos.

Some “unsuccessful” graduates who have not landed into online jobs must also try to re-evaluate if they have failed to do something that the successful ones did. Those who work online have been aggressive in working and seeking employment online while others remain timid.

Overall, DJT has met its objectives in building the capacities of marginalized groups and eventually transforming rural communities into a digital countryside. The presence of online freelancers in these areas is also tantamount to making the locality competitive in hosting the IT-BPM industry through the online freelancing subsector.

Recommendation

For the program to not die a natural death, it is recommended that the Department of Information and Communications Technology review its post-training approach for the DigitalJobsPh Technical Training. There is no doubt for the pre- and during-training approach as they have been successful in providing communications to gather trainees. It all lies after the graduation where some graduates have not landed into online jobs. This however is not representative of whether the program is successful or not in the entire country. It is too early to conclude that the program is successful or not in the perspective of the implementation in Visayas Cluster 2 but the responses of the respondents have validated DJT's objectives of capacitating and empowering the marginalized sector.

DICT must consider partnering with other bigger companies in providing similar trainings or supporting the DJT's program objectives. DICT already has external linkages with LGUs and other NGAs but there has been no partnership with a bigger company, aside from 51Talk in providing the trainer or ESL/EFL module. It would be ideal for DICT to ask assistance from other companies especially for equipment provision or their workers being displaced to undergo DJT, as a fallback for their jobs lost due to the pandemic.

DICT should have an extension arm or unit that would oversee how the countryside be developed digitally not only capacitating these marginalized groups but also coping up and surviving the digital infostructure and infrastructure so that all these will be in place.

It's been noted that the graduates clamor for longer training days (the longest course so far only has 12 days). The DJT graduates also express their desires for

DICT to help them after graduation, providing suggestions like assisting them in getting online clients or other trainings that can equip them the necessary needs to work online, apart from the technical training itself. These must be considered by DICT although in fairness to the agency, they have provided such online trainings in a series of webinars once the pandemic came about; however, the graduates may have overlooked these opportunities, or there might be a communication gap by the department in cascading down invitations for them to join to such.

With millions of fund allotment for the program, it would be very likely for DICT to provide more avenues for the graduates to work online, although DJT is the initial step in doing such. Budget for the logistics and technical implementation of the program has been allocated but post-training measures have not been itemized. If DICT wants to include the parameters in making DJT successful through its graduates working online, then additional budget must be taken into consideration especially that such reinforcement is another matter to attend to.

The strongest factor of the training are the trainees and the graduates. These graduates can help DICT and other online freelancers reach their niche, and it is recommendable for DICT to bank on the talents and skills of the graduates. Note that some of the graduates are now the trainees, re-echoing what they have learned and applied during the training. It is very ideal for DICT to continue assisting these trainees even after graduation because they become an extension arm of the department even if they are not employees per se of the agency. They can help, in their own little ways, advocate for the department and provide a positive branding for the agency who is in its toddler years as an established executive arm. The DJT/RIS graduates are already a solid foundation for the country to prosper even more in terms of online jobs. They

can create a network of talents that can help boost the economy, especially that we are recovering from the ill effects brought about by COVID-19 economically.

In this day and age where technology plays an important role in the advancement of the country, online freelancers should not be left alone since they are part and parcel of the IT-BPM industry, which contributes significantly in the country's economy especially in the previous years. And the marginalized group, OSYs, Unemployed, Underemployed, PWDs, and SCs, among others, must also be valued in the advancement of such industry. Appreciation to DICT must be noted for spearheading and implementing such DJT program to bridge the digital divide among these marginalized groups. DICT must devise strategies on how the training can even be more fruitful, given that we are in the age where digitalization is but becoming the norm.

Majority of the graduates are not working online, inasmuch as they wanted to, but factors that contribute to such are but in question especially that there are factors that are beyond DICT's controls. It is highly recommended though that support post-training by DICT must be reinforced. Careful consideration by this government agency must be taken into account so that fruitful and significant findings will take effect in the next few years. And another study must be done to carefully analyze how the program has been.

In its toddler years, the DJT/RIS program has yielded positive results, but only countable. More strategies for the graduates after their training must be considered so that they can pursue their career online. It will be a waste for DICT to provide trainings, where hundreds of thousand budget is doled out for a single location, if the department cannot reap its objective to provide online opportunities for these graduates.

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Appendix A. Communication Letter

April 16, 2020

Dear Rural Impact Sourcing/DigitalJosPH Graduate,

Christ's Peace!

I hope you are feeling well especially that we are facing the crisis brought about by the global pandemic.

It is with my humblest intention to include you in my master's thesis entitled, "DIGITALJOBPH TECHNICAL TRAINING (FORMERLY RURAL IMPACT SOURCING): THE GOVERNMENT'S APPROACH TOWARDS A DIGITAL COUNTRYSIDE."

I am a Master of Development Communication student at the university of the Philippines Open University. I have chosen this thesis topic because this is very close to me, especially that I am the regional coordinator for such program of DICT. I wanted to know how the program has been doing especially in its early years. This can help us design a more proactive approach in continuing the program and even helping you as our graduate.

It is rest assured that all your answers will be confidential. They will be included in the statistical data for analysis that the study will bring.

You may answer the online survey at the convenient of your homes by following the link below.

<http://tiny.cc/DICTPostTrainingSurvey>

Should you have any clarification or anything that I can answer, you may reach me through this e-mail address: jpdomen@up.edu.ph or my number 09152596064.

Thank you very much and I look forward to your answers. Here's hoping you can fill out the survey on or before June 16, 2020.

Best regards,

Joshua Eleazar P. Domen

MDC Student, UPOU

Appendix B. Online Survey Form

DigitalJobsPH/Rural Impact Sourcing (DJT/RIS) Graduates' Assessment and Post-Training Survey - Region 7 and 8

This survey is intended for graduates of DigitalJobsPH/Rural Impact Sourcing since its inception. This is to measure how graduates have been doing after the graduation. This survey will allow the project implementers devise an approach to cater to the growing needs of graduates' post-training activities.

This will help in assessing and continuing improve DICT's Rural Impact Sourcing/DigitalJobsPH training.

CONFIDENTIALITY NOTICE: We value and protect your personal information in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173). The information you shared will be stored in a database accessible to DICT Only. These will be used to serve as a reference for assessment of program, for future planning, for communication, among others.

* Required

Email address *

Your email

Last Name *

Last Name *

Your answer

First Name *

Your answer

Age *

Your answer

Gender *

Female

Male

Current Address *

Identify your current location you are residing in.

Your answer

RIS/DJT location

Tell us the city/municipality where your training was held.

	Bogo City 2017	Maasin City 2017	Allen 2017	Sogod (Southern Leyte) 2018	María, Siquijor 2018	Bayawan City 2018	Tagbilaran City 2018	Borongan City 2018
Location	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Region *

What is the region where the training location belongs to? (Ex. Central Visayas)

Region 7 - Central Visayas

Region 8 - Eastern Visayas

Other:

Year *

What year was the beginning date of your training?

2017

2018

2019

Course/Module *

What was the module of the training?

- Online ESL (51Talk)
- Digital Marketing/e-Commerce (Comprehensive)
- Virtual Assistance
- Search Engine Marketing and Advertising
- Social Media Marketing and Advertising
- Content Writing
- Graphic Design
- Website Development
- Other:

Affiliation

- Senior Citizen
- Person with Disability/Differently Aabled Person
- Indigenous Person
- Single Parent
- Student
- Out-of-School Youth
- Unemployed
- Underemployed
- Overseas Filipino Worker
- Online Freelancer
- Affected by COVID-19
- Other:

Page 1 of 2

1. Are you currently working right now or have you found a job after the training? *

Yes

No

1.1 - If your answer to No. 1 is 'Yes', please tell us the nature of your job. *

Online work

Physical Work

A combination of both

N/A

Other: _____

1.2 - If your answer to No. 1.1 is 'Online Work' or 'A Combination of Both', what kind of online job do you do or have you done since the end of your training? (Ex. Full-time Digital Marketer). *

Your answer _____

1.3 - If your answer to No. 1.1 is 'Online Work' or 'A Combination of Both', how much do you earn on average per month? *

Less than Php 5,000

Php 5,001 to 15,000

Php 15,001 to 30,000

Php 30,001 to 45,000

Php 45,001 to 60,000

Php 60,001 and higher

N/A

Other: _____

1.4 - If your answer to No. 1.1 is 'Online Work' or 'A Combination of Both', how long have you been working online since the end of your training? (Ex. 2 years and 2 months) *

Your answer _____

1.5 - If your answer to No. 1 is 'No', what do you think are the reasons why you have not landed into an online job yet? *

Poor or absence of Internet connectivity

No devices (laptop, desktop, etc.)

Training is insufficient

Resumé/profile portfolio is not enough

Lacks guidance on how to work online

'I don't see myself fit working online'

N/A

Other: _____

2. What do you think should DICT do as a post-training activity to support graduates in their needs? *

Ex. DICT should do another round of training for the graduates

Your answer _____

3. Has your batch formed an organization among yourselves? *

Yes

No

We are planning

3.1 - If your answer to No. 3 is 'Yes', have you had activities that your organization has organized or supported?

Yes

No

3.2 - If your answer to No. 3.1 is 'Yes', what are these activities and when?
Ex. Christmas Charity Event (12/25/2019), Content Writing Workshop (12/26/2019)

Your answer _____

4. What can you suggest to help improve the program and provide continuity of graduates' online freelancing involvement? *

Election of batch officers

Quarterly meetings

Cluster-wide online meeting

More trainings conducted by DICT

Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc.).

Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub

Webinar by fellow batchmate

Other: _____

5. What should the RIS/DJT improve on? *

Ex. Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the requirements

Your answer _____

6. What other projects/programs by DICT that you want to participate in and why? *

You can also suggest certain topics for seminars/webinars/trainings that you wish DICT would conduct on.

Your answer _____

7. How has DJTIRIS changed your life? *

Your answer _____

Send me a copy of my responses.

Page 2 of 2

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Google Forms

Appendix C. Transcript of Answers to Open-Ended Questions

<u>Respondent</u>	<u>5. What should the RIS/DJT improve on?</u>	<u>4. What can you suggest to help improve the program and provide continuity of graduates' online freelancing involvement?</u>	<u>6. What other projects/programs by DICT that you want to participate in and why?</u>	<u>7. How has DJT/RIS changed your life?</u>
1	Longer training days and more advanced lessons	Election of batch officers Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Webinars and talks	It opened doors to me and I can easily partner with the government for projects. I also widened my network and connections.
2	Comprehensive training on the subject	Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Virtual assistant	A bit
3	make training easier for starter	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	ePayment and Cyber Security	Yes. a lot of improvement

4	Training days should be longer enough especially if it is a comprehensive one, and even its not so that there would be enough time for the to comprehend what is being taught since not everyone is as "techy".	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	comprehensive training on graphic designing	through the training i was able to learn new knowledge and skills that is very helpful to this generation.
5	Skills that is in demand for the beginners so that they can easily land jobs.	I think All of the above must be checked here but the most important that the gradutes will land a job and not left them behind. Although they have the skills but the confidence them to apply is another hindrance factor of why they don't pursue on applying on the freelancing jobs. It shoud have a couching system so that every gradutes will land into jobs.	Many. the more skills that you have the higher chance to land job.	Its Okay.
6	Training days should be longer in order to master the topic.	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Video Editing and Graphics	Yes, I learned a lot like making portfolio for my job hunting.
7	More trainings please	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Follow up with the graduates	NA

8	Training should be longer in order for us to really apply it in the online world and DICT graduate should have a group like linkend in order for recruiters to have an access to us for hiring purposes.	More trainings conducted by DICT, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Anything that involves online jobs.	Yes, in my computer knowledge.
9	More trainers and more time so that scholars can finish the requirements on time	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Personality training	I learned that there are many ways to earn money in online platforms you dont need to apply or become an employee
10	Good job!	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).	N/A	DJT/RIS changed my life to inspired my self to work online with less stress.
11	Stable internet connectivity and ICT ready and equipped classroom and training facility.	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Seminars relating to financial aspects and rates of output and online tasks depending on client and output complexity.	I've become involved and equipped with technical ideas and knowledge for professional skill applications.
12	Longer Training dates, don't cramp up schedule	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Webinar by fellow batchmate	N/A	Many aspects actually

13	The students should focus on gaining knowledge and experience rather than focusing on delivering outputs..	Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT	They should conduct an intensive training for jobs like: setting up Fb Ads and Google Ads How to become an SEO specialist How to become a virtual assistant How to become an appointment setter	DJT helped me build a career as an online freelancer/Virtual Assistant. I Work and earn money from the comfort of our home. And on top of that, I get to spend more time with my family. I am a working mom but a full time mom as well. I can say that I am financially stable. I invested some of my earnings to open a food business with my sister. we will start serving as soon as the covid19 crisis ends.
14	I am satisfied and appreciated with this training that they offered to us. nothing to improve on.	Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I think graphic designs, because I am interested in designs and I want to learn and improve my skill	This time nothing at all yet but maybe in the future. But this training fill up my knowledge about SMM so kudos to all. Thank you for sharing your ideas about social media marketing to us.
15	Shoul be longer time to finish the requiremnts	Election of batch officers Cluster-wide online meeting Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	To have an online based tutorial. E-learning	I got an ideas on how to work online.
16	Training should have more time face to face	More trainings conducted by DICT	Training customer service	No

17	None. I'm satisfied of what happen on our training.	More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	It my pleasure to participate any training from DICT. Because iknow it will help me to my success	It help me to become a better person.
18	I think the DICT should have it's own training facility or permanent location to conduct a training.	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Animations.. another skill to develop.	Made me more confident when looking for a job
19	Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the requirements Mentoring with the new graduates.	Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Dropshipping, Graphic Design, Animation, Lead Generation, Video Editing. Because they are also in demand jobs online.	I am very much grateful for DJT program of DICT because I gained basic knowledge about online freelancing for free. I had the confidence to apply in different freelancing platforms. I am also grateful for my trainer.
20	The internet should have a secure and stable connection	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Virtual Assistance	Its changed when it comes to understanding about digital marketing.
21	Tasks that are given should have more longer time to do.	More trainings conducted by DICT	Photoshop tutorial video editing	Gain confidence and courage to face challenges through task.

22	training days should be longer to accomodate more time to finish the requirements	Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	e commerce	a lot from zero knoledge to 8
23	Should be required to teach voluntary to some out of school youth in the municipality.	Election of batch officers Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	More elaboration about FB ad marketing.	Proper way of doing SMM
24	Training days should be longer	Cluster-wide online meeting	Web dev training	I was able to enhance my skills because of the training
25	Provide more trainings	Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).	Virtual assistant	They enhancing my skills using digital.
26	Internet connection should faster.	Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Trainings/ Webinars/Semin ar	It does not change ..It give me more knowlegde about selling your skills .
27	During our training we had struggle of our internet connection. So hopefully next time they should also provide the stable connection.	More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	As long as it could help me I will participate.	It really change my life because of dict I became a knowledegable person how to find job through online.
28	Focus the training on one subject at a time	Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, You should focus on teaching students how to find clients since that is where most freelancers struggle.	SEO	I had more local connections.
29	Bringing out clients	Clients provided by DICT or projects	Webinars	A little bit improved

30	N/A	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Maybe seminars	N/A
31	Training should be in specific niche so that every trainees can focus what work was to be done.	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	I want to be train more about graphic designs, and graphic arts.	DJT/RIS changed my life in so many reasons: * I am now a computer literate. * I learn how to manage my time. * Self confidence, self motivated. * Discover new skills. * And now, I can be part of this online automated world.
32	The DICT should recruit more competent trainers.	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).	Virtual Assistant	Rural Impact Sourcing changed my view on freelancing. That you can work from home and everyone can be a freelancer. No matter what is your status in life, whether you normal person or PWD as long as you have the proper knowledge. RIS added experience and knowledge to my web development skills. It served as a stepping stone

				for a much higher chance of getting hired at upwork.
33	Longer training days and internet accessability	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Digital Jobs Ph - SMM training	Because of DJT/RIS I was able to find a job online.
34	Training days should be longer.	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Anything and I'm so willing to participate anytime.	I learned a lot of things through this training, applied it to my bussiness and it really works. Now life is easy as it is.
35	Training days should be longer and devices to be borrowed even after the training.	Quarterly meetings Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc).	Web dev and graphics design.	DJT makes me digital literate.

		Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub		
36	Training needs more actual and good internet, must extended days training	More trainings conducted by DICT	Website designing, and graphic designing to enhance our skills	I learned a lot about social media marketing. And have more skills
37	Internet connection should be improve so that other requirements can finished before the training end.	Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	I love to be part of the training program so that I can share also my knowledge to other who eager to learn more.	I am more competitive enough to work in any company.
38	A reliable internet connection could be of big help especially in the SMM niche	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Virtual Assistant and Video editing because I like data entry jobs and editing videos	Yes, I feel like I have elevated my static knowledge in the world of freelancing, I learned that it has a wide variety of opportunity
39	To provide strong wifi connection	Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	None	I learn more digital skills

40	It should be longer in order for trainees deliver great results and understand more the topic	Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Training on virtual assistance in order to have more knowledge about the job	It gave me confidence and opportunities in online freelancing even though I don't have any job yet rather than sticking to online tutor
41	Must improved their WiFi connection and more time to finish the said task.	Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Digital marketing	It gives me confident to work online jobs.
42	not to compressed the training days so much that as a result trainees are forced to do all the tasks without really understanding or learning anything from the lesson	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	virtual assistant training, social media campaign and booster training	it made me more confident, and this confidence hugely changed my life
43	Training days should be longer	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I want to enroll E-commerce	Internet has a lot of opportunities to offer. We just only need to discover it more and should leard how to earn income from it.

44	Securing venue and stable internet connection during training first before conducting a training	More trainings conducted by DICT, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Voice Account VA trainings or webinars	It helped me gain skills that I now used as a VA to my client
45	Training days should be longer	More trainings conducted by DICT	Focus on developing web	Not Much
46	Yes, the training days should be longer.	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Adobe Photoshop Virtual Assistant.	DJT/RIS change my life in a way that it helps me finding online home based job..
47	Trainings should have any follow up group activities such as meetings, gatherings, and other related trainings. This will help the graduates have sustainability in their career and groups before finally letting them off the hook.	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Trainings on coding/programming	DJT/RIS had opened more windows of opportunities for me, both on the online and physical work area.
48	Availability of facilities and equipments and stable fast internet.	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Online workshop, seminars, webinars and trainings.	It opens to more opportunities for me about online jobs and e-commerce and e-marketing workspace and work at home. Thank you.

49	Training days should be longer to ensure in depth discussion of topics without needing to rush the trainer because of the schedule. If in depth training is done, graduates will feel more prepared for embarking on their online journey. Coaching after the training would also be good to guide graduates on how to build their online presence, impressive portfolio, applying for jobs, writing impressive resumes and cover letters. These are important to get them noticed by employers online.	Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I'm interested in learning Shopify, Amazon FBA, eBay listing, Magento, and other eCommerce platforms. Off-Page SEO is also another one. Video creation/editing is also important because social media is big on videos these days. More people engage with video content posts compared to photos.	It has opened the world of online freelancing to me and has given me a way to be with my son more. I'm lucky to have been chosen as one of the scholars.
50	Longer training s	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Web developing, this is my favorite	I dont know

51	Publicity in rural areas & urban poor settings	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate, Job Matching	Workshops & trainings	DICT-RISTT E-Commerce has opened up fresh perspectives on digital opportunities which will impact societies in general. If the backbone of Philippine economy rests on MSMEs, the digital landscape is its horizon.
52	Availability of fast internet connection	More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Messenger automation, Animation	It has realized my untapped potentials
53	Actual process in getting online clients in order the trainees to have an idea in the real world of freelancing. Participation of MSME affects the process and cooperation is always very low. Why not create a trainee's website/Social media that will serve has his/her own portfolio. MSME should serve as actual client.	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	I want to teach others. But I need to experience the actual world of online freelancing that I can share with my trainees too.	I learned to push myself through the limit. It boosted my confidence in getting online job specially that my portfolio was improved.

54	Trainings should spend more time/days. And hoping that RIS/DJT will continue again and again in order to help more.	Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Video editing Training/seminars, comprehensive SEO training, follow up webinars etc	I was mold to become a productive citizen inspite of how covid affect us nowadays. I was able to improve my learned techniques in digial marketing particulary in social media. Helped some of my friends by sharing the skilss i learned from the training. Hoping and looking forward to explore more opportunities in digital world. Thanks and Godbless DICT!
55	Focus On Specific Training ON a Specific qualified Scholar	Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Digitaljobs	It made me more engaged in the new and basic advantage in digital technology
56	Trainings days should be longer and the internet connectivity must be stable	Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I don't have idea yet.	It did not changed my life yet.
57	Longer training Days	Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Tech4ed	It help me as a therapy as a stroke patient

58	Traning days should be longer so it will not end up.like a crash course, but still i am thankful for the traininf i had attended.	Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	na	Yes, somehow I am now confident to apply in online jobs platform .
59	Specific Skills or Module with enough time to fully teach the steps dealing different situation if different outcome in your work or in your employer in order for fully understand the training and be confident.	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc)., Webinar by fellow batchmate	Seminars about improvement or best way to do each freelancing skills in order to be competitive. I suggest webinar or training in Shopify and should have enough time to teach all necessary topics.	It has changed my life to take a step to the online jobs but not confident enough due to not enough full teach the web development and I was planning to propose to make the website of my previous employer in Saudi but I am afraid I may not give their expectations due to the knowledge I have right now although I have been viewing youtube tutorials but its different with the actual training.
60	Maybe making sure that there is a stable and reliable internet connection during the live training. And training days should be longer to accomodate more time to finish the requirements.	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Social media training	Ive learned a lot of things with the DJT training but not everybody is fitted to be an online freelancer. If there is one thing i realized after the training, what we learned in the training room is very much different when you will be applying for a job. In my case, i have to stop due to health reasons. But it doesnt mean that i am giving up.

61	Training should be extensive	Not at all	Seminar/ actual training	Not at all
62	Provision of ICT Equipment at home	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Graphic Design	Life Changing
63	Provide a laptop to DJT scholars after graduation.	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Web development, if possible, programming and graphic design is a big help.	It was a big advantage to me in applying everytime the employer saw it in my resume that I am a graduate of DJT/RIS and a lot of job positions to apply for.
64	Conduct another training	Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Training related on digital	It opened my mind on how the digital works nowadays.
65	To provide more trainings to enhance our skills more; provide online freelancing job to the graduates.	More trainings conducted by DICT	Topics about social media management and customer service management.	I already taken few steps into the freelancing world. It makes me more confident to face realities in life.

66	Handouts or the lesson notes that are from the trainer will be very helpful so even after training, you still have reference you can look back.	Quarterly meetings Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Helpful skills as video editing, photo editing	It gave me more credentials that I can be more confident and qualified in applying in online work.
67	Should have a follow-up training for certain topics.	Election of batch officers Cluster-wide online meeting Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I would love to participate for another face-to-face training.	It has opened the door for me to freelancing and I have never been so satisfied with my career until I experienced online job. RIS is a blessing to me and my family. Thank you DICT. More power!
68	Training should be longer	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	n/a	It improves my knowledge and skills
69	Small programs and orientations- like different online skills that meets the demand online	More trainings conducted by DICT	Drop shipping, lead generation	It helped me open my mind to all possibilities online.

70	<p>If we are to assume trainees are newbies to ICT, the Digital Marketing comprehensive module should be adjusted to take into account the psychology of learners. Based on my experience (considering I am a certified trainer myself), the current module is overwhelming. The process of learning should not be overwhelming, but should be fun, to be effective and for the knowledge transfer to be more permanent. The learning experience the trainee undergoes should be a positive one not a stressful one.</p>	<p>More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, If graduates will organize themselves into a freelancer group or digital agency, they should be given trainings on management, business, leadership, entrepreneurship and financial literacy as well because technical training is just a starting point. Moving forward as an entrepreneur, they need guidance and assistance with the right agencies that can help them to succeed.</p>	<p>The new normal now is really going online. DICT should offer more webinars, but, perhaps not just on technical or Digital Jobs PH trainings. Considering DICT is the technology agency of the government, perhaps, DICT can also work with other government agencies like DTI, for example, to create more relevant and holistic webinars to Filipinos. The economy is down due to the pandemic, so webinars that can easily empower Filipinos to earn would be relevant.</p>	<p>It has opened a lot of possibilities for me.</p>
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71	comprehensive is too comprehensive / longer time is needed/ the lack of self confidence when skills is required to land the needed job hiring online	More trainings conducted by DICT	I suggest that modules for basic training like Virtual Assistant , bookeeping online, transcribed and how we can be competitive to other applicants	Yes
72	Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the requirements	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT, Webinar by fellow batchmate	I would love to have a training on Web Design using HTML, CSS and Bootstrap 4 since I have gone training on Web Development using WordPress so that I can enhance my skills more in programming.	DJT taught a lot of new things and made me enhanced my skills and make me want to share my skills to others.
73	Before training ends trainees should have prepared resume and check thoroughly by trainer to at least a trainee will be hired for at least one online job	Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Enhancement of resume preparation that will encourage employers to at least try to hire graduate from the course	Had more learning on online jobs and technologies

74	Training should have a longer time period	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Webinars	I acquired skills I can use in the future.
75	Updates on the module.	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Application Development because in this time of crisis everybody needs legit information with just one tap of a finger. Hopefully an intensive program for e-payments too.	I did found another skill.
76	Training should not be crammed. Half-day classes should be enough.	Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Digital marketing	It has opened doors to new opportunities
77	A quick check for graduates regarding the status of their application and provision of guidance in improving their profile and application letters.	Quarterly meetings Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	No idea	It changed enough to be more hard-working and finishing task on time.

78	Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the req's.	Election of batch officers, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Webdev	Gives me knowledge in digital field.
79	Training days should be longer and they should provide fast and reliable internet connection with good facilities.	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Technical Support Trainings	I learned a lot from the training and it helps me find a better job.
80	Training on communication(English).	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT	Training on CSS and Java	I am empowered to build site using wordpress
81	Improve training venues.	I suggest DICT will create a online portal mainly for 'DICT Graduates'. There DICT can provide the graduates an entryway to a variety of helpful information, tools, links to legit online homebased jobs, and a forum between the graduates where they can share thoughts about freelancing and online jobs.	Trainings on essential online tools used by freelancers for their online jobs. (e.g. Photoshop, MS tools such as Advance Excel, Access, Outlook, Publisher, PowerPoint etc.)	Being recognized as DICT graduate is a life changing already. DICT is like giving eligibility to the graduates to work online. Contributing to the online workforce. Forever thankful and grateful to DICT who provided training opportunity to individuals like me, so thank you very much.
82	Training days should be longer to accommodate more time to finish the requirements	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I want to participate in their specific trainings to specialize in a specific niche.	DJT/RIS helped me to be more responsible in handling tasks and tracking what I do. I am also able to wake up early without using an alarm clock since the training days.

83	More time on training	More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	POS courses for businesses	Knowledgeable to online world
84	Training should be longer to accomplish the tasks correctly and hands-on application is very important to be considered in the training so that the participants can apply the actual correct method on the computers.	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Training on Graphic/Visual design, Programming, ESL to broaden my options in freelancing.	It gave me a better perspective that life indeed should go on and that it gave me a chance to be productive even after retirement.
85	Training days should be longer	More trainings conducted by DICT	Seminars or webinars	Not so much right now
86	They should expand their locations to help other people especially on the provinces.	Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub, Webinar by fellow batchmate	Basic IT courses since computer is really useful these days.	Wow, haha. They conducted a really useful seminar that can be used in daily life.
87	Create more Tech4Ed centers and Digital hubs.	Quarterly meetings More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Web design, programming, apps developer.	It gives me more knowledge about the digital world and making me digitally literate.

88	Longer training days and to get together more often to immediately adhere to quintessential information	Quarterly meetings	All of it if possible, not only does this pace way to provide more opportunities but this too can mold characteristics of self sufficient individual that can support the nation as a whole	I've been much more open to the many possibilities and opportunities around me if I look for it
89	Must provide job after the training	Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Another Trainings	Not really
90	hardware	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	should have ESL training, because it's the only job that is flourishing.	a bit...
91	Should be in longer time	Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Webinar by fellow batchmate	Comprehensive	DICT change my life in online industry
92	There should be a specific training course.	Quarterly meetings Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Virtual Assistant and Lead Generation which is highly demand in an online jobs.	As a student, DJT changed my life by providing an extra income thru part-time job

93	More training should be launch	Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I would like to participate any form of training in DICT to improve my knowledge and skills specially in Virtual Assistant, because i need to improve my knowledge and skills in that specific area.	RIS give me so much confident in applying for a Job both offline and online, it gives me a lot of opportunity I got hired by the municipal after the Training and currently i am working at TESDA also i have a partime job online.
94	I hope DJT will improve on opening more room for more participants as there's only limit to 25 per session	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
95	More guide in entering the online freelancing community	Election of batch officers Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Tech4Ed	I now work online, thanks to DJT

96	LONGER DAYS FOR TRAINING	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I WOULD LIKE TO ATTEND TO ANOTHER COURSE OR MODULE OF DJT IF GIVEN THE CHANCE	I BECOME MORE TECHY AS A PERSON
97	There should be shorter but concise number of campaign period to trim down from 21 but more days of training	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	I landed into an online job, more time for my family
98	Nothing, I am satisfied	Quarterly meetings	N/A	N/A
99	Get-together more often after the training	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Tech4Ed	I am now working online!

100	Establishment of hubs in barangays or key areas just like DTI's GoNegosyo Center	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I think if there are cybersecurity trainings by DICT I would glad to be involved in	I am now working online and provide for my family as I have 2 kids and sickly parents
101	Jobs should be provided to participants or guide in landing into jobs after the training	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	N/A	It allowed me to be more particular in clerical stuff and always check and recheck my works in the office
102	Improve venues for trainings	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
103	Longer training days and more time to accomplish the tasks	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A

104	More time for training	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Tech4Ed	I now have multiple gigs or freelancing companies and I would like to train others who would like to become online freelancers like me too
105	Longer period of time for training	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
106	Provide stable Internet connection so that there is no breaks or halts in the classes	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Tech4Ed	From working in fast food chains, I am now working at home able to support my family's needs
107	More training days to finish the tasks,5 days in a week will do	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	As an out-of-school youth who only finish high school, being rejected by companies because of lack of education, I am now working for an international advertising company as a content creator and graphics designer

108	Establishment of freelancing hubs or co-working spaces in DICT offices	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Join other trainings	I am now working online and the certificate I gained from RIS became my passport to landing into online jobs
109	DJT should improve on its trainers and encourage the graduates to also become trainers	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	I can now travel and work at the same time because I am into an online job that has flexible time scheme
110	During screening of applicants, DICT must see to it that everyone is on the same level. There are others who are advanced while others have no idea of what is being taught.	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Tech4Ed	It changed me in terms of being able to provide food on the table
111	DJT should improve its screening and selection of trainees	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	It changed my life for just a bit

112	DICT should always follow up on their trainees especially that others leave the training even if there is a training bond for those who have not finished	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
113	Days for learning should be longer	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	If DICT will establish a coworking space or training center or facility, I wish to make use of such	I am a single mom but with the online jobs that I have, I am able to provide for my children, thanks to DICT's trainings
114	Longer training days but lesser time or if possible, no more campaign period	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Not at all
115	DJT trainers must be well versed and have good command in communicating to their learners	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Tech4Ed	

116	Provide better Internet access	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
117	DICT must have its own venue for these trainings to be conducted – less expenses for the government or partners	Quarterly meetings	N/A	N/A
118	Longer training days as everything is crammed in a matter of 8 days or so	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
119	Training days should be longer	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	I stopped schooling and college drop-out because of financial but I think I can go back to school now since I can support my schooling

120	Better internet access	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	I am introvert but thanks to DJT where I met my fellow trainees, I became more confident especially in landing into online jobs
121	Establishment of DJT hubs in DICT Centers where trainees can do assignments	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I hope to participate in more trainings conducted by DICT	I am now working online and I love this kind of job where I have more time for my family
122	Training days should be longer	Quarterly meetings	n/a	COVID19 pandemic didn't affect me at all because I still have my online job with me. While others lost their jobs, I have something that support me
123	DICT should market DJT to its fullest extent so that many will participate	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	I have additional online gigs after the trainings

124	Better internet connectivity	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I am interested in learning how to create a website for government agencies or LGUs	I was able to send my 2 children to private schools. Before when I do not have online job, they are studying public
125	Longer time to do assignments or tasks	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	I was able to buy a secondhand car
126	As the lessons rely heavily on the Internet, make the Internet connection faster	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Tech4Ed trainings	Thanks DICT, I have a chance to go to China and continue my online job there
127	DICT must improve on its facilities for the trainees to do their tasks or assignments. Not all have Internet at their homes so it would help for DICT to provide areas with free connectivity	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Me and my batchmates were able to launch a digital startup agency for those who want to create their websites

128	Training days should be longer	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Not changed at all
129	Better internet access/connection	Quarterly meetings	N/A	N/A
130	Nothing more, I am satisfied.	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
131	Establishment of DJT hubs	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	N/A

132	Better internet connectivity	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other RIS courses	It gave me connections to other online freelancers not only in our province but the whole of Philippines and other countries too
133	Training days should be longer	Election of batch officers	Trainings on programming/web development	N/A
134	Improve the training's Internet speed	Quarterly meetings	Na	It helped me in my freelancing career and I was able to renovate our house which is now my working place
135	Improvement on the module as I believe some matters are already obsolete and not the industry standards anymore	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	N/A

136	Online freelancing entails stable and fast Internet connection	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	More trainings	My batchmates from Bayawan created our own group where we are a digital marketing agency catering to the needs of those who wants our services
137	Length of training must be longer to accommodate some breathing for the trainees	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
138	Centers with Internet provision so trainees can do their tasks after the training	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings	As a PWD with polio, I am earning at home where I don't need to leave our house to earn
139	Better internet access	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	Not at all changed, just slight

140	Training days should be longer	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
141	Establishment of centers or hubs with Internet connection	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I am interested in Government Web Hosting Services training of DICT to develop websites of LGUS, NGAS, ETC	I'm tapped to develop websites of international brands and gain money from this. Aside from financial, I am emotionally satisfied because the training boost my confidence in applying in online jobs
142	Training days should be longer	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Slightly changed in terms of additional item in resume
143	Better internet connectivity	Quarterly meetings	N/A	N/A

144	Longer training sessions	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Tech4Ed, PNPKI, Cyber security	I was able to buy a laptop to continue my online career
145	Establishment of training venues or hubs that can accommodate multiple people	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings or other DJT courses and modules	I can now afford what my children wants. Although I am not sure until when this will be but I'm enjoying it as of the moment
146	Securing fast and reliable Internet connection is a must	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Free Wifi For All	I learned new things for free
147	Nothing	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	N/A

148	Longer training sessions	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
149	Better internet access	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	Before I'm afraid or has phobia in using computers, now I can say I am improved
150	More time to prepare the assignments or tasks given and improve the quality of Internet connection. Although I have Internet connection in where I live, some of my classmates or batchmates do not have	Election of batch officers	If given the chance, I will attend other trainings by DICT if they are for free just like DJT	It changed me careerwise. I left my office daytime job and concentrated in fully working online.
151	Longer training sessions	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	N/A

152	Better internet connectivity	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I want to become a trainer for RIS/DJT too	I am no longer a son who waits for my parents' allowance, I can now provide on my own and there are times Im the one giving them even if I am just only a student
153	Please I hope DJT can improve its length of the training. I'm shocked that the deadline for a task is nearing but it requires a lot of effort	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Free webinars	Still the same jobless
154	Better internet access	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
155	DJT must improve its venues and facilities where they conduct the training	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A

156	Support of the LGU must really be evident, not only from DICT	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I don't know of other DICT projects sorry	At daytime I work in the LGU, at night time or when I have free time I work online which supports my financial obligations
157	Improve internet access	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Not really
158	Longer training days	Quarterly meetings	N/A	N/A
159	More time to finish the lessons and less tasks as some are burdensome	Quarterly meetings	N/A	N/A

160	Better internet connection	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Still the same before but I have included DJT in my portfolio
161	DJT must be longer in terms of its number of training days	Election of batch officers	More trainings	None at all
162	Establishment of DJT hubs	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	DJT changed my perspective in life. I thought that being old and senior citizen, I am now turning 61, I cannot work anymore. But now, I am partner with my son we are both working online and we enjoy life
163	Please improve the connectivity. Sometimes we have nothing to do because there is no Internet connection in the first place	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	I am more aware of the online careers and opportunities we have in this world. Although I am not yet working online, I see myself working one day when I am ready and when I already have the equipment

164	More training days, less assignments	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	na	I found out I have other skills
165	Adding in or transforming DICT offices into coworking spaces where it can be used as training venues or venues to finish trainees' tasks	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
166	Longer training sessions	Quarterly meetings	N/A	N/A
167	Better internet access	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	The training paved the way for me to find my niche. I am a vlogger, just a small YouTuber with no other means of income. Because of the training I have something to put or add in my contents that I'm pretty sure will help my viewers, and also me for monetization.

168	DJT must improve on its marketing collaterals. Some of my friends do not know that there is an existing training	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	New learnings and skills
169	Longer training days	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
170	Please make the Internet connection faster or not dwindling	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	DigitalJobsPH Web Development course	Aside from gaining friends and fellow online freelancers, my classmates in the training, it also opened more opportunities for me to work sideline. I have midnight jobs and this really helps me because I am a single parent.
171	DICT must consider spreading the word about the training more and more to provide more opportunities to the public.	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	N/A	Not at all changed.

172	More hours for training	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
173	Better internet access	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	DJT SMM	My life has changed in such a way that I am already working online and I left my job in the BPO to concentrate working online. I have more time for my family as I can work anytime.
174	Establishment of DJT hubs	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	New skills
175	Longer training sessions	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Training on web development	As an IT professional, I acquired new learnings that I didn't study during college. I already have an online presence with my own website and I have clients who hire me for their websites.

176	Better internet connectivity so that we can finish on time	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	Just the same
177	Longer training sessions	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	N/A	N/A
178	Establishment of more Tech4Ed hubs or training locations with free Internet connectivity	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
179	More marketing promotions. I never know of this training not until my former workmate told me so	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	I gained a lot of friends, learnings, and opportunities.

180	Better internet provider	Quarterly meetings	None	DJT made me aware of the opportunities online, compared to day-job work. The salary is higher and more competitive than my regular work.
181	Establishment of DigitalJobs hubs aside from the training venues that are accessible to the public to finish tasks or perform assignments	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
182	Make Internet access not just an option but a necessity for the training, if possible even after the training	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
183	Longer training sessions/number of days for training	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	I once had phobia in using computers but now I am more confident thanks to the training

184	Establishment of DJT hubs	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Trainings and webinars	I have become more digital literate,
185	Improve the module as some things are not updated anymore. I know there are new bills or laws regarding online freelancing but were not discussed	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Being a member of the marginalized sector as an out-of-school youth, availing the free training helped me a lot in terms of jobs generation. I am now working online and it proves that even if I don't have a diploma I can still make it in online world.
186	Longer hours for training sessions	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other DJT module	Yes
187	Better internet access	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	Nothing much

188	Establishment of DJT hubs	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
189	More days to learn online freelancing	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	I have a business and with DJT I was able to still sell and earn even if there is pandemic and lockdown because I transitioned to online selling which I learned from the DJT
190	Better internet connectivity	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	None	None
191	Longer training sessions	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	

192	Better internet connection	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Webinar topics like IoT, 4Ri, etc.	DJT served its purpose in providing opportunities to the countryside. There are limited jobs in the province and with online freelancing and good Internet connection I can earn even if there is few oppoetunities from day jobs
193	Please make the training longer	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	The training provided opportunity to grow. I might have not been successful in terms of schooling or education, I can provide proper education to my children as I earn through online.
194	Establishment of DJT hubs	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Web development training	It made me more confident.
195	Internet at some point lags because there are many users accessing all at the same time. I hope this is improved	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	It made me more independent without having to ask money from my parents or family and relatives.

196	Provide better venue, good and stable connection, a trainer who is not only a freelancer but also with good communication skills	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Training on online ESL	I am a teacher by profession but I opted not to practice my profession because I find it stressful. In online freelancing which I learned from DJT, I enjoy working at my own pace at my own time. It's very convenient for solo parents like me.
197	There should be longer training sessions	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
198	Better internet access	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Application development like Android or Ios.	The training helped me a lot in terms of finances. As the pay is bigger and higher online compared to traditional work, I am able to provide more for my family. I learned online freelancing with the help of DICT's DigitalJobs training and I really appreciated the efforts of my trainer and DICT to mould as as freelancers. I am very thankful to the team.

199	Establishment of DJT centers or hubs	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I want to take the ICT Proficiency exam of DICT so that I have a chance to work in the government.	It helped me grow my network being an already existing online freelancer prior to joining the training.
200	The number of days seem lacking, it must be longer	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	A lot
201	Better internet connection	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	VA/virtual assistance course	I learned more digital skills
202	Longer training hours or sessions	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	More confidence in applying online

203	Improve quality of trainers that can really deliver	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Webinars related to social media marketing and e-commerce	It changed me in terms of my perspective in life. Before I felt lost in which job is suited for me. I always lose my determination in working everytime I find it routine. But with the help of DJT, I am now working online and I can say that I like how dynamic it is working online. Different job roles, different tasks. The salary is also higher.
204	Better internet access	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	Not really
205	Training days must be longer	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	N/A	N/A

206	Trainers must really know what they are talking about	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	N/A
207	Training must be longer as it's as if everything is crammed	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Catch-up sessions among DJT graduates	I learned the skills necessary for online freelancing.
208	An Internet connection that can accommodate multiple users all at the same time. Imagine 25 or so trainees connected to one access point.	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	It changed my outlook in working. Before, the chances of being hired is earning a degree or having a backer. In online freelancing, you can prove yourself worthy to be hired by showing your portfolio or your works. The certificate provided by DICT really helped me in landing into an online job.
209	Improve quality of trainers	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	It changed me in terms of being able to provide more for my family.

210	Longer training sessions	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
211	Better internet access	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	DJT changed me in terms of growth in mindset. I became more skillful and compassionate in helping others to also succeed.
212	Not only should the trainees be screened, also the trainers who must be approachable	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	It made me even better in terms of the technical aspects of my knowledge
213	Longer training sessions	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Free trainings and webinars	DJT brought me a lot of blessings. For one, I am now working online. The money I earned from freelancing also allowed me to put up my own buy and sell business.

214	Better internet connectivity	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	None so far
215	Trainers should be accommodating. They are key to the success of the graduates	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Digital literacy trainings - I want to also share what I learned from the training	RIS or DJT proved me that there are opportunities just waiting and you can be successful if you really given efforts to finish the training
216	Improve its campaign in promoting the existence of this opportunity	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	I am more equipped in terms of technical knowledge and skills and I can now contribute to the bills in our house
217	Access to Internet must be given priority so that everyone can comprehend, especially trainees who are beginners	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	I discovered that I have talent. Imagine, an out of school youth who once worked as a cashier and waitress now earns more than those who are blessed in life

218	Longer training sessions	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
219	DJT should improve the quality of the trainers. Our trainer has to invite another speaker to talk about Wordpress	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Continuous improvement
220	Better internet access	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Trainings that will improve my chances of being hired	Before the training, I am a plain housewife, in my 50s, with teenage children. I have basic computer knowledge as I used to work once in a bank as a teller before resigning. The training changed my life as I know more about computer stuff and I am currently working on the side while being a full-time mom.Thanks DICT

221	Better and more aggressive marketing promotions by DICT or the organizers	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	Now more than ever, I can provide for my family due to the learnings I gotten from the training
222	Longer training sessions	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	N/A	Many to mention
223	DICT must see to it that their trainers are really equipped and has a passion for teaching	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	Just a few changes
224	Longer training days and trainers must be of good quality, trainers who are not only book smart but also street smart	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	I'm not yet working online but I will try to become once I have my own computer. I am confident to enter the freelancing community since I learned a lot from the program.

225	Better internet connection	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	I became more aware of the online opportunities
226	Longer training sessions	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Training for social media marketing and ecommerce	I was able to raise money for the operation of my mother through online freelancing. I also have time to stay beside her during hospital admission because I can carry with me my work – laptop and with my own time.
227	DJT trainers must also learn from the students	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	I was able to pay my debts because of working online which I learned through DJT. I am now debt-free and as a matter of fact, I'm the one lending now.
228	Training sessions must be longer	Quarterly meetings	Other trainings/webinars	I am the breadwinner of the family and through the training, I became able to support my family more.

229	Better internet access please	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
230	Trainers of DJT must be well versed and good in speaking, not only in online freelancing	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Digital literacy training	DJT made me more skillful
231	Longer training sessions for everyone to grasp the lessons	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	The training allowed me to widen my horizons as I became more professional in the online freelancing community.
232	Stable Internet connection for everyone to enjoy	Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A

233	I myself am a trainer and teacher and I see that our trainer is not that efficient in delivering the modules, although points to her for being motherly	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	The training changed me in so many ways as to how I value time and effort. Before that I wasn't into online freelancing yet, I would not make importance of the time. But in online freelancing, it taught me to make use of time wisely because we can be cramming in finishing our tasks.
234	Longer training sessions	Quarterly meetings Election of batch officers	N/A	N/A
235	Better internet access	Election of batch officers	Other trainings/webinars	I am more knowledgeable and skillful about computers
236	Longer days for trainings	Quarterly meetings	N/A	N/A

237	Better internet connectivity	Election of batch officers, Quarterly meetings Cluster-wide online meeting More trainings conducted by DICT Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	I want to have more Free Wifi sites from DICT in our locality	More knowledge learned about online freelancing
238	Short period of training, here's hoping DICT consider making the number of days for the course/module longer	Utilization of nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub Provision of ICT Equipment (laptop/desktop, etc). Provision of stable Internet connection in nearest DICT Office/Tech4Ed Center/Digital Hub	Other trainings/webinars	N/A